

DISCOVERIES AT HIGH REDSHIFTS: STRONG EVIDENCE FOR CONSECUTIVE EXPANSION EPOCHS OF THE UNIVERSE THAT PRECEDED THE CURRENT EPOCH OF COSMIC EXPANSION

KARAN R. TAKKHI

PUNE 411015, INDIA

E-mail: takkhi.karan@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The comparison of the redshift-distance relationship for high and low-redshift supernovae revealed the surprising transition of the Universe's expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration. As compared to local supernovae, remote supernovae appear 10% to 25% dimmer as they are further away than expected indicating that the Universe is accelerating (expanding at a faster rate) now at low redshifts and was decelerating (expanding at a slower rate) in the past at high redshifts. Since observed redshifts (z) in an expanding Universe also provide an estimate of recession velocities (the more shifted a spectral line is towards the red end of the spectrum (redshift), the faster that object is said to be receding from us), therefore, it is very disturbing (conflicting) to find that low recession velocities ($z = 0.01$) indicate a faster rate of expansion (acceleration or "speeding up"), whereas high recession velocities ($z > 1$) indicate a slower rate of expansion (deceleration or "slowing down"). Based on pure Hubble flow interpretation (recession velocities arising solely due to the expansion of the Universe), I unravel an undiscovered aspect of inhomogeneous expansion that perfectly mimics cosmic acceleration; I provide the first-ever conclusive evidence in this paper by showing that a purely kinematic interpretation of type Ia supernova sample provides strong evidence for "consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion", rather than "cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration" (Riess et al. 2004). As a result of consecutive expansion, expansion began for remote objects in the preceding epochs of cosmic expansion before it did for local objects in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion; remote supernovae, quasars, and gamma-ray bursts are therefore not only further away than expected, but they also happen to yield a slower rate of expansion, thereby suggesting their deceleration or "slowing down" even with "high recession velocities". As a result of consecutive expansion, preceding epochs of cosmic expansion "appear to be decelerating or slowing down" as compared to the epoch of cosmic expansion that succeeds them – a natural feature of consecutive expansion. The analysis is based on the redshift-distance relationship plotted for 580 type Ia supernovae from the Supernova Cosmology Project, 7 additional high-redshift type Ia supernovae discovered through the Advanced Camera for Surveys on the Hubble Space Telescope from the Great Observatories Origins Deep Survey Treasury program, and 1 additional very high-redshift type Ia supernova discovered with Wide Field and Planetary Camera 2 on the Hubble Space Telescope. The results obtained by the High- z Supernova Search Team through observations of type Ia supernovae have also been analysed. Studies incorporating quasars and gamma-ray bursts to determine how the expansion of the Universe has changed over time have been taken into consideration as well. The results obtained in this paper have been confirmed by plotting velocity-distance relationship, expansion rate vs. time relationship, expansion factor vs. time relationship, scale factor vs. time relationship, scale factor vs. distance relationship, distance-redshift relationship, distance modulus vs. redshift relationship, Hubble residuals, and magnitude-redshift relationship, moreover, the deceleration parameter (q_0) is also found to be negative ($q_0 < 0$). The natural consequence of the type of expansion unravelled in this paper also makes it possible to help solve (i) the "Hubble tension", (ii) an additional perplexing problem that makes the Universe appear to us as if it is "not only expanding faster than before but is also younger than before", and, (iii) the "impossible early galaxy problem".

Key words: accelerating Universe – cosmology: observations – cosmology: theory – dark energy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Using type Ia supernovae as standard candles, the research work conducted by the High- z Supernova Search Team (HZT) (Riess et al. 1998) and the Supernova Cosmology Project (SCP) (Perlmutter et al. 1999) resulted in a very surprising discovery that made the teams win the 2011 Nobel Prize in Physics. By comparing the brightness of the very distant, remote supernovae with the brightness of the nearby, local ones, remote supernovae were found to be 10% to 25% dimmer than their nearby, local counterparts – a direct indication that remote supernovae were further away than expected. Based on these direct observations, a surprising feat was found being displayed by the Universe; a feat so extraordinary that the remarkable results obtained were not even expected. It was the startling, serendipitous discovery of the Universe expanding at an accelerating rate. A research that was originally aimed at observing the expected deceleration of the Universe under the gravitational influence of matter was welcomed by something completely unexpected. According to Filippenko (2001), "This was not the answer we had expected, and many members of the HZT were worried that a subtle error had been made; indeed, Bob Kirshner reflected that "deep in our hearts, we know this can't be right". "If the result was wrong, the reason had to be subtle" (Filippenko 2001).

Incorporating 16 type Ia supernovae in their study, the High- z Team measured not only the distances to those supernovae, but also the velocities at which those supernovae were receding from us. Based on these measurements, the team was stunned to find that the Universe was expanding 10% to 15% more slowly in the past than can be accounted for without a cosmological constant (*Science News* 1998).

Here is an excerpt describing this astounding discovery from "Written in the stars" by the Nobel Committee for Physics – the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, "By establishing the distance to the supernovae and the speed at which they are moving away from us, scientists hoped to reveal our cosmic fate. They expected to find signs that the expansion of the Universe was slowing down, which would lead to equilibrium between fire and ice. What they found was the opposite – the expansion was accelerating".

A mysterious and hypothetical energy of unknown origin, having no explanation in fundamental physics, rightfully termed as "dark energy" is considered responsible for accelerating the Universe's expansion. The simplest explanation for dark energy is the cosmological constant (denoted by Λ) that was introduced by Einstein in 1917 into his gravitational field equations to account for what matched well with observations back then –

a "static Universe" – a Universe "suspended between gravity pulling inward and the cosmological constant making the universe expand" (Kirshner 2004). Cosmological constant was essentially introduced to help keep the Universe distended by providing the necessary repulsion against the gravitational attraction of matter since it was not known back then that the Universe was expanding as observations were confined to the stars of our home galaxy.

However, in 1929, the revolutionizing discovery through the observations of distant galaxies using the 100-inch Hooker telescope atop Mount Wilson in California showed that the Universe was expanding (Hubble 1929); it was not "static" as was being considered. This observation of expanding Universe led to the banishment of the cosmological constant. However, the startling discovery of cosmic acceleration has dramatically resurrected the discarded constant.

Cosmological constant denotes the intrinsic energy associated with empty space or the vacuum. According to Riess (2012), "A contemporary particle physicist would call it vacuum energy, that is, "the zero point energy summing all possible particles in the vacuum," and then would complain that calculating it yields a nonsensically enormous answer". The theoretically-calculated value of the cosmological constant according to the quantum field theory results in a colossal discrepancy – a mismatch between the small observed value and the huge theoretically-calculated value by 120 orders of magnitude (10^{120}).

Using type Ia supernovae (SNe Ia) as standard candles, the expansion history of the Universe has been depicted by the Hubble diagrams (Figure 1 and Figure 5). The observed deviation from linearity provides the ground-breaking conclusive evidence regarding the transition of the Universe's expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration since the distances to the remote supernovae are larger than expected with respect to the local supernovae. "Observations of Type Ia supernovae (SNe Ia) at redshift $z < 1$ provide startling and puzzling evidence that the expansion of the universe at the present time appears to be *accelerating*" (Riess et al. 2004); the Universe was decelerating in the past due to the gravitational attraction of matter (Riess et al. 2001, Riess 2012). "A single SN Ia at $z \approx 1.7$, SN 1997ff, discovered with WFPC2 on the *Hubble Space Telescope (HST)* (Gilliland et al. 1999), provided a hint of past deceleration" (Riess et al. 2004).

According to Riess et al. (2004), "It is valuable to consider the distance-redshift relation of SNe Ia as a purely *kinematic* record of the expansion history of the universe, without regard to its cause". Such that, "A purely kinematic interpretation of the SN

Ia sample provides evidence at the greater than 99% confidence level for a transition from deceleration to acceleration” (Riess et al. 2004). That is, interpreting the data as model independent as possible, not comparing the distances to a cosmological model, treating the expansion to be independent of any assumption on the constituents, fully obtaining the result by only assuming that the Universe is expanding, and modeling that expansion only through its history (‘kinematics’) (Leibundgut 2024) (private communication (electronic) (August 2024)).

2. HOW IT ALL BEGAN?

The startling discovery of cosmic acceleration was the work of two research teams that independently arrived at the same startling conclusion. There was a fierce inter-team competition to determine the fate of the Universe or by what extent was the Universe’s expansion decelerating or slowing down due to gravity. What contributed in making the competition fierce was the scientific background of the researchers involved and the quest to reach the podium first as a team. On one hand, with astronomers on board, was the High- z Supernova Search Team (HZT), and on the other hand, with particle physicists on board, was the Supernova Cosmology Project (SCP). Quite clearly, there was going to be a clash of the titans while incorporating methodologies to arrive at conclusions, and there was; the members of the High- z Team had their own code of conduct as astronomers, and the members of the Supernova Cosmology Project had their own code of conduct as particle physicists.

Fierce competition and differences in the code of conduct may have drawn a dividing line between the two teams, but science helped uniting them reach a common conclusion. What renders the discovery evergreen, interesting, as well as one of my most favourite discoveries, is the era in which the research was being conducted – the 1990s! Born and brought up in the era of the 90s, I see the discovery of cosmic acceleration, the remarkable journey embarked by two research teams, as an enthralling scientific adventure that evokes amusing nostalgia as the chronology of those past events unfold.

The discovery of cosmic acceleration was a journey that took almost a decade for the research work of two teams to come to fruition; it was not a discovery that yielded results within a year or two, however, every day contributed to the eventual discovery, and every day brought along with itself sheer excitement and revealed something new. Therefore, without retelling the scientifically-adventurous story of how two research teams presented direct observational evidence in favour of cosmic acceleration, this paper would largely be incomplete.

To determine the fate of the Universe or by what extent was the Universe’s expansion slowing down, researchers needed a reliable cosmological tool or a probe that would be visible, owing to its dazzlingly-blinding luminosity, over myriad range of distances incurred on cosmic scales. The luminosity would help measure the distance, while the redshift would help measure how fast that particular object is receding from us in an expanding Universe; the relation between these two would then be used to determine the expansion rate of the Universe.

The idea of using supernovae or exploding stars as cosmological probes to measure the deceleration of the Universe was conceived back in the 1930s (Baade 1938), however, the supernovae that were known about at that time were not quite good enough “standard candles” as they were not of the same brightness; this continued to remain a problem for the next 50 years, until it was realized that supernovae could be subdivided into subclassifications (Perlmutter 2012).

Supernovae or the highly-luminous explosive brightening of stars come in varieties and have therefore been divided into two types based on the spectra they exhibit (see Schmidt 2012) – type I, supernovae that do not exhibit hydrogen lines in their spectrum, and type II, supernovae that exhibit hydrogen lines in their spectrum. These two classes (type I and type II) have further been divided into subclasses – the silicon-rich are type Ia, the helium-rich are type Ib, and with neither of these in abundance are type Ic. Similarly, for type II class – type II-P that exhibit an approx. 100-day plateau in their light curves, type II-L that exhibit a linear decline in their light curves, type IIb that exhibit features associated with type II and type Ib supernovae, however, there is a second peak in their light curves, and type IIc that exhibit narrow lines in their spectrum (also see Filippenko 1997). The supernova subclass “type Ia”

was identified in the mid-1980s and it began to become clear that a supernova belonging to this particular subclass was a better standard candle than the others (Perlmutter 2012) due to its consistent peak luminosity. Type Ia supernovae are also the most luminous of the common supernova types (Riess 2012).

To understand how a type Ia supernova springs into existence, consider the life-cycle of a low or a medium-mass star like the Sun. The thermonuclear energy generated at the interior of the star by fusing hydrogen to helium creates an outward pressure, whereas gravity creates an inward pull – a dancing balance between these two helps keep the star stable. However, this stability ceases when the thermonuclear energy generated at the interior of the star is no longer sufficient to counterbalance the inward gravitational pull. After running out of hydrogen, when hydrogen has been fused to helium, the star contracts, heats up, and the core, mostly helium now, attains a sufficiently high temperature to kick-start a new phase of thermonuclear reaction – the fusion of helium to carbon and oxygen at 10^8 K. A thin shell of hydrogen around the core heats up, burns, and causes the outer envelope of the star to expand and cool. A drop in temperature changes the colour of the star from hot white to cool red – a luminous red giant forms. If the mass of this red giant star is insufficient to further increase the core temperature to 10^9 K (required to kick-start carbon fusion), then a white dwarf star in the form of a carbon-oxygen core is left behind, while the outer layers drift away into space. A white dwarf is a compact star – as small as the Earth but as heavy as the Sun.

A type Ia supernova springs into existence when a carbon-oxygen white dwarf star, one discussed above, accretes mass from a companion star, grows beyond the Chandrasekhar limit, and explodes (Riess 2012) – on exploding, their light output rises, attains a peak, and then declines. A type Ia supernova explosion at its peak luminosity is 4×10^9 times brighter than the Sun (Riess 2012); it outshines the entire galaxy in which it lies. Type Ia supernovae can therefore be used as cosmological probes to determine the expansion history of the Universe as they are visible over large distances.

The first research program that used high-redshift supernovae as cosmological probes to determine the deceleration parameter of the Universe was a collaboration of Danish and British astronomers (Danish-Durham team (Nørgaard-Nielsen et al. 1989)) in the mid-1980s (Guralp 2020). To help increase the probability of recording an astronomical event in the form of a supernova explosion, the team, instead of observing just a single galaxy, focused on observing rich clusters of galaxies in the redshift (z) interval $0.2 < z < 0.5$. Using the Danish 1.5-meter telescope at the European Southern Observatory in La Silla, Chile, they searched several years for very distant type Ia supernovae but found just one, several weeks after it had already passed its peak brightness (Perlmutter 2012); it was a type Ia supernova discovered at a redshift of 0.31 (SN 1988U) – this was the most distant and highest redshift supernova to have been recorded back then. Using the data, the team was able to publish a very tentative result on the value of the deceleration parameter (q_0) as $-0.6 \leq q_0 \leq +2.5$; this was the first determination of q_0 using a supernova (Guralp 2020).

The Supernova Cosmology Project had been working towards the goal of measuring the deceleration parameter (q_0) since 1988 (Schmidt 2012). The Danish-Durham team had started working on this goal shortly before them in 1986; the difficulties faced by the Danish-Durham team were therefore illustrated when the Supernova Cosmology Project saw their results (Perlmutter 2012). The work of the Danish-Durham team showed that the existing supernova measurement system was not yet capable of delivering the evidence it had sought. The project was too demanding to continue; it proved to be extremely difficult – only one object discovered in two years; their project ended in 1989 (Guralp 2020).

On one hand, the discovery of this supernova by the Danish-Durham team provided hope for future endeavours in the sense that high-redshift supernovae exist and can be found, however, on the other hand, the discovery raised certain doubts regarding the viability of such a supernova search program if it were to be pursued, after all, supernovae are rare events; type Ia supernovae explode only a couple of times per millennium in a given galaxy, moreover, they are random, and they brighten and fade away in time scales of weeks (Perlmutter 2012).

By 1989, the efforts started gaining momentum when the Supernova Cosmology Project developed a novel imaging

equipment and deployed it on the 4-meter Anglo-Australian Telescope (AAT) in Siding Spring, Australia – it was a wide-field camera with a very big field of view, allowing a larger area of the sky to be captured in a single exposure (thousands of distant galaxies at a time) using a small CCD or a digital camera. The weather in Australia was, however, not good; the observations were hampered because of rain and clouds (Perlmutter 2012). By the early 1990s, the team decided to mount a large CCD camera on the 2.5-meter Isaac Newton Telescope (INT) in the Canary Islands; the telescope was smaller than the one at Australia, but the camera deployed was bigger and the weather for observations was better, this combination helped them discover, in 1992, their first high-redshift supernova, SN 1992BI at a redshift (z) of 0.46 (Clocchiatti 2011); this was the most distant supernova to have been discovered back then.

Also, in the early 1990s, the Calán/Tololo Survey (a survey initiated in 1990 by a group of astronomers – a collaboration between the University of Chile and the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory at Cerro Calán) came online to help improve the Hubble diagram using type Ia supernovae. This survey was built on the original supernova survey that was previously carried out at the Cerro Roble Observatory, University of Chile between 1979 and 1984 by Maza et al. (1981). The Calán/Tololo Survey discovered more than 50 objects from 1990 to 1993 (Schmidt 2012) out to a redshift of 0.1 (Hamuy et al. 1993).

However, a problem was stumbled upon when some type Ia supernovae were found not behaving identical as some of them were more luminous than the others; it would be of no use to incorporate such objects to help measure distances if they cannot behave reliably as standard candles – the distances would get underestimated or overestimated. Subsequently, a pattern was uncovered by the team – supernovae that exhibited light curves rising and falling rapidly were less luminous (these produced less iron), whereas supernovae that exhibited light curves rising and falling gradually were more luminous (these produced more iron) (Schmidt 2012).

Based on this observed pattern, in 1993, the incorporation of a seminal research method (Phillips 1993) helped discover and establish a relationship (the Phillips relationship) that showed that the intrinsic luminosity of supernovae at their peak appeared to correlate with the rate at which their light output declined after reaching peak, that is, the more slowly their light declined, the more luminous they were. Therefore, the decline rate of type Ia supernovae could be used to help improve the precision of their distance estimates (Riess 2012).

Early in 1994, the application of the Phillips relationship to type Ia supernova samples by the Calán/Tololo Survey started yielding positive results when they plotted the Hubble diagram. The scatter in the Hubble diagram was significantly reduced as nearby objects began exhibiting a well-organised linear Hubble diagram; type Ia supernovae were providing distances with a precision better than 7% per object (Schmidt 2012).

By 1994, the Supernova Cosmology Project reported the “batch discovery” of 6 type Ia supernovae events using the 2.5-meter Isaac Newton Telescope (INT) in the Canary Islands and the 4-meter telescope at the Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO) in Arizona (Perlmutter et al. 1994). They were the first group to show that supernovae could be found in “batches” (Perlmutter et al. 1994). This strategy helped them predict half a dozen new supernova discoveries (Perlmutter 2012); this was a highly significant achievement as sufficient photometric and spectroscopic follow-up observations using different telescopes could be scheduled (Filippenko 2001). However, they had not yet given a serious consideration to the standardization of supernova light curves and hence their luminosities through the Phillips relationship and also to the reddening correction required for individual supernovae (Clocchiatti 2011).

These strengths and weaknesses in the analysis planned by the Supernova Cosmology Project motivated, by the end of 1994, another group that would soon form a team to compete against them (Clocchiatti 2011). With renewed confidence that type Ia supernovae can now be used as precise distance indicators, an observing proposal in the form of a pilot project to search for distant type Ia supernovae was sent to the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) on September 29, 1994 – this proposal marked the next step in the Calán/Tololo Survey. It was during this period that the High- z Supernova Search

Team was formed while they wrote down a circular to notify the International Astronomical Union (IAU) regarding the discovery of their first most distant type Ia supernova (SN 1995K) at a high redshift of 0.479 (≈ 0.48) discovered in April, 1995 using the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) 4-meter telescope (Schmidt 2012).

Surprisingly, this single supernova (SN 1995K) provided an intricate answer to the High- z Team; showing them that the Universe was not slowing down; it was speeding up! However, it was just a single object. Moreover, it was analogous to the very first high-redshift supernova discovered by the Supernova Cosmology Project back in 1992 – SN 1992BI at a redshift of 0.458 (≈ 0.46). By mid-1994 when the Supernova Cosmology Project began analysing the cosmological implications of this particular supernova (Perlmutter et al. 1995), even they ended up getting an intricate answer – a very low value for the slowing of the expansion of the Universe, and hence the mass density of the Universe responsible for its slowing; a value so low that it made the team think about the “cosmological constant” (Perlmutter 2012). However, it was also, just a single object.

By 1995, the Supernova Cosmology Project implemented a method of their own, like the one implemented by the Calán/Tololo Survey, to standardize the luminosities of type Ia supernovae (Perlmutter et al. 1995). To standardize all supernova light curves, the brighter/slower light curves as well as the fainter/faster light curves, the team stretched or compressed the time axis of the light curve by a single “stretch factor” until all light curves matched each other. The measured stretch factor would predict the brightness of each light curve. In other words, by appropriately brightening the faster light curves and dimming the slower light curves while stretching or compressing their time scales, the standardization can be achieved for all light curves so that they all match and lie right on top of each other (Perlmutter 2012).

The Phillips relationship implemented by the Calán/Tololo Survey and the stretch factor technique implemented by the Supernova Cosmology Project came to rescue and helped with the standardization of supernova light curves and hence their luminosities. However, there were other problems that had to be addressed.

What if there was intervening dust along the line-of-sight? What if supernovae were intrinsically dim? Both these effects would also make us overestimate the distances to supernovae. Moreover, the typical size of dust grains makes them efficient at scattering a shorter wavelength more readily than a longer wavelength, therefore, besides causing the supernovae to appear dimmer due to extinction, intervening dust would also cause the supernovae to appear redder as more red light would be passing through (Riess 2012). How can one determine then which supernovae are appearing dim because they are really far away, which supernovae are appearing dim because of intervening dust along the line-of-sight, and which supernovae are appearing dim because they are intrinsically dim?

In 1996, an empirical method of multicolour light-curve shapes (MLCSs) was presented by Riess et al. (1996) to estimate the luminosity, distance, and total line-of-sight extinction of type Ia supernovae. They found that intrinsically-dim supernovae are redder and have faster light curves than the bright ones, which are slow and blue. The idea was to isolate the colour intrinsic to the supernovae from their extrinsic reddening by dust by using several different-coloured filters (Riess 2012). The application of MLCS method provided enough information to determine which supernovae are dim because they are distant, which supernovae are intrinsically dim, and which supernovae are dim because of extinction by dust. The MLCS method provided an accurate determination of distance; an accuracy of 5% for a single object was achieved using this method.

By 1997, the teams had reached the pinnacle of observational runs; more and more supernova samples were being collected and analysed using different telescopes spread all around the globe, including one telescope in orbit, high above the Earth – the Hubble Space Telescope. The ultimate fate of the Universe was about to be revealed.

By mid-1997, the Supernova Cosmology Project presented their results of the first seven supernovae discovered by them during 1992 – 1994 using the Isaac Newton 2.5-meter telescope and the Kitt Peak 4-meter telescope (Perlmutter et al. 1997). They had incorporated the stretch factor method to calibrate

supernova light curves, but the correction required due to extinction by dust was not considered (Clocchiatti 2011). Their results, however, were making sense as per the expectations set by astronomy texts of the time; their data supported a strongly decelerating Universe with enough matter that its mutual gravitation would cause the Universe to recollapse onto itself in the future (Riess 2012). But, with only seven supernovae, the uncertainties were large (Perlmutter 2012); it was clear that more data were badly needed (Riess 2012).

On the 7th of October 1997, the Supernova Cosmology Project submitted their paper to *Nature*; they had finished analysing a supernova that was discovered by them on the 5th of March 1997 using the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) 4-meter telescope – it was a type Ia supernova at a high redshift of 0.83 – SN 1997AP (Perlmutter et al. 1998). Owing to the photometric follow-up observations carried out using the Hubble Space Telescope, this particular supernova was very-well-measured and it ended up playing its role of turning the table; making the team change their initial decision regarding a high-mass-density Universe that was strongly decelerating under gravity to recollapse in the future. They witnessed that the Universe was not decelerating strongly enough to recollapse in the future – they were witnessing a Universe with low mass density (low Ω_M) that would expand forever.

In 1997, the High- z Team had also used the Hubble Space Telescope time for the photometric follow-up observations of ground-based discovery of three high-redshift type Ia supernovae discovered by them in April of 1997 using the 3.58-meter Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope (CFHT) – SN 1997CE, SN 1997CJ at redshifts of ≈ 0.5 , and SN 1997CK at a redshift of 0.97 (Garnavich et al. 1998). On the 14th of October 1997, the High- z Team submitted their paper to the *Astrophysical Journal Letters*. The analysis of these supernovae revealed the Universe's future to the High- z Team; they witnessed the initial glimpse that the Universe was not decelerating strongly enough to recollapse in the future (Riess 2012); the fate of the Universe appeared that it would expand forever – a Universe with low mass density (low Ω_M).

An article surfaced in the 31st of October 1997 issue of the *Science* magazine (Glanz 1997). The article was penned not only with the results presented by the two teams that were in agreement regarding the fate of the Universe – a Universe with low mass density that would expand forever, but also with exotic descriptions and possibilities. The article mentioned the research teams' goal of measuring the ultimate fate of the Universe or how the expansion rate of the Universe has changed over time. But then the article mentioned the expansion of the Universe, “whether it has been slowed by gravity, or perhaps boosted by large-scale repulsive forces”. Moreover, the article also mentioned that “the results even leave open the possibility that a so-called cosmological constant – a hypothetical property of empty space that might generate repulsive forces – is at work, giving the universe an expansive antigravity boost”. Exotic descriptions like these made their way into the article when the paper of the High- z Team was under review at *Astrophysical Journal Letters* (Garnavich et al. 1998), and the paper of the Supernova Cosmology Project was in press at *Nature* (Perlmutter et al. 1998).

Through 1995 – 1997, the High- z Team discovered 16 distant type Ia supernovae that were enough to make a statistically-robust measurement of the deceleration parameter (Schmidt 2012). In 1997, the High- z Team availed the opportunity to analyse and interpret all data collected by them so far; including their very first high-redshift supernova discovered by them in 1995 – SN 1995K. Competition from the Supernova Cosmology Project was stiff (Filippenko 2001); they had already published their results based on seven supernovae indicating a strongly-decelerating Universe that would recollapse in the future (Perlmutter et al. 1997), later they revised this estimate after taking into account a very-well-measured high-redshift supernova – SN 1997AP that began telling a different story (Perlmutter 2012) indicating a Universe with low mass density that was not decelerating strongly enough to recollapse in the future (Perlmutter et al. 1998), and now they were busy analysing their full set of 42 supernovae collected by them through 1992 – 1997.

In November of 1997, something far more interesting (surprising even) than just a low-mass-density Universe got revealed to the High- z Team; the analysis of supernovae sample

by them yielded a stunning result, indicating the presence of “negative mass” in the Universe (Riess 2012). In other words, the deceleration parameter (q_0) turned out to be negative ($q_0 < 0$) as it initially did for SN 1995K! High-redshift supernovae, as compared to the low-redshift ones, were 10% to 25% dimmer as they were further away than expected. The expansion of the Universe was not decelerating at all, it was accelerating! This was an unexpected and a crazy result; completely at odds with the result that the Supernova Cosmology Project had come up with using seven supernovae (Schmidt 2012).

What could have gone wrong was the High- z Team's immediate concern. A crazy and an unexpected result made it imperative for them to verify their analysis for simple/silly errors like sign errors and programming bugs (Filippenko 2001). It would be embarrassing to go out with results that the world would not welcome with open arms, especially when a competing team had obtained a more sensible answer using seven supernovae. Through November 1997 – January 1998, the High- z Team checked and rechecked their own work making sure no obvious errors had crept in their analysis. A number of checks, however, did not reveal anything amiss; if the result was wrong, the reason had to be subtle (Filippenko 2001).

Possibilities that could mimic cosmic acceleration were also ruled out one by one by the High- z Team. The deployment of the multicolour light-curve shape (MLCS) as well as the Phillips relationship ruled out the possibility of dust being the contaminating culprit, moreover, the light curves and the spectra of the nearby and distant supernovae were found to be indistinguishable, therefore, these deployed algorithms also helped ruling out the possibility of distant supernovae being different from the nearby ones, the High- z Team also ruled out the presence of a local void in the Universe that would increase the low-redshift expansion rate relative to the high-redshift expansion rate due to the addition of contaminating velocity component (peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow) to recession velocity arising solely due to the expansion of the Universe (pure Hubble flow), the contamination of type Ia supernovae sample by other supernova types was also ruled out by the High- z Team (Riess 2012).

The “Hello Lambda” inscribed in the subject line of the High- z Team's internal communication email sent in the first week of January 1998 was suggestive that the preliminary analysis of data by the High- z Team required a non-zero cosmological constant (non-zero Λ) – the Universe was accelerating! Most of the High- z Team had not been shown the analysis at this point (Schmidt 2012) and a select few members of the team who knew the results at this initial and crucial stage were ready to present them at the American Astronomical Society meeting in Washington, D.C.

The Supernova Cosmology Project was also in the race; they had finished analysing their 42 type Ia supernovae at high redshifts and the evidence for a low-mass-density Universe that would expand forever became even stronger once they incorporated these 42 high-redshift supernovae. The Supernova Cosmology Project had plotted their findings on a graph, matching the distance of type Ia supernovae against their velocity as they were swept away by cosmic expansion – their data gave them a perplexing graph – a line that deviated from linearity, implying that the Universe was not decelerating at all; it was accelerating! This graph, stuffed in a briefcase, was on its way to the annual meeting of the American Astronomical Society (Anton 2000).

On the 8th of January 1998, a press conference was scheduled at the American Astronomical Society meeting in Washington, D.C. where both teams presented their evidence for a low-mass-density (low- Ω_M) Universe that would expand forever (Garnavich et al. 1998 and Perlmutter et al. 1998). The High- z Team did not yet feel ready to announce the possible discovery of cosmic acceleration at this stage as various checks were still being made (Filippenko 2001). With an uncertain conclusion, the Supernova Cosmology Project presented tentative evidence for acceleration while showing their Hubble diagram for type Ia supernovae (Filippenko 2001), however, the High- z Team members at the conference were quick at deciphering what the findings of the Supernova Cosmology Project implied and where were they heading; their findings showed them the same thing that they were seeing (Schmidt 2012); both teams were heading in the same direction – high-redshift supernovae were fainter as they were further away than expected.

The Supernova Cosmology Project had already made their results public by posting their new paper on the astrophysics archive on the 16th of December 1997 (Perlmutter et al. 1997). A few members of the High- z Team learnt about this paper published in *Nature* (Perlmutter et al. 1998) only after the American Astronomical Society press conference on the 8th of January 1998 (Schmidt 2012), whereas a few members of the High- z Team had already studied this paper (Panek 2011). The value of the deceleration parameter (q_0) according to their new paper was much lower than before (Schmidt 2012).

Reporters present at the press conference availed the golden opportunity and disseminated the exciting news all over the world; *The New York Times*, *The San Francisco Chronicle*, and *The Washington Post*, were penned with the exciting results presented by the two teams. It was enormous news (Anton 2000) that focused primarily, and rightly, on the consensus that the participants in the press conference had reached – the fate of the Universe (Panek 2011) – a Universe with low mass density that would expand forever.

By the 10th of January 1998, the High- z Team did their own spot-checking of the results and found no mistakes – their data clearly required a non-zero cosmological constant (Riess 2012). Consequently, emails between the team members – a lengthy thread of seemingly never-ending messages reflected their mixed reactions. Some of the team members were excited, others were in disbelief, and still others felt that they had a long way to go to show the result to be robust to errors (Schmidt 2012).

On the 20th of February 1998, the High- z Team had a team-wide teleconference to decide whether to go forward with the paper that was being written; a draft of which was already sent around (Riess 2012) – the High- z Team had been trading drafts since the early-January 1998 emails exchanged between the team members; they explored the math, they debugged the code (they missed a few glitches, but nothing important), they examined the photometry and the spectroscopy, they even examined the charts, the graphs, and the tables (Panek 2011). Finding no flaws in their final reanalysis, the High- z Team agreed to the contents of the paper, and were ready to announce their result in an upcoming meeting (Schmidt 2012).

By the end of February 1998, a meeting was held in Los Angeles, California. The Supernova Cosmology Project presented strong evidence for low mass density (low Ω_M), and a tentative evidence for non-zero energy density (non-zero Ω_Λ), whereas the High- z Team strongly suggested, based on extensive data analysis, that Λ is positive (Filippenko 2001).

The surprising results presented by both teams made top headlines across the globe. The startling discovery got picked by mainstream media giants – *The New York Times*, *News Hour*, *CNN's Headline News*, and even the *Science* and the *TIME* magazines. Moreover, several television documentaries also featured the High- z Team and the Supernova Cosmology Project (Filippenko 2001).

On the 13th of March 1998, the High- z Team submitted their paper to the *Astronomical Journal*; their paper appeared in September 1998 issue (Riess et al. 1998), whereas the Supernova Cosmology Project submitted their paper with the same startling conclusion 9 months later to the *Astrophysical Journal*; their paper appeared in June 1999 issue (Perlmutter et al. 1999).

The Supernova Cosmology Project had more supernova samples; they had emphasized on quantity, whereas the High- z Team had chosen quality of supernova samples over quantity. But, at the end of an enthralling journey, both teams reached the podium victoriously; their results implied one and the same thing – the expansion of the Universe was not decelerating at all; it was accelerating!

The startling discovery of cosmic acceleration made a big impact (Clocchiatti 2011) – it was selected as the “Science Breakthrough of the Year” for 1998 by the *Science* magazine (Glanz 1998), and things did not stop there; the discovery of cosmic acceleration – the work of two teams was recognized and honoured with many prestigious prizes. The teams – the Supernova Cosmology Project led by Professor Saul Perlmutter of the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory and University of California, and the High- z Supernova Search Team led jointly by Professor Brian Schmidt of the Australian National University, and Professor Adam Riess of the Johns Hopkins University and Space Telescope Science Institute – were

awarded the 2006 Shaw Prize, the 2007 Gruber Cosmology Prize, the 2011 Nobel Prize in Physics, the 2011 Albert Einstein Medal, the 2012 Dirac Medal, the 2015 Breakthrough Prize in Fundamental Physics, and the 2015 Wolf Prize in Physics.

3. WHAT HAVE WE LEARNT SO FAR?

Why does it appear that the Universe was decelerating in the past and is accelerating now? Why do remote supernovae appear 10% to 25% dimmer than the nearby, local supernovae, thereby making us believe that they are further away than expected? Could distant supernovae be appearing dim due to intervening dust? Or, could it be that those distant supernovae have different properties as compared to the nearby, local supernovae? These possibilities have already been taken into account and have therefore been addressed – dust is not a factor, similarly, the brightness of local and remote supernovae differing due to property mismatch brought about by evolution is also not a factor (Riess 2000, Coil et al. 2000, Leibundgut 2001, Sullivan et al. 2003, Riess et al. 2004).

More recent studies conducted by Betoule et al. (2014), Scolnic et al. (2018), and Kenworthy et al. (2019) (discussed later in this section) help type Ia supernovae continue their undisputed streak of providing direct and the best observational evidence in favour of cosmic acceleration. This been said does not imply that the discovery of cosmic acceleration is well-settled; it is laced with problems of its own. The first problem itself being that there is still no understanding as to why the Universe is accelerating or what is driving cosmic acceleration, and then, in order to explain this apparent acceleration, or to explain what is driving this accelerating expansion of the Universe, researchers pass the buck to an energy component which itself is mysterious, hypothetical, of unknown origin, and has no explanation in fundamental physics; this is doubly unfair; it is adding more complication to a problem that is already complicated. According to Carroll (2004), “In trying to understand the universe in which we apparently live, we are faced with a problem, a puzzle, and a scandal:

- The cosmological constant problem: why is the energy of the vacuum so much smaller than we estimate it should be?
- The dark energy puzzle: what is the nature of the smoothly-distributed, persistent energy density which appears to dominate the universe?
- The coincidence scandal: why is the dark energy density approximately equal to the matter density today?

Any one of these issues would represent a serious challenge to physicists and astronomers” (Carroll 2004). Below we discuss briefly what constitutes a problem, a puzzle, and a scandal:

The first issue is the “The cosmological constant problem”: According to the quantum field theory what acts as the cosmological constant (Λ) is the energy density associated with empty space (vacuum energy density) or the zero-point energy due to ground-state quantum fluctuations. However, a discrepant problem discussed earlier involving an alarming 120-orders-of-magnitude (10^{120}) mismatch between the small observed value and the huge theoretically-calculated value according to the quantum field theory arises; “the worst theoretical prediction in the history of physics” (Hobson et al. 2006). Had the observed value been so large, vacuum catastrophe would have been inevitable; it would have ripped the Universe apart; structures we observe in the Universe would have not formed, and life as we know it would have not existed. What cancels out the theoretically-calculated colossal value so that the energy density takes on the observed small and gentle value?

The second issue is the “The dark energy puzzle”: Once type Ia supernova observations made it clear that the Universe is accelerating, a mysterious and hypothetical energy component of unknown origin, having no explanation in fundamental physics was invoked by researchers as the culprit fuelling the acceleration. In the simplest form, dark energy is Einstein’s cosmological constant (Λ) or the energy density associated with empty space. According to Durrer (2011), “our single indication for the existence of dark energy comes from distance measurements and their relation to redshift. Supernovae, cosmic microwave background anisotropies and observations of baryon acoustic oscillations simply tell us that the observed distance to a given redshift z is larger than the one expected from a Friedmann–Lemaître universe with matter only and the locally measured Hubble parameter”. Also, according to Mohayaee

et al. (2021), “it was inferred (based on type Ia supernova observations) that the Hubble expansion rate is accelerating as if driven by a positive Cosmological Constant Λ in Einstein’s theory of gravity. This is still the only *direct* evidence for the ‘dark energy’ that is the dominant component of today’s standard Λ CDM cosmological model. Other data such as baryon acoustic oscillations (BAO) in the large-scale distribution of galaxies, temperature fluctuations in the cosmic microwave background (CMB), measurement of stellar ages, the rate of growth of structure, *etc.* are all ‘concordant’ with this model but do not provide independent evidence for accelerated expansion”.

The third issue is the “The coincidence scandal”: What is so special about the *current epoch* of cosmic expansion? From the description by Riess et al. (2004), “cosmic deceleration that preceded the *current epoch* of cosmic acceleration”, it seems that the *current epoch* of cosmic expansion is very special; we are living in a privileged or a very special epoch of cosmic expansion – we are not only lucky to witness the recent onset of cosmic acceleration in the *current epoch* (other observers were unlucky and probably depressed witnessing a decelerating Universe), but we are also more than lucky to witness this recent onset in an epoch when the dark energy density is approximately equal to the matter density. “How finely-tuned is it that we exist in the era when vacuum and matter are comparable?” (Carroll 2004).

Some possible ideas that can help explain cosmic acceleration have succinctly been discussed by Durrer (2011), these include, replacing cosmological constant by some other form of ‘dark energy’ like an ordinary or a tachyonic scalar field (Linder 2008), modifying the left-hand side of Einstein’s equation, that is, modifying gravity (Durrer and Maartens 2008, 2010), modifying Einstein–Hilbert action by $R \rightarrow f(R)$ (Capozziello and Francaviglia 2008), theories with extra dimensions (Maartens 2004, Sahni 2005, Durrer 2005, Dvali et al. 2000, 2000). However, according to Durrer (2011), “All these models are quite speculative. Furthermore, even if one of these models is realized in nature, the question of why we do *not* measure a cosmological constant gravitationally remains”.

To answer this question, a model based on massive gravity (de Rham et al. 2011, de Rham 2014) makes modification to gravity by assuming that the graviton (a massless, hypothetical particle representing quantum of energy exchanged in a gravitational interaction) has mass; such an assumption eliminates the need for dark energy and explains cosmic acceleration by rendering gravitational influence weaker on large scales. Since massive gravity imparts mass to a graviton and makes modification to gravity, therefore, in such a case, a gravitational wave is expected to travel at a velocity less than the velocity of light. However, the “detection of the binary neutron star merger GW170817 and its associated electromagnetic counterparts have shown almost coincident observation of both signals” (Ezquiaga and Zumalacárregui 2017), therefore, many theories based on modified gravity as alternatives to dark energy have been ruled out. In other words, massive gravity and additional models that are closely related to it, such as bigravity (Hassan and Rosen 2012, Akrami et al. 2013, 2015) and multi-gravity (Hinterbichler and Rosen 2012) “remain viable as long as the graviton mass is small” (Ezquiaga and Zumalacárregui 2017).

Another possibility that could mimic cosmic acceleration deals with inhomogeneities on small scales; we are probably located in a region where the expansion is faster than the remote background due to inhomogeneities (Räsänen 2008, Clarkson and Maartens 2010, Tsagas 2011, Colin et al. 2011, Räsänen 2011, Colin et al. 2019). Instances holding bulk flow responsible as a possible contaminant while determining the expansion rate of the Universe have been noted in the literature. Kashlinsky et al. (2008), Watkins et al. (2009), and Lavaux et al. (2010) found bulk flow that extends out to at least 300 Mpc, 100 Mpc, and 120 Mpc respectively. Study conducted by Colin et al. (2011) found that at low redshifts ($z < 0.05$), an isotropic model such as Λ CDM is barely consistent with the SNe Ia data. According to them, there is a bulk flow of 260 km s^{-1} extending out to $z \sim 0.06$, which disagrees with Λ CDM. However, they suggest that at higher redshifts ($z > 0.15$), the agreement between the SNe Ia data and the Λ CDM model does improve.

Keeping this in mind that inhomogeneities are suggested to exist at $z < 0.15$, Kenworthy et al. (2019) conducted a study by using a sample of 1295 type Ia supernovae over a redshift range

$0.01 < z < 2.26$ that helped them conclude that local structure does not impact measurement of the Hubble constant (H_0); the study conducted by them therefore rejects the dipole/bulk flow interpretation and reconfirms cosmic acceleration. Study conducted using 740 spectroscopically-confirmed type Ia supernovae covering the redshift range $0.01 < z < 1.2$ (Betoule et al. 2014) also confirmed cosmic acceleration. Another study incorporating 1048 spectroscopically-confirmed type Ia supernovae in the redshift range $0.01 < z < 2.3$ (Scolnic et al. 2018) also confirmed cosmic acceleration; according to them, the evidence for an accelerating Universe using type Ia supernovae alone is $> 6\sigma$.

On one hand where cosmic acceleration continues to remain a major unsolved problem since 1998, recent studies on the other hand have uncovered some additional problems. The study conducted by Riess et al. (2016) showed that the Universe is not only expanding 9% faster than before but is also younger than before. The study conducted by Riess et al. (2019) has uncovered a crisis in cosmology – the “Hubble tension” – necessitating an immediate need for some new physics beyond Λ CDM to explain the discrepancy in the expansion rates of early and late Universe. According to Lusso et al. (2019) there has been “mounting evidence that the standard Λ CDM model is in tension at more than 4σ with local direct measurements of the Hubble constant” suggesting new physics beyond Λ CDM (Riess et al. 2019, Lusso et al. 2019); a tension that is confirmed to be “at $> 4\sigma$ with the whole SNe Ia + quasars + GRB data set” (Lusso et al. 2019).

Myriad of possibilities have been invoked to help alleviate these recent problems (see Di Valentino et al. 2021); some of the possibilities include, “cracks in the standard cosmological scenario” (Abdalla et al. 2022), contamination of supernova results due to local inhomogeneities resulting in a higher local value of the Hubble constant (H_0); according to Shanks et al. (2019), “we need to go to distances beyond the largest local inhomogeneities so that the recession velocity completely dominates any peculiar velocity”. According to them, “the existence of a ‘Local Hole’ in the galaxy distribution implies an outflow of $\approx 500 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Accounting for this in the recession velocities of SNIa standard candles out to $z \approx 0.15$ reduces H_0 ”. However, the study conducted by Kenworthy et al. (2019) discussed earlier, claims that “local structure does not impact measurement of the Hubble constant”, whereas the study conducted by Haslbauer et al. (2020) takes into account the possibility of “a local underdensity between 40 and 300 Mpc around the Local Group” and provides a solution to the Hubble tension by replacing General Relativity with modified Newtonian dynamics. “Early dark energy (EDE) that behaves like a cosmological constant at early times and then dilutes away like radiation or faster at later times” (Poulin et al. 2019) has also been considered to help resolve the Hubble tension.

The problems do not stop there; high-redshift observations have uncovered an additional conundrum – the “impossible early galaxy problem” (see Melia 2014 and references therein). The “impossible early galaxy problem” refers to the conundrum that galaxies at high redshifts, especially those observed using the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) (Naidu et al. 2022a, 2022b; Adams et al. 2023; Boyett et al. 2023; Dekel et al. 2023; Hainline et al. 2023; Labbé et al. 2023; Robertson et al. 2023), appear as evolved, as bright, and as massive as those at lower redshifts (see Gupta 2023, 2024 and additional references therein) – how can it be possible that galaxies at high redshifts, existing at ~ 0.3 Gyr after the Big Bang, are as evolved as the galaxies in existence for ~ 10 Gyr, if the age of the Universe at very high redshifts was less than half a billion years as per the Λ CDM model? The JWST findings, according to Gupta (2023), are thus in strong tension with the Λ CDM cosmological model.

According to Melia (2023), “billion-solar mass structures must have formed in only $\sim 70 - 90$ Myr in some cases, and even prior to formation of the very first stars in others”. “None of the calculations to date have been able to account for the formation of such galaxies. The time-compression problem would therefore be inconsistent with the age-redshift relation predicted by Λ CDM” (Melia 2023).

For instance (see Gupta 2023) – a massive quasar observed by Eilers et al. (2023) at high redshift ($z > 6$) hosts a ten-billion-solar-mass black hole just 1 Gyr after the Big Bang is a challenge for current black hole formation models. Another challenge for theoretical models comes from analysing a very

luminous galaxy at a high redshift (z) of 10.6 by Maiolino et al. (2023), according to them, the black hole seed for this exceptionally luminous galaxy must be accreting at a rate 5 times greater than the Eddington rate for 100 Myr.

Attempts have been made to resolve this “impossible early galaxy problem” by modifying the star and galaxy formation models, such as by compressing the time required for the formation of population III stars and galaxies more and more by considering the presence of (i) primordial massive black hole seeds (this possibility is still speculative according to Melia (2023)), and, (ii) super-Eddington accretion rates in the early Universe (this possibility appears to have been ruled out by measurements suggesting that most distant quasars are accreting at or below their Eddington rate (Melia 2023)). Therefore, adjusting well-established galaxy formation and cosmological models developed for low-redshift observations render the problem even more severe for high-redshift observations (see Gupta 2023, 2024 and references therein).

Without requiring the existence of primordial black hole seeds, rapid formation of massive population III stars, and super-Eddington accretion rates in the early Universe, Gupta (2023, 2024) has incorporated a hybrid model based on covarying coupling constants (CCC) + Tired Light (TL) to help resolve the “impossible early galaxy problem”. This hybrid (CCC + TL) model stretches the cosmic time or increases the age of the Universe to 26.7 Gyr (doubling the age of the Universe against the generally accepted value of 13.8 Gyr) – giving enough time to form massive galaxies.

According to Gupta (2024), “If the Universe’s age is established by other methods to be significantly higher than the currently accepted 13.8 Gyr, astrophysicists will be relieved from the burden of constraining stellar ages below 13.8 Gyr”. Therefore, “Instead of attempting to *compress* the cosmic timeline for creating well-evolved massive galaxies in a very young Universe to resolve the impossible early galaxy problem with the Λ CDM model, it might be prudent to consider alternative models that *stretch* the timeline, especially at high redshifts, to allow the formation of large galaxies” (Gupta 2023).

The aim of the study conducted in this paper is to help expand the range of possibilities. The *primary objective* of this paper is to help unravel an undiscovered aspect of expansion (“consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”) based on pure Hubble flow (recession velocities arising solely due to the expansion of the Universe) that perfectly mimics cosmic acceleration. Then, as a natural consequence of the type of expansion unravelled in this paper, the *secondary objective* of this paper is to help solve (i) the “Hubble tension”, (ii) an additional perplexing problem that makes the Universe appear to us as if it is “not only expanding faster than before but is also younger than before”, and (iii) the “impossible early galaxy problem”.

Since the luminosity distance helps probe the expansion history of the Universe up to that redshift, therefore, in an expanding Universe, the directly-observable luminosity distance and the directly-observable redshift associated with type Ia supernova observations can be considered as the directly-observable “end points” (or the final readings) of a particular expansion (both near and far) that help us determine the expansion history of the Universe; it is only when a type Ia supernova attains peak luminosity that researchers make a note of its luminosity and the associated redshift – luminosity helps measure the distance, whereas the redshift helps measure how fast the supernova is receding from us.

Taking into account these directly-observable “end points” (or the final readings) of a particular expansion (both near and far) associated with type Ia supernova observations (luminosity and redshift) that alone provide $> 6\sigma$ evidence for an accelerating Universe (Scolnic et al. 2018), the aim of the study conducted in this paper is to shed light on an undiscovered aspect that mimics cosmic acceleration so perfectly well that it tricks us into believing that the Universe was decelerating in the past at high redshifts and is accelerating now at low redshifts. The undiscovered aspect of expansion unravelled in this paper deals with “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”. Since this description is perfectly analogous to (and stems entirely from) the description by Riess et al. (2004), “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration”, therefore, it

is most likely that it was this undiscovered aspect of expansion that got interpreted as cosmic acceleration – the study aims at providing the “subtle reason” (Filippenko 2001) that the researchers have been looking for ever since the unexpected discovery of cosmic acceleration.

According to Riess and Turner (*Scientific American* 2004), “Astronomers can deduce the recession velocity of a supernova by measuring the redshift of the light from the galaxy in which it lies”. According to them, the expansion history of the Universe “is encoded in the relation between the distances and recession velocities of galaxies. If the expansion is speeding up, the distant galaxy’s velocity would fall below the predicted value. Or, to put it another way, a galaxy with a given recession velocity will be farther away than expected – and hence fainter – if the universe is accelerating”.

Therefore, based on recession velocities arising solely due to the expansion of the Universe (Hubble flow), the study essentially shows how consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion (one expansion epoch following the next in a consecutive manner) can mimic cosmic acceleration; it is shown that preceding epochs of cosmic expansion “appear to be decelerating or slowing down” as compared to the epoch of cosmic expansion that succeeds them. The fact that such an aspect mimics cosmic acceleration so perfectly well is the revelation of new physics in its own right and motivates further the unravelling of an additional aspect in this paper based on “expansion epochs of the Universe “succeeding” the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion” to help solve the Hubble tension as well as an additional perplexing problem that makes the Universe appear to us as if it is not only expanding faster than before but is also younger than before. The type of expansion unravelled in this paper also makes it possible to increase the age of the Universe (particularly at high redshifts). *Stretching* the timeline, especially at high redshifts, allows the formation of large galaxies (Gupta 2023); this would help solve the “impossible early galaxy problem”.

4. THE SURPRISING TRANSITION OF THE UNIVERSE’S EXPANSION FROM DECELERATION TO ACCELERATION: ANALYSING REMOTE AND LOCAL OBJECTS

Figure 1. Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 588 type Ia supernovae (from $z = 0.015$ to $z = 1.7$) showing the transition of the Universe’s expansion from deceleration to acceleration (red curve) (as measured from past to present – high redshift to low redshift – remote to local) (plotted by using the Supernova Cosmology Project data for 580 type Ia supernovae from Union 2 (Amanullah et al. 2010) and Union 2.1 (Suzuki et al. 2012), 7 additional high-redshift type Ia supernovae discovered through the ACS (Advanced Camera for Surveys) on the Hubble Space Telescope from the GOODS (Great Observatories Origins Deep Survey) Treasury program (joint work conducted by Giavalisco et al. 2004 and Riess et al. 2004), and 1 additional very high-redshift type Ia supernova discovered with WFC2 (Wide Field and Planetary Camera 2) on the Hubble Space Telescope (Gilliland et al. 1999)).

“The observed redshift of a distant galaxy or quasar gives a direct estimate of the universal expansion (i.e. the “recession velocity”). For instance, a redshift of $z = 0.1$ corresponds to a velocity of 30,000 km s⁻¹” (*European Southern Observatory (ESO) 1998*). Once the redshifts and the distances are known, “The relation between redshift and distance is then used to determine the expansion rate of the Universe” (Riess 2012).

Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for near and far type Ia supernovae plotted in Figure 1 is the new Hubble

diagram. Supernova observations ($z > 1$) confirmed the result that the Universe was decelerating or slowing down in the past before it began accelerating (Riess 2012). Therefore, according to Figure 1 that clearly depicts the transition of the Universe's expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration (red curve), a nearby, local supernova at $z = 0.015$ is expanding at a faster rate as compared to a supernova which is further away than expected at $z = 0.479$, or as compared to another supernova which is even further away than expected at $z = 1.7$. Therefore, by just looking where the objects lie on the Hubble diagram (Figure 1 and Figure 5), one gets to know if the Universe is accelerating or decelerating over time. High-redshift remote objects that are further away than expected are expanding at a slower rate (decelerating) as compared to the low-redshift local objects, and this is where a paradoxical trend gets uncovered.

Since observed redshifts (z) in an expanding Universe also provide an estimate of recession velocities – the more shifted a line in the spectrum is towards the red (redshift), the faster that object is said to be receding from us in an expanding Universe. Therefore, it is disturbing that high-redshift remote expansion ($z > 1$) gets advocated as deceleration or “slowing down” as compared to low-redshift local expansion ($z = 0.015$). Moreover, based on the velocity versus luminosity distance relationship for type Ia supernovae (Figure 6 and Figure 8) as well as the plot by the High- z Supernova Search Team (Figure 7), it is again disturbing to find that further-away-than-expected remote supernovae even with high recession velocities (60% of speed of light) are yielding a slower rate of expansion (deceleration) as compared to the nearby, local supernovae that are yielding a faster rate of expansion (acceleration) even with low recession velocities (just 1% of speed of light). Confidently enough, remote expansion at 60% of speed of light is way faster than local expansion at just 1% of speed of light. Then why should we encounter such a paradoxical trend wherein remote expansion at 60% of speed of light indicates a slower rate of expansion (deceleration), whereas local expansion at just 1% of speed of light indicates a faster rate of expansion (acceleration)?

Such a paradoxical trend as discussed above is not limited only to type Ia supernova observations. To study how the expansion of the Universe has changed over time, Risaliti and Lusso (2015) used quasars as standard candles (up to $z \approx 6$) as quasars are available in large numbers especially at much higher redshifts as compared to type Ia supernovae. The Hubble diagram (distance modulus vs. redshift relationship) obtained by them for those quasars (extending up to $z > 6$) (Figure 2) is in perfect agreement with the Hubble diagram for type Ia supernovae in the redshift (z) range of 0.01 to 1.4. Therefore, the study conducted by them using quasars is also consistent with past deceleration at high redshifts and recent acceleration at low redshifts.

Figure 2. “Hubble Diagram for the quasar sample (small gray points) and supernovae (cyan points) from the Union 2.1 sample (Suzuki et al. 2012). The large red points are quasar averages in small redshift bins”. Credit: Risaliti G., Lusso E., “A HUBBLE DIAGRAM FOR QUASARS”, *ApJ*, Vol. 815, 33, page 7, year 2015. © AAS. Reproduced with permission. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/815/1/33>

Studies incorporating gamma-ray bursts (GRBs) have gone even beyond by focusing at much higher redshifts (up to $z \approx 8$ and $z \approx 9$ (Dirirsa et al. 2019 and Demianski et al. 2017 respectively)). GRBs, just like type Ia supernovae, have also been used as standard candles to probe the expansion history of the Universe. The results obtained using GRBs, just like

quasars and type Ia supernovae, are also consistent with cosmic acceleration, that is, past deceleration at high redshifts and recent acceleration at low redshifts as shown below in Figure 3 (red curve).

Figure 3. Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 588 type Ia supernovae (from $z = 0.015$ to $z = 1.7$) from Figure 1 and for 216 GRBs (from $z = 0.414$ to $z = 9.3$).

Now, according to Riess et al. (2001), “If the cosmological acceleration inferred from SNe Ia is real, it commenced rather recently, at $0.5 < z < 1$. Beyond these redshifts, the universe was more compact and the attraction of matter dominated the repulsion of dark energy. At $z > 1$, the expansion of the universe should have been decelerating”.

Quasars, as depicted by the Hubble diagram (Figure 2) which extends up to $z > 6$, are way beyond, GRBs, as depicted by the Hubble diagram (Figure 3) which extends up to $z > 9$, are even way beyond, at these redshifts, the Universe was more compact, and the expansion of the Universe should have been decelerating according to Riess et al. (2001). However, when we observe remote objects (a supernova at $z = 1.7$, a quasar at $z \approx 6$, or a GRB at $z \approx 9$), we find that they are further away than expected (as per the observed luminosity), and they have high redshifts (as per the observed shifts in their spectral lines towards the red), and as stated earlier, the more shifted a line in the spectrum is towards the red (redshift), the faster that object is said to be receding from us in an expanding Universe; this is exactly what the High- z Team has also depicted in their plot.

The plot by the High- z Team (Figure 7) depicts how the expansion rate of the Universe has changed over time. They clearly show in their plot that the expansion is decelerating or “slowing down” for further-away-than-expected, high-redshift supernovae receding at 30% to 60% of the speed of light, whereas the expansion is accelerating or “speeding up” for nearby, low-redshift supernovae receding at just 1% to 10% of the speed of light. The plot literally compares further-away-than-expected, high-redshift or high-recession-velocity remote supernovae with nearby, low-redshift or low-recession-velocity local supernovae. Therefore, advocating that higher and higher recession velocities or higher and higher redshifts ($z > 1$) are an indication of cosmic deceleration or “slowing down” under the gravitational attraction of matter sounds very disturbing.

As compared to a minuscule redshift of 0.01 (SN Ia) that indicates acceleration, a high redshift of 1.7 (SN Ia) indicates deceleration, an extreme redshift of 6 (QSO) also indicates deceleration, and surprisingly, a whopping redshift of 9.3 (GRB) also indicates deceleration – this sounds weird – it is conflicting that every high-recession-velocity remote expansion ($z > 1$) is also (simultaneously) an indication of deceleration or “slowing down” under gravity as compared to low-recession-velocity local expansion (a mere redshift of 0.01). One should answer the question, how can every high-recession-velocity remote expansion ($z = 1.7$, $z = 6$, and $z = 9.3$) even be termed as deceleration or “slowing down” under gravity as compared to low-recession-velocity local expansion ($z = 0.01$)?

Finding this question to be a problematic threat to the notion of past deceleration or “slowing down” at high redshifts, a proponent, or a supporter of cosmic acceleration would readily suggest that recession velocities (particularly at high redshifts) are meaningless (see (13) of Section 9). However, according to Davis and Lineweaver (2004), “If recession velocity were meaningless we could not refer to an ‘expanding universe’ and would have to restrict ourselves to some operational description

such as ‘fainter objects have larger redshifts’”. Based on observations, and also according to Davis and Lineweaver (2004), “higher redshift galaxies are more distant from us and receding faster than lower redshift galaxies”. Clearly, “expanding Universe”, “accelerating Universe”, “Universe’s expansion is *not* slowing down with time, as expected, *but is speeding up*”, “remote supernovae, quasars, and GRBs are *not* receding as quickly as expected from observations of the local ones” (as per the discovery of accelerating Universe), and then, the expansion rate measured in “ $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$ ” that itself has units of *velocity* over distance, all these necessarily require a velocity description to make sense in an expanding Universe.

Figure 4. Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for type Ia supernovae and GRBs (from $z = 0.162$ to $z = 9.3$). All objects ($z < 0.15$) have been discarded since inhomogeneities on small scales (that are suggested to exist at $z < 0.15$) could mimic cosmic acceleration.

Perhaps we are located in a region where the expansion is faster than the remote background due to inhomogeneities, therefore, as a test, here in Figure 4, we have plotted the distance modulus versus redshift relationship by taking into account only those objects with redshifts (z) ranging from 0.162 to 9.3 (≈ 724 Mpc onwards). By doing so we have ensured that inhomogeneities on small scales ($z < 0.15$) would get washed away and we would be left only with those redshifts that happen to arise solely due to the Universe’s expansion.

Surprisingly, even after discarding all such objects ($z < 0.15$), Figure 4 still continues to exhibit the similar trait (red curve) exhibited by Figure 1, Figure 2, and Figure 3 while considering all objects ($z < 0.15$); a supernova at $z = 0.162$ is still expanding comparatively faster than a supernova at $z = 1.7$, a quasar at $z = 6$, or as compared to the GRB at $z = 9.3$, therefore, even after discarding very local objects ($z < 0.15$) where inhomogeneities are believed to play a role in mimicking cosmic acceleration, we still continue witnessing the disturbing paradoxical trend wherein low-redshift (low-recession-velocity) local expansion ($z = 0.162$) still turns out to be faster as compared to high-redshift (high-recession-velocity) remote expansion ($z > 1$), and therefore, the question still remains open, why would further-away-than-expected high-redshift remote object end up yielding a slower rate of expansion, thereby suggesting its deceleration or “slowing down” as compared to a low-redshift local object?

Since “local structure does not impact measurement of the Hubble constant” (Kenworthy et al. 2019), redshifts as low as 0.01 (Betoule et al. 2014, Scolnic et al. 2018, Kenworthy et al. 2019) can also be used to determine Universe’s expansion rate to confirm recent acceleration at low redshifts and past deceleration at high redshifts, therefore, in such a case, the above question becomes even more serious and rightfully demands an answer, rather than being swept under the rug.

Since evidence for an accelerating Universe from type Ia supernovae-only sample is $> 6\sigma$ (Scolnic et al. 2018), therefore, we will conduct an analysis (hereafter) based on those type Ia supernova observations (keeping QSOs and GRBs still in mind) and unravel how “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion” can mimic cosmic acceleration.

A very low-redshift local supernova ($z = 0.015166$) falling within the linear regime of the Hubble diagram (Figure 5) yields a slope of $2.2379 \times 10^{-18} \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$ ($\approx 69 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$) – this is the local expansion rate and it is significantly much higher than the remote measurement while incorporating further-away-than-expected remote supernova with very high redshift ($z = 1.7$).

Figure 5. Redshift-distance relationship for 588 type Ia supernovae from Figure 1. The blue line indicates the linear redshift-distance relationship exhibited by low-redshift local structures. The deviation from linearity at high redshifts indicates an accelerating Universe since the distances to remote supernovae are larger than expected with respect to the local ones. The slope is steeper for the local structures suggesting a faster rate of expansion (acceleration) and shallower for the remote structures suggesting a slower rate of expansion (deceleration).

However, since observed redshifts in an expanding Universe provide an estimate of recession velocities as shown in Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 46, therefore, the notion of deceleration or “slowing down” becomes very problematic at those high redshifts; the original discovery of accelerating Universe itself was based (to a reasonable extent) on measuring the recession velocities of type Ia supernovae from their observed redshifts (see (15) of Section 9), therefore, it becomes conflicting that further-away-than-expected remote supernova with high redshift ($z = 1.7$) indicates deceleration or “slowing down” under gravity as compared to a local supernova with low redshift ($z = 0.015166$).

Furthermore, it has also been acknowledged by Nugent (Research News 2001) while referring to this highly-redshifted supernova with a redshift (z) of 1.7, “highly redshifted objects are moving away from us so fast” (of course, due to expansion). However, something very strange that does not go hand in hand simultaneously with the above statement is then advocated while referring to this same highly-redshifted supernova with a redshift of 1.7, “the supernova allows us to glimpse an era when matter in the universe was still relatively dense and *expansion was still slowing under the influence of gravity*. More recently the dark energy has begun to predominate and expansion has started to speed up” (Nugent, Research News 2001).

Above statements clearly imply that the “highly-redshifted supernova with a redshift of 1.7 is moving away from us so fast (of course, due to expansion) that it is also providing us an indication of past deceleration or slowing down under the gravitational influence of matter” – this sounds paradoxical; how can “moving away from us so fast” simultaneously be an indication of “slowing down” under gravity?

5. ANALYSING THE SUPERNOVA SN 1995K AND ADDITIONAL TYPE IA SUPERNOVA OBSERVATIONS

An observing proposal was sent to the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) on September 29, 1994; it was “A Pilot Project to Search for Distant Type Ia Supernovae” (Schmidt et al. 1995, 1998). Using the 4-meter telescope that the observatory was equipped with, the aim of the proposal was to discover fainter type Ia supernovae at high redshifts ($z = 0.3 - 0.5$). The proposal marked the next step in the Calán/Tololo Survey (a survey initiated in 1990 by a group of astronomers – a collaboration between the University of Chile and the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory at Cerro Calán) that discovered 30 type Ia supernovae between 1990 and 1993 out to a redshift of 0.1 (Hamuy et al. 1993). If the proposal worked

smoothly in an expected manner, it would help the researchers determine the ultimate fate of the Universe by measuring a quantity called q_0 – the deceleration parameter – a measure of how much the Universe was decelerating or slowing down with time.

First observations were taken on February 25, 1995, and the team had another night's data on March 6, 1995 (Schmidt 2012). Unfortunately, the team faced a few problems in this initial run – the computing system at CTIO refused executing the program that would search for supernovae, a slow internet connection made it impossible to work remotely, and, the data tapes, that had to be evaluated to fix problems, never arrived through the courier; the delivery was lost somewhere (Schmidt 2012).

However, a very distant galaxy appeared as a smudge of pixels (Panek 2011) in an image taken on March 30, 1995; it was a new object (that looked like a supernova) discovered in a galaxy (Schmidt et al. 1998). The spectrum of this object was obtained using the European Southern Observatory (ESO) New Technology Telescope (NTT) on April 3, 1995 (Schmidt et al. 1998). The spectrum, however, provided no hint of that object being a supernova; the spectrum was found to be heavily contaminated by its host galaxy (Leibundgut et al. 1995), and, it was only when the light of the host galaxy was subtracted that a type Ia supernova spectrum got revealed. The spectrum of this type Ia supernova exhibited the characteristic Si II absorption at a rest wavelength of 6150 Å (Schmidt et al. 1998).

The discovery of this supernova was the proof that the proposal was working (Leibundgut et al. 1995). The observation was reported to the IAU (International Astronomical Union) and the object got designated SN 1995K (Schmidt et al. 1995, 1998). It was at this stage while writing the IAU circular that the team decided coming up with a name for itself (Schmidt 2012) – the High- z Supernova Search Team was formed.

At a redshift (z) of 0.479, SN 1995K was the first distant type Ia supernova discovered by the High- z Supernova Search Team in April, 1995. Its position on the Hubble diagram was subsequently plotted once its distance was measured and the team members, according to Riess (2012), “chuckled nervously” as soon as different possible values for the Universe’s deceleration started becoming apparent; SN 1995K was in an unexpected region of the Hubble diagram and indicated that the Universe’s expansion was accelerating.

As compared to the nearby, low-redshift type Ia supernovae that fell within the linear regime of the Hubble diagram as shown in Figure 6, SN 1995K deviated from linearity as it was further away than expected. SN 1995K showed deceleration parameter (q_0) = -0.6 (Schmidt 2012). A negative value for the deceleration parameter clearly implied that the Universe was accelerating, however, the uncertainty was such that the team required at least 10 objects to make a statistically significant measurement, and the actual value was not given much thought (Schmidt 2012); the team members consoled themselves that the error bar was big and one can be unlucky with a single object (Riess 2012).

More supernovae were therefore required for a reliable measurement of the deceleration parameter (q_0). The team estimated that about 20 supernovae with accurate peak magnitudes were needed to put significant constraints on the deceleration of the Universe (Leibundgut et al. 1995). Through 1995 – 1997, the High- z Team discovered 16 distant type Ia supernovae that were enough to make a statistically robust measurement of the deceleration parameter (Schmidt 2012).

In November of 1997, the analysis of supernovae sample by the High- z Team yielded a stunning result; indicating the presence of “negative mass” in the Universe (Riess 2012). High-redshift supernovae, as compared to the low-redshift ones, were 10% to 25% dimmer as they were further away than expected; the value of the deceleration parameter (q_0), something that the team had always wanted to measure as their ultimate goal, turned out to be negative ($q_0 < 0$) as it initially did for SN 1995K; distant type Ia supernovae were fainter than even a $q_0 = 0$ model (Schmidt 2012). To everyone’s surprise, the expansion of the Universe was not slowing down, it was speeding up! A crazy and an unexpected result like this made it imperative for the High- z Team to verify their analysis, making sure no obvious errors had crept in. A number of checks, however, did not reveal anything amiss; if the result was wrong, the reason had to be subtle (Filippenko 2001).

Figure 6. “SN 1995K on the Hubble Diagram” at a redshift (z) of 0.479. Credit: Schmidt B. P., *Reviews of Modern Physics*, Vol. 84, 1151, page 1158, year 2012, reprinted with permission, American Physical Society and the Nobel Foundation. This figure is a part of the Nobel Prize lecture of Brian P. Schmidt, Copyright © 2011 The Nobel Foundation. <https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.84.1151>

SN 1995K, plotted above in Figure 6, was the most distant type Ia supernova discovered in 1995 by the High- z Team ($D = 9.7211$ Gly, $z = 0.479$) – this yields a slope of $1.5617 \times 10^{-18} \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$ ($\approx 50 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$). Nearby, local supernovae that happen to fall within the linear regime of the Hubble diagram have also been plotted; consider one such local supernova ($D = 0.4877$ Gly, $z = 0.0333$) – this yields a slope of $2.1641 \times 10^{-18} \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$ ($\approx 67 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$). Comparison of expansion rates ($\text{km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ or $\text{m s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$) for these supernovae shows that SN 1995K is expanding at a slower rate (decelerating) as compared to this nearby supernova obeying the linear Hubble expansion.

Since observed redshift is providing an estimate of recession velocity as shown above in Figure 6 itself, therefore, advocating that SN 1995K is decelerating or “slowing down” as compared to the nearby supernova sounds paradoxical – the recession velocity of SN 1995K is ≈ 14 times higher than the recession velocity of the nearby supernova. Therefore, why is it that further-away-than-expected SN 1995K even with high recession velocity appears to be expanding slowly as compared to a local supernova with low recession velocity? Same question also arises while taking into account the following plot by the High- z Team.

Figure 7. Observations of additional type Ia supernovae by the High- z Supernova Search Team. The plot confirmed an accelerating Universe – remote supernovae that are further away than expected are expanding at a slower rate (decelerating or “slowing down”) as compared to the nearby, local supernovae. Credit: High- z Supernova Search Team.

Figure 7 depicts the result of additional type Ia supernova observations carried out by the High- z Team at even larger distances (high redshifts) that helped them confirm Universe’s acceleration. Distant supernovae were dimmer than expected (as they were further away than expected) and the expansion rate for them was found to be lower than the expansion rate for the nearby, local supernovae. Figure 7 clearly shows this transition of the Universe’s expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration – Universe was expanding slowly (decelerating) in the past and is expanding faster (accelerating) now.

However, if we look at the observed redshifts that are also providing an estimate of recession velocities as shown in Figure 7, then there seems to be a conundrum, it is very disturbing to find that local recession velocities ranging from just 1% to 10% of speed of light indicate a faster rate of expansion (acceleration or speeding up), whereas remote recession velocities ranging from 30% to 60% of speed of light indicate (comparatively) a slower rate of expansion (deceleration or slowing down).

Why is it that a remote object which happens to be further away than expected is yielding a lower value of slope (a slower rate of expansion or deceleration) even with high recession velocity (60% of speed of light) as compared to a nearby, local object that is yielding a higher value of slope (a faster rate of expansion or acceleration) even with low recession velocity (just 1% of speed of light)? Such an intriguing attribute is also encountered while taking into account the following plot.

Figure 8. “Velocity versus luminosity-distance for type Ia supernovae (filled circles), S-Z clusters (open circles) and gravitational lens time-delay systems (filled triangles), with $z > 0.05$ ”. Credit: Blanchard A., et al., *A&A*, Vol. 412, 35, page 39, year 2003, reproduced with permission © 2003 ESO. <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20031425>

Figure 8 illustrated above from Blanchard et al. (2003) depicts an expansion rate of $46 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ (broken line); this value reconciles with deep determinations of the Hubble constant and is much lower than the local expansion rate of $72 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ (solid line) obtained by the Hubble Key Project (Freedman et al. 2001). According to Sarkar (2007 (Seminar)), “the values obtained for the Hubble constant from the longest-range distance indicators are typically smaller than values obtained more locally”. The expansion rate measured for local objects with low recession velocities is greater than the expansion rate measured for remote objects with high recession velocities. “Perhaps the local void is expanding 20-30% faster than the global Hubble rate?” (Sarkar 2007 (Seminar)).

“It has been noted by Zehavi et al. (1998) that the SNe Ia out to 7000 km s^{-1} exhibit an expansion rate that is 6% greater than that measured for the more distant objects” (Riess et al. 1998). One might say that local void is expanding faster than the remote expansion rate. According to Riess et al. (1998), “In principle, a local void would increase the expansion rate measured for our low-redshift sample relative to the true, global expansion rate. Mistaking this inflated rate for the global value would give the false impression of an increase in the low-redshift expansion rate relative to the high-redshift expansion rate”. However, according to Riess et al. (1998), “only a small fraction of our nearby sample is within this local void, reducing its effect on the determination of the low-redshift expansion rate”. Furthermore, the reanalysis carried out (Riess et al. 1998) by discarding the seven SNe Ia within 7000 km s^{-1} (108 Mpc for $65 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$) ruled out the possibility of local void and confirmed cosmic acceleration.

Here low redshifts of seven, nearby supernovae (within 108 Mpc) have been interpreted as recession velocities of 7000 km s^{-1} by Riess et al. (1998) to determine the local expansion rate (H_0) as $65 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ ($7000 \text{ km s}^{-1}/108 \text{ Mpc}$); this local expansion rate is 6% greater than the expansion rate measured for the more distant objects as noted by Zehavi et al. (1998). If

nearby, local supernovae with low redshifts can be incorporated to measure the local expansion rate by deeming their low redshifts ($z \ll 1$) as recession velocities of 7000 km s^{-1} , then intuitively, do distant, remote supernovae with high redshifts ($z > 1$) not imply that they are receding from us at even higher recession velocities in an expanding Universe? Does recession velocity interpretation of observed redshifts in an expanding Universe “miraculously” disappear for high-redshift objects, or, is it only to reconcile with type Ia supernova observations (no other better explanation/alternative available) that the notion of past deceleration or “slowing down” under gravity is put forward at high redshifts?

According to Conley et al. (2007), “In an analysis of the luminosity distances of Type Ia supernovae (SNe Ia), Jha et al. (2007) presented evidence for an offset between the Hubble constant measured from SNe Ia with $2500 \text{ km s}^{-1} < cz < 7400 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and the Hubble constant from those with $7400 \text{ km s}^{-1} < cz < 45,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Specifically, the more distant SNe are slightly fainter than one would expect, implying a high local value of H_0 ”. The value of H_0 derived by Jha et al. (2007) is 6.5% higher using the nearby Hubble flow objects with $2500 \text{ km s}^{-1} < cz < 7400 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ as compared to the distant Hubble flow objects with $7400 \text{ km s}^{-1} < cz < 45,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.

Why should it be that a remote object with high recession velocity is not only further away than expected, but it is also yielding a lower value of slope (or a slower rate of expansion, thereby suggesting its deceleration or “slowing down”) as compared to a nearby, local object with low recession velocity?

6. AN UNDISCOVERED ASPECT

If an epoch of “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” can be advocated (Riess et al. 2004), then, epochs of “consecutive expansion that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion” can also be advocated.

It remains undiscovered that an object that begins expanding before in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion (as a result of consecutive expansion) will not only be further away than expected, but it will also be yielding a lower value of slope (or a slower rate of expansion) even with high recession velocity as compared to an object with low recession velocity that begins expanding comparatively later in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion.

Such an interpretation imparts the liberty to an observer located in any expansion epoch to observe expansion attributes that appear similar to cosmic acceleration, therefore, there is nothing special about the current epoch – to an observer in any expansion epoch, preceding expansion epochs will appear to be decelerating, whereas the observer’s current epoch of cosmic expansion, that happens to “succeed” those preceding expansion epochs, will appear to be accelerating.

Intuitively, an object that begins expanding before in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion has an utmost probability of being further away than expected; the observational fact, that such an object, which happens to be further away than expected, yields a lower value of slope (a slower rate of expansion or deceleration) even with high recession velocity as compared to an object with low recession velocity is the most compelling (independent) evidence in favour of this undiscovered aspect, that is, recession velocity interpretation of observed redshifts in an expanding Universe (as shown in Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8, Figure 46, and supported by notable excerpts quoted in (15) of Section 9) serves as a powerful “confirmatory test” (a litmus test) that alone provides the most compelling (independent) evidence in favour of this undiscovered aspect.

Plotting together the high-recession-velocity remote structures that began expanding before, and the low-recession-velocity local structures that began expanding comparatively later, causes the Hubble diagram to deviate from linearity, whereas the comparison of slope and thus the expansion rate obtained from such objects, causes the high-recession-velocity remote structures to appear as if they are receding slowly (not as fast) as compared to the low-recession-velocity local structures.

It must be noted that even with high recession velocity (no matter how high), an object that begins expanding before will never yield a value of slope, or the expansion rate that is higher than the value of slope, or the expansion rate for an object with low recession velocity (no matter how low) that begins expanding comparatively later. Comparing the slope and thus the expansion rate of such objects results in the apparent

transition of the Universe's expansion from deceleration to acceleration – an object with high recession velocity (high redshift) that began expanding before in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion will be further away than expected and will appear to be decelerating, whereas an object with low recession velocity (low redshift) that began expanding comparatively later in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion will appear to be accelerating.

7. A SIMPLE NUMERICAL PROOF

Let us consider two test particles – particle A* and particle B*. Particle A* has an extreme recession velocity of 10^6 m s^{-1} , whereas particle B* has a recession velocity of just 0.4 m s^{-1} .

Particle A* begins expanding first, after 4 seconds, particle B* begins expanding and is observed for 1 second. By the time particle B* is observed for 1 second, particle A* has already been expanding for 5 seconds. Since particle A* began expanding before, therefore, intuitively, as compared to particle B*, particle A* will undoubtedly be further away than expected.

The distance covered by particle A* in 5 seconds with a recession velocity of 10^6 m s^{-1} is $5 \times 10^6 \text{ m}$, whereas the distance covered by particle B* in 1 second with a recession velocity of 0.4 m s^{-1} is 0.4 m .

The slope or the expansion rate for these particles is obtained by using the relation,

$$H = \frac{v}{D} \quad (1)$$

where H is the slope or the expansion rate ($\text{m s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$), v is the recession velocity of the particles (m s^{-1}), and D is the distance covered by them (m). The inverse of the slope or the expansion rate ($1/H$ or H^{-1}) gives back the time (t_H) in seconds.

The value of slope or the expansion rate for particle A* with a whopping recession velocity of 10^6 m s^{-1} turns out to be $0.2 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$, whereas for particle B*, the value of slope or the expansion rate with a mere recession velocity of 0.4 m s^{-1} turns out to be $1 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$.

The value of slope or the expansion rate for particle A* even with an extreme recession velocity of 10^6 m s^{-1} is much lower (5 times lower) than the value of slope or the expansion rate for particle B* even with a mere recession velocity of 0.4 m s^{-1} . Does this scientifically imply that particle A* with high recession velocity of 10^6 m s^{-1} is decelerating, whereas particle B* with low recession velocity of 0.4 m s^{-1} is accelerating?

10^6 m s^{-1} – recession velocity of particle A* is 2.5×10^6 times higher than the recession velocity of particle B*! Such a high recession velocity of particle A* does not indicate in any way a low recession velocity, or a slower rate of expansion, or deceleration due to the gravitational attraction of matter!

Then why is particle A* with a whopping recession velocity of 10^6 m s^{-1} yielding a lower value of slope or a slower rate of expansion, thereby suggesting deceleration as compared to particle B* with a minuscule recession velocity of 0.4 m s^{-1} ?

There is absolutely no other reason for an object with high recession velocity to yield a lower value of slope (or a slower rate of expansion, thereby suggesting deceleration) and then be further away than expected, unless it began expanding before in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion.

As already discussed, even with high recession velocity (no matter how high), an object that begins expanding before will never yield a value of slope, or the expansion rate that is higher than the value of slope, or the expansion rate for an object with low recession velocity (no matter how low) that begins expanding comparatively later.

Therefore, we should refrain and never compare the slope and thus the expansion rate of such objects; not refraining from such a comparison will undoubtedly result in the apparent transition of the Universe's expansion from deceleration to acceleration – an object with high recession velocity that began expanding before will be further away than expected and will appear to be decelerating, whereas an object with low recession velocity that began expanding comparatively later will appear to be accelerating. Requiring mysterious dark energy of unknown origin to explain this apparent transition from deceleration to acceleration would unnecessarily complicate things to an unimaginable extent.

Comparing the slope and thus the expansion rate of high-recession-velocity object that began expanding before, with the slope and thus the expansion rate of low-recession-velocity object that began expanding comparatively later, causes the

high-recession-velocity object to appear as if it is receding slowly (not as fast) as compared to the low-recession-velocity object. It is only the result of this comparison that particle A* even with an extreme recession velocity of 10^6 m s^{-1} appears to be expanding at a slower rate (decelerating) as compared to particle B* with a mere recession velocity of 0.4 m s^{-1} .

8. GRAPHICAL CONFIRMATION

To further confirm the credibility of the type of expansion unravelled in this paper, it is necessary to plot some graphical relationships. Therefore, we will take into consideration 11 test particles with random recession velocities (recession velocities that decrease from remote to local); these test particles expand consecutively (one particle after another).

8.1. Velocity-distance relationship

Particle A (3517.60 m s^{-1}) begins expanding first, 0.1 seconds later, particle B (2983.93 m s^{-1}) begins expanding, the expansion of particle B is followed by the expansion of particle C (2648.64 m s^{-1}) after another 0.1 seconds. Consecutive expansion of particles continues in the same way for particle D (2496.43 m s^{-1}), particle E (2223.52 m s^{-1}), particle F (1676.20 m s^{-1}), particle G (1219.96 m s^{-1}), particle H (917.97 m s^{-1}), and particle I (768.62 m s^{-1}). Particle J (530.48 m s^{-1}) and particle K (257.85 m s^{-1}) are the last particles to expand; they expand exactly at the same time and are observed for 1 second. By the time these last two particles (J and K) expand and are observed for 1 second, particle A has already been expanding for 1.9 seconds, particle B for 1.8 seconds, particle C for 1.7 seconds, and so on; this becomes their respective observation/expansion time.

The above description constitutes scenario 1: Here we know very accurately the recession velocity of each and every test particle along with their corresponding expansion time frame values, that is, knowing the recession velocity, we can calculate the distance covered by a particle within a given expansion time frame. Therefore, using Equation (1), we can obtain the value of the slope or the expansion rate (H) for test particles, while the inverse of that slope or the expansion rate ($1/H$ or H^{-1}) yields the time when expansion began for them.

Now, if we were to measure redshifts and distances from the luminosity of test particles, the same way researchers use type Ia supernovae as standard candles, then, as a thought experiment, let us consider that each and every test particle is also an efficient distance indicator based on the standard luminosity that it would emit. The consistent luminosity of each and every test particle will therefore help us measure two directly-observable “end points” or the final readings of a particular expansion (both near and far): (1) redshift – how fast the particles are receding from us based on the amount of shift of a spectral line towards the red end of the spectrum, and, (2) luminosity distance – how far away the particles are based on how bright they appear to us.

Particle A begins expanding first, 0.1 seconds later, particle B begins expanding, the expansion of particle B is followed by the expansion of particle C after another 0.1 seconds. Consecutive expansion of particles continues in the same way for particle D, particle E, particle F, particle G, particle H, and particle I. Particle J and particle K are the last particles to expand; they expand exactly at the same time and expand for 1 second. By the time these last two particles (J and K) expand for 1 second, particle A has already been expanding for 1.9 seconds, particle B for 1.8 seconds, particle C for 1.7 seconds, and so on; this becomes their respective observation/expansion time.

The above description constitutes scenario 2 (this is the luminosity-interpretation of scenario 1): Here, the expanding particles have not emitted the light yet, therefore, as observers, we do not yet know the recession velocity of a test particle, we also do not yet know the distance to a test particle; in fact, we also do not yet know the corresponding expansion time frame values of the test particles – everything remains unknown just like type Ia supernova observations, that is, only when the light emitted by a test particle would reach us that we will be able to measure everything associated with its expansion – its recession velocity based on its observed redshift, its distance from us based on its standard luminosity, its value of slope or the expansion rate (H) using Equation (1), and the time when expansion began for it from the inverse of its slope or the expansion rate (H).

As a matter of fact, this is exactly how type Ia supernovae are used as cosmological probes to map how fast the Universe is expanding as explained by Riess (*News Hour* 1998), “we would like to map out the universe. We would like to see how fast it’s expanding, but the universe is very dark. And occasionally a supernova explodes and it illuminates a piece of the universe. And while it’s lit up, we can use that supernova to measure how fast that piece of the universe is rushing away from us”. So, basically, it is the directly-observable “end points” or the final readings of a particular expansion (both near and far) – redshift and luminosity distance – that are taken into consideration to map the expansion history of the Universe; it is only when a supernova explodes that it helps illuminate a piece of the Universe, before this luminous event, everything remains unknown, that is, only when the light emitted by a type Ia supernova reaches us that we are able to measure everything associated with its expansion: (1) redshift – how fast the supernovae are receding from us (recession velocity) based on the amount of shift of a spectral line towards the red end of the spectrum, and, (2) luminosity distance – how far away the supernovae are based on how bright they appear to us.

The Universe being very dark also makes it impossible for us to use expanding test particles as cosmological probes to map how fast the Universe is expanding; this is where the standard luminosity of test particles comes to the rescue. Exactly 1 second after the expansion of particle J and particle K, every test particle emits a very bright flash of light (consistent luminosity), following this luminous event, the particles are again no longer visible but continue expanding. Therefore, every test particle illuminates a piece of the Universe. And while the particles are lit up, we can use them to measure how fast a piece of the Universe is rushing away from us.

Since test particles would be at different distances, therefore, with finite velocity of light, it is obvious that the light emitted by test particles will not reach us at the same time (Equation (4) – according to Riess (2016 (Seminar))), “we cannot measure time because we have not found clocks, really good clocks in the Universe, but instead we measure distance, we measure how far away something is and we know that, that distance relates to the time by the speed of light (Distance (~ct)), and so by going out and measuring lots of distances and redshifts we can measure the expansion rate of the Universe both today and in the past”). Therefore, from the emitted light, or the light that eventually reaches us from the test particles, we will be able to measure two directly-observable quantities: (1) redshift – how fast the particles are receding from us (recession velocity) based on the amount of shift of a spectral line towards the red end of the spectrum, and, (2) luminosity distance – how far away the particles are based on how bright they appear to us.

Table 1

11 test particles with recession velocities and distances based on scenario 1 and scenario 2.

Particle	Recession velocity ($v = cz$) ($m s^{-1}$)	Distance (D) (m)
A	3517.60	6683.440
B	2983.93	5371.074
C	2648.64	4502.688
D	2496.43	3994.288
E	2223.52	3335.280
F	1676.20	2346.680
G	1219.96	1585.948
H	917.97	1101.564
I	768.62	845.482
J	530.48	530.480
K	257.85	257.850

Based on scenario 1 and scenario 2, the data for 11 test particles has been tabulated above in Table 1, and the velocity-distance relationship for these test particles has been plotted in Figure 9. The plot is remarkably similar to the redshift-distance relationship for 588 type Ia supernovae (Figure 5), and to the velocity-distance relationship for 5 type Ia supernovae (Figure 21).

Therefore, with respect to Figure 9, the following are the inferences based on the “end points” or the final readings of

a particular expansion (both near and far) associated with the expansion of test particles (scenario 1 and scenario 2):

- (1) Based on luminosity interpretation, remote particles are fainter than one would expect as they are further away than expected, implying a high local value of H_0 (consistent with the description given by Conley et al. (2007)).
- (2) Remote particles are not only further away than expected, but they are also yielding a lower value of slope (a shallower slope), or a slower rate of expansion (deceleration or slowing down) even with high recession velocities as compared to the local particles that are yielding a higher value of slope (a steeper slope), or a faster rate of expansion (acceleration or speeding up) even with low recession velocities.
- (3) Direct measurements of the expansion using test particles suggest that the expansion of our portion of the Universe is *accelerating* (consistent with the description given by Starkman et al. (1999)).
- (4) The observed distance to a remote particle is larger than the one expected from the locally-measured expansion rate (consistent with the description given by Durrer (2011)).
- (5) Distant particle’s velocity is falling below the predicted value. Or, to put it another way, a particle with a given recession velocity is farther away than expected – and hence fainter – as the Universe is accelerating (consistent with the description given by Riess and Turner (*Scientific American* 2004)).
- (6) High-redshift or high-recession-velocity remote particles are receding slowly (not as fast, therefore, decelerating or “slowing down”) as compared to low-redshift or low-recession-velocity local particles.

Therefore, as a test, it would be interesting to send the following plot (Figure 9 (as it is)) to the proponents of cosmic acceleration to see if they infer acceleration or not.

Figure 9. Velocity-distance relationship for 11 test particles (local and remote particles) expanding consecutively (one particle after another). Distances to remote particles are larger than expected with respect to local particles without acceleration. In other words, expansion initiated for remote particles in the preceding expansion epochs before it did for local particles in the current (or more recent) expansion epoch.

The value of slope for the most distant, remote particle A in Figure 9 is $0.526315789 m s^{-1} m^{-1}$ (a lower value of slope, or a slower rate of expansion even with high recession velocity of $3517.60 m s^{-1}$) – does this imply deceleration or slowing down? The inverse of this slope yields the original observation/expansion time of 1.9 seconds. For local particles, particle J and particle K, the value of slope (slope of the blue line) turns out to be $1 m s^{-1} m^{-1}$ (a higher value of slope, or a faster rate of expansion even with low recession velocities of $530.48 m s^{-1}$ and $257.85 m s^{-1}$ respectively) – does this imply acceleration or speeding up? The inverse of this slope yields the original observation/expansion time of 1 second.

The recession velocity of particle A is 6.63 times higher than the recession velocity of particle J, and 13.64 times higher than the recession velocity of particle K. Particle A still happens to yield a lower value of slope, thereby suggesting a slower rate of

expansion or deceleration as compared to these two particles (not to mention again that particle A is further away than expected as compared to these two particles).

Such a trend makes it imperative to conclude that there is absolutely no other scientifically-valid reason for an object with high recession velocity to yield a lower value of slope (or a slower rate of expansion, thereby suggesting deceleration) and then be further away than expected as compared to an object with low recession velocity, unless it began expanding before.

High recession velocities of remote objects yielding a lower value of slope do not indicate their deceleration. Similarly, low recession velocities of local objects yielding a higher value of slope do not indicate their acceleration. Requiring mysterious dark energy of unknown origin to explain such a transition would only complicate things to an unimaginable extent.

Since expansion began for remote particles before it did for local particles, therefore, remote particles are not only further away than expected, but they are also yielding a lower value of slope (or a slower rate of expansion) even with high recession velocities as compared to local particles that are yielding a higher value of slope (or a faster rate of expansion) even with low recession velocities. It therefore appears that local particles are expanding at a faster rate as compared to remote particles. One would therefore be forced into believing that local particles, as compared to remote particles, are accelerating.

8.2. Expansion rate versus time relationship

Although the observational fact that a remote object which happens to be further away than expected yields a slower rate of expansion even with high recession velocity as compared to a local object that yields a faster rate of expansion even with low recession velocity is the most compelling (independent) evidence to suggest that remote structures began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local structures, however, to further confirm upon this aspect, we will plot expansion rate versus time relationship for such a scenario where remote particles with high recession velocities (high redshifts) began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low recession velocities (low redshifts).

Figure 10. Plot of expansion rate versus time when expansion began (measured from past to present) for 5 type Ia supernovae (remote and local supernovae from Figure 5) shows an accelerating expansion (expansion rate increasing with time). Expansion rate for remote supernovae that are further away than expected (see Figure 5 and Figure 21) is lower even with high recession velocities as compared to the expansion rate for nearby, local supernovae even with low recession velocities.

Here in Figure 10, we can see that expansion rate is increasing with time; expansion rate for remote supernovae is lower than the expansion rate for local supernovae – Universe is expanding slower in the past and is expanding faster now.

Now we need to plot the expansion rate versus time relationship when particles with high recession velocities (high redshifts) began expanding before the expansion got initiated for particles with low recession velocities (low redshifts).

As discussed previously in Section 8.1, the high-recession-velocity (high-redshift) particle A began expanding first, 0.1 seconds later, particle B began expanding, the expansion of particle B was followed by the expansion of particle C after another 0.1 seconds. Consecutive expansion of particles continued in the same way for remaining particles. Low-recession-velocity (low-redshift) particles – particle J and particle K were the last particles to expand; they expanded exactly at the same time and were observed for 1 second. By the time these last two particles expanded and were observed for 1 second, particle A had already been expanding for 1.9 seconds, particle B for 1.8 seconds, particle C for 1.7 seconds, and so on.

Figure 11. Plot of expansion rate versus time when expansion began (measured from past to present) for 11 test particles (remote and local particles from Figure 9) mimics an accelerating expansion (expansion rate appears to be increasing with time) when remote particles with high recession velocities began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low recession velocities. Expansion rate for remote particles that are further away than expected (see Figure 9) is lower even with high recession velocities as compared to the expansion rate for nearby, local particles even with low recession velocities, similar to what we observe for type Ia supernovae in Figure 10.

In Figure 10 and Figure 11, the time when expansion began has been obtained by using the relation,

$$t_H = \frac{1}{H} \quad (2)$$

See H from Equation (1). The similarities encountered while plotting Figure 10 and Figure 11 (expansion rate increasing with time) are strong enough to indicate that remote structures with high recession velocities (high redshifts) began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local structures with low recession velocities (low redshifts).

8.3. Expansion factor versus time relationship

Since redshift also helps indicate the size of the Universe now as compared to its size when the light was emitted (Francis and Schmidt 2020), therefore, the study conducted here based on the redshifts of 10 test particles should also help us confirm that high-redshift remote structures began expanding before the expansion got initiated for low-redshift local structures.

Velocity of particles (v) in m s^{-1} has been converted to redshift (z) by using the relation,

$$z = \frac{v}{c} \quad (3)$$

where c is the velocity of light in m s^{-1} . Similarly, the light-travel-time (t_c) in seconds corresponding to the distance (D) to particles in meters has been calculated by using the relation,

$$t_c \approx \frac{D}{c} \quad (4)$$

Just like a high-redshift remote supernova that we observe to be further away than expected as a result of cosmic acceleration (Figure 5 and Figure 6), we are observing the high-redshift

remote particle A which is also further away than expected (however, not because of acceleration, but because it began expanding before as per consecutive expansion (Figure 9)), at a distance (D) of $2.227813333 \times 10^{-5}$ light seconds (6683.44 m) with a redshift (z) of $1.172533333 \times 10^{-5}$ (3517.60 m s^{-1}).

The percentage of shift in the spectral lines towards the red end of the electromagnetic spectrum for particle A is $1.172533333 \times 10^{-3}\%$ (this also corresponds to the percentage of expansion that has occurred while the light from particle A has been in transit before reaching us), in other words, the Universe is $1.172533333 \times 10^{-3}\%$ larger now than it was when the light was emitted.

To get a factor (expansion factor) which would help us calculate the time when the Universe was 100% smaller than now, we need to divide 100% by the percentage of shift in the spectral lines towards the red end of the electromagnetic spectrum for a particular particle (this percentage of shift in the spectral lines also corresponds to the percentage of expansion that has occurred while the light from that particular particle has been in transit before reaching us), therefore, the expansion factor for the remote particle A is,

$$\frac{100}{1.172533333 \times 10^{-3}} = 85285.4219 \quad (5)$$

(The expansion factor can also be obtained directly by taking an inverse of the redshift (z)). This factor suggests that we will have to reverse the expansion 85285.4219 times back into the past when the scale factor was zero. (Since $t = D/v$, and $v = cz$, therefore, $t = D/cz$, on isolating we get, D/c which is the light-travel-time (t_c), and $1/z$ which is the expansion factor). Therefore, multiplying the expansion factor obtained for particle A (85285.4219) with its light-travel-time in seconds ($2.227813333 \times 10^{-5}$ seconds) gives back the original expansion time (t) for particle A (1.9 seconds), that is, the time (t) in the past when particle A began expanding (the time when expansion began for every particle has been obtained accurately; this also includes remote particles that deviate from linearity in Figure 9).

Figure 12. Plot of expansion factor versus time when expansion began (measured from past to present) for 10 test particles (remote and local particles from Figure 9) mimics an accelerating expansion (expansion factor increasing exponentially with time – red curve) when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts. The green curve (overlapping with the red curve) traces out an expansion that initially decelerates before accelerating (also see Figure 18).

Here in Figure 12, the time when expansion began for test particles has been obtained by multiplying their expansion factor with their light-travel-time in seconds, and, this is consistent with time when expansion began for these test particles obtained in Figure 11 by using Equation (2).

High-redshift remote particles that began expanding before are yielding a smaller expansion factor (expansion factor for remote particle A (85285.4219)) as compared to the expansion

factor that is increasing exponentially with time for low-redshift local particles that began expanding comparatively later (expansion factor for local particle J (565525.5618)).

We will now follow the same method for type Ia supernovae (remote and local supernovae from Figure 5) to see if they also exhibit a similar expansion factor versus time relationship. A similar relationship will further help us confirm that remote structures with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local structures with low redshifts.

We have remote supernova 1996H at a distance (D) of 14.5043 Gly with a redshift (z) of 0.62; this remote supernova is further away than expected as compared to local supernovae. The percentage of shift in the spectral lines towards the red end of the electromagnetic spectrum for this supernova is 62% (this also corresponds to the percentage of expansion that has occurred while the light from this remote supernova has been in transit before reaching us), in other words, the Universe is 62% larger now than it was when the light was emitted.

To get the expansion factor which would help us calculate the time when the Universe was 100% smaller than now, we need to divide 100% by the percentage of shift in the spectral lines towards the red end of the electromagnetic spectrum for a particular supernova (this percentage of shift in the spectral lines also corresponds to the percentage of expansion that has occurred while the light from that particular supernova has been in transit before reaching us), therefore, the expansion factor for the remote supernova 1996H is,

$$\frac{100}{62} = 1.612903226 \quad (6)$$

This factor suggests that we will have to reverse the expansion 1.612903226 times back into the past when the scale factor was zero. Therefore, multiplying the expansion factor obtained for supernova 1996H (1.612903226) with its light-travel-time in years (14.510739×10^9 years) gives back the original expansion time (t) for supernova 1996H (23.4044×10^9 years), that is, the time (t) in the past when supernova 1996H began expanding.

Figure 13. Plot of expansion factor versus time when expansion began (measured from past to present) for 5 type Ia supernovae (remote and local supernovae from Figure 5) shows an accelerating expansion (expansion factor increasing exponentially with time).

Here in Figure 13, the time when expansion began for supernovae has been obtained by multiplying their expansion factor with their light-travel-time in years, and, this is consistent with time when expansion began for these supernovae obtained in Figure 10 by using Equation (2).

High-redshift remote supernovae that are further away than expected as a result of cosmic acceleration are yielding a smaller expansion factor (expansion factor for remote supernova 1996H (1.612903226)) as compared to the expansion factor that is increasing exponentially with time for low-redshift local supernovae (expansion factor for local supernova 1994S (65.93696426)).

In Figure 12, high-redshift remote particles that are further away than expected are yielding a smaller expansion factor as compared to the expansion factor that is increasing exponentially with time for low-redshift local particles, and, such an exponential increase in expansion factor has occurred when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts, in other words, such an exponential increase in expansion factor has occurred without subjecting any test particle to acceleration or deceleration.

In Figure 13, high-redshift remote supernovae that are further away than expected are also yielding a smaller expansion factor as compared to the expansion factor that is increasing exponentially with time for low-redshift local supernovae – similar to what we observe in Figure 12 using test particles.

Such a similarity further confirms that remote structures with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local structures with low redshifts as per consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion.

8.4. Expansion factor versus light-travel-time relationship

In the previous section we obtained the expansion factor, the light-travel-time, and the time when expansion began. We plotted expansion factor versus time (time when expansion began) relationship and found expansion factor increasing exponentially with time (past to present – remote to local) when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts (as per consecutive expansion), a similar relationship was also obtained for 5 type Ia supernovae. The time when expansion began was obtained by multiplying the expansion factor with the light-travel-time (also consistent with Equation (2)).

Here we will consider plotting expansion factor versus light-travel-time relationship for the same scenario when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts, we will then plot expansion factor versus light-travel-time relationship for 5 type Ia supernovae to see if they also exhibit a similar relationship. A similar relationship, if obtained, will further help us confirm that remote structures with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local structures with low redshifts.

Figure 14. Plot of expansion factor versus light-travel-time (measured from past to present) for 11 test particles (remote and local particles from Figure 9) mimics an accelerating expansion (expansion factor increasing exponentially with time) when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts. Figure is consistent with Universe that is accelerating as expansion factor is increasing exponentially with time.

Plot of expansion factor versus light-travel-time relationship (measured from past to present) for 5 type Ia supernovae (remote and local supernovae from Figure 5) shows a similar relationship in Figure 15 as obtained here in Figure 14 for 11 test particles that expanded consecutively – expansion factor increasing exponentially with time.

Figure 15. Plot of expansion factor versus light-travel-time (measured from past to present) for 5 type Ia supernovae (remote and local supernovae from Figure 5) shows an accelerating expansion (expansion factor increasing exponentially with time).

8.5. Scale factor versus light-travel-time relationship

The evolution of the Universe's scale factor with time plays an important role in determining the type of Universe we live in. Measuring the variation of the Universe's scale factor with time (past to present – remote to local) would not only help us determine the type of Universe we live in, but it would also help us predict its ultimate fate.

The study conducted here based on the redshifts of 11 test particles should also help us confirm that remote structures with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local structures with low redshifts.

We have remote supernova 1996H at a distance (D) of 14.5043 Gly with a redshift (z) of 0.62. As a result of cosmic acceleration, this remote supernova is further away than expected as compared to the nearby, local supernovae. The scale factor ($a(t)$) which denotes the size of the Universe when the light was emitted is obtained by using the relation,

$$a(t) = \frac{1}{1+z} \quad (7)$$

where z is the redshift. The light-travel-time (t_c) in years corresponding to the distance (D) to the supernovae in meters has been calculated by using Equation (4).

Figure 16. Plot of scale factor versus light-travel-time (measured from past to present) for 5 type Ia supernovae (remote and local supernovae from Figure 5) shows an accelerating expansion (scale factor increasing with time).

In Figure 16, high-redshift remote supernovae that are further away than expected are yielding a smaller scale factor (scale factor for remote supernova 1996H (0.61728395)) as compared to the scale factor that is increasing with time for low-redshift local supernovae (scale factor for local supernova 1994S (0.985060571)), in fact, scale factor evolution with time (past to present) exhibiting a curve as obtained in Figure 16 clearly depicts an accelerating expansion.

Now we need to plot the scale factor versus light-travel-time relationship when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts as per consecutive expansion.

Velocity (v) of particles in $m\ s^{-1}$ has been converted to redshift (z) by using Equation (3). Similarly, the light-travel-time (t_c) in seconds corresponding to the distance (D) to the particles in meters has been calculated by using Equation (4).

Just like a high-redshift remote supernova that we observe to be further away than expected (as a result of cosmic acceleration) as shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6, we are observing the high-redshift remote particle A which is also further away than expected (however, not because of acceleration, but because it began expanding before as a result of consecutive expansion (Figure 9)) at a distance (D) of $2.227813333 \times 10^{-5}$ light seconds (6683.44 m), exhibiting a redshift (z) of $1.172533333 \times 10^{-5}$ ($3517.60\ m\ s^{-1}$). The scale factor ($a(t)$) for these 11 test particles has been obtained by using Equation (7).

Figure 17. Plot of scale factor versus light-travel-time (measured from past to present) for 9 test particles (remote and local particles from Figure 9) mimics an expansion that accelerates (scale factor increasing with time) when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts. Figure is consistent with Universe that is accelerating as scale factor is increasing with time (in agreement with Figure 16).

As shown above in Figure 17, scale factor versus light-travel-time relationship for 9 test particles is consistent with an expansion that is accelerating with time (past to present – remote to local) even when the test particles have not been subjected to acceleration, whereas in Figure 18, scale factor versus light-travel-time relationship for 11 test particles is consistent with an expansion that first decelerates, and then accelerates even when the test particles have not been subjected to deceleration or acceleration. This apparent transition of particles’ expansion from deceleration to acceleration as obtained in Figure 18 can also be seen in Figure 12 as traced by the green curve.

It is evidently clear from Figure 17 and Figure 18 that high-redshift remote particles that are further away than expected are yielding a smaller scale factor (scale factor for remote particle A (0.999988274)) as compared to the scale factor that is increasing with time for low-redshift local particles (scale factor for local particle K (0.99999914)). Why should test particles that were not at all subjected to deceleration or acceleration exhibit scale factor evolution consistent with a Universe whose expansion is accelerating over time?

Figure 18. Plot of scale factor versus light-travel-time (measured from past to present) for 11 test particles (remote and local particles from Figure 9) mimics an expansion that first decelerates, and then accelerates when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts. Figure is consistent with Universe that first decelerates, and then accelerates (in agreement with Figure 19).

In Figure 17 and Figure 18, the observed increase in scale factor with time (past to present) for test particles (remote to local) has occurred when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts as per consecutive expansion, in other words, such an increase in scale factor has occurred without subjecting any test particle to deceleration or acceleration.

In Figure 16 and Figure 19, far and near supernovae are also exhibiting a similar scale factor evolution as measured from past to present – high-redshift remote supernovae that are further away than expected are also yielding a smaller scale factor as compared to the scale factor that is increasing with time for low-redshift local supernovae – similar to what we observe in Figure 17 and Figure 18 using test particles.

Such a similarity further confirms that high-redshift remote structures began expanding in the preceding epochs of cosmic expansion before the expansion got initiated for low-redshift local structures in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion – in agreement with consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion.

Figure 19. Plot of scale factor versus light-travel-time (measured from past to present) for type Ia supernovae helps depicting the expansion history of the Universe – the plot depicts Universe’s expansion that first decelerates, and then accelerates. High-redshift remote supernovae that are further away than expected are yielding a smaller scale factor as compared to the scale factor that is increasing with time for the nearby, local supernovae with low redshifts, thereby indicating an accelerating expansion of the Universe. Credit: Perlmutter S., *Physics Today*, Vol. 56, 53, page 57, year 2003, reproduced with the permission of the American Institute of Physics, Copyright (2003) American Institute of Physics. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1580050>

8.6. Redshift-distance and velocity-distance relationships

Figure 20. Redshift-distance relationship for 5 type Ia supernovae (local and remote supernovae from Figure 5). Remote supernovae are further away than expected as compared to the nearby, local supernovae.

Figure 21. Velocity-distance relationship for 5 type Ia supernovae (local and remote supernovae from Figure 5). Remote supernovae are further away than expected as compared to the nearby, local supernovae.

Here we have plotted redshift-distance relationship and velocity-distance relationship for 5 type Ia supernovae from Figure 5. Both these plots, just like Figure 5, demonstrate that the very distant, remote supernovae are further away than expected, thereby getting rendered 10% to 25% dimmer as compared to the nearby supernovae. This further-away-than-expected placement of remote supernovae is attributed to dark energy – an unknown energy component that has accelerated the expansion of the Universe – without this energy component there would have been no cosmic acceleration, and without cosmic acceleration, remote supernovae would have not been placed further away than expected.

In particular, the velocity-distance relationship for local and remote supernovae (Figure 21) is characteristically similar to the velocity-distance relationship obtained for local and remote test particles (Figure 9), that is, the expansion rate for remote supernovae (Figure 10) is lower even with high recession velocities as compared to the expansion rate for nearby, local supernovae even with low recession velocities – this attribute is exactly similar to what we have observed for test particles (Figure 11) without having subjected any of those test particles to deceleration or acceleration. Such a similar attribute provides

the most compelling and an independent confirmation in favour of consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion, rather than a previous decelerated expansion and a recent accelerated expansion.

8.7. Distance-redshift relationship

Redshift-distance relationship already plotted for local and remote supernovae (Figure 5 and Figure 20) shows the deviation from linearity at high redshifts as remote supernovae are further away than expected. Here we will consider plotting distance-redshift relationship for 5 type Ia supernovae from Figure 5 (these are the same 5 type Ia supernovae that have been considered so far) we will then plot the same relationship for 11 test particles from Figure 9. A similar relationship will further help us confirm that remote structures with high redshifts began expanding in the preceding expansion epochs before the expansion got initiated for local structures with low redshifts in the current expansion epoch – in agreement with consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion.

Figure 22. Distance-redshift relationship for 5 type Ia supernovae (local and remote supernovae from Figure 5). High-redshift remote supernovae lie above the line; the deviation from linearity makes it clear enough that the distances to remote supernovae are larger than expected, thereby making them appear 10% to 25% dimmer as compared to the nearby, local supernovae. This further-away-than-expected placement of remote supernovae is attributed to a mysterious energy component that has accelerated the Universe’s expansion.

Figure 23. Distance-redshift relationship for 11 test particles (local and remote particles from Figure 9). High-redshift remote particles lie above the line; the deviation from linearity also makes it clear enough that the distances to remote particles are larger than expected.

The deviation of distance-redshift relationship from linearity at large distances (at high redshifts) depends on how the expansion rate has changed over time. The deviation from linearity implies distances to type Ia supernovae to be larger than expected and hence an obvious change in the expansion rate, that is, such an observed feat is only possible if the Universe expanded slowly in the past than it does today.

As per Figure 23, there should also be an energy component that has accelerated the expansion of particles, thereby placing remote particles further away than expected – there has also been a change in the expansion rate for test particles over time (Figure 11). However, as per Section 8.1, we are well aware that not even a single test particle was subjected to deceleration or acceleration, therefore, the presence of an energy component responsible for placing remote particles further away than expected is completely out of question. It is only because of consecutive expansion of particles wherein expansion of one particle is followed by the next in a consecutive manner that we are getting a plot that is characteristically similar to the distance-redshift relationship for 5 type Ia supernovae as shown in Figure 22.

8.8. Distance modulus versus redshift relationship

Distance modulus (μ) is the difference between the apparent magnitude (m) and the absolute magnitude (M); it denotes distances on a logarithmic scale and is given as,

$$\mu = m - M = 5 \log(D) - 5 \quad (8)$$

where D is the luminosity distance in parsecs. If we know the distance (D), for instance, we already know the distances to 11 test particles, therefore, we can calculate and obtain the distance modulus (μ) for them by using the relation,

$$\mu = 5 \log(D) - 5 \quad (9)$$

or, by using the relation,

$$\mu = 5 \log\left(\frac{D}{10}\right) \quad (10)$$

If distance modulus (μ) is known, we can obtain the distance (D) in parsecs by using the relation,

$$D = 10^{\frac{\mu}{5} + 1} \quad (11)$$

Here in Figure 24, we have plotted distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 5 type Ia supernovae from Figure 5.

Figure 24. Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 5 type Ia supernovae (local and remote supernovae from Figure 5). The red logarithmic curve shows that type Ia supernovae are further away than expected, this confirms the presence of an unknown energy component responsible for accelerating the Universe's expansion, thereby placing remote supernovae further away than expected.

Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 11 test particles (local and remote particles from Figure 9) has also been plotted in Figure 25. The similar relationship obtained for test particles (red curve) further helps us confirm that remote structures with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local structures with low redshifts – consistent with consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion.

Figure 25. Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 11 test particles (local and remote particles from Figure 9) is consistent with an accelerating Universe (in agreement with Figure 24) when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts (red curve).

8.9. Replication of results

Replication of results plays an important role in scientific analysis. If same results as the original study are obtained (reproduced) on repeating the experiment, then the analysis is most likely to be correct.

Having considered 11 test particles to prove the credibility of the study conducted in this paper that happens to be most consistent with consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion, it would now be imperative to bring in another set of test particles to further confirm upon this undiscovered aspect that mimics cosmic acceleration so perfectly well.

We will now consider 113 test particles that expand consecutively – one particle after another – in agreement with consecutive expansion. All test particles have been assigned random recession velocities that decrease from remote particles to local particles (similar to what was incorporated in Section 8.1 for 11 test particles). Consecutive expansion of these 113 test particles is observed for 2 seconds with every test particle expanding consecutively after an interval of 0.01 seconds.

Figure 26. Velocity-distance relationship for 113 test particles (local and remote particles) expanding consecutively (one particle after another). Distances to remote particles are larger than expected with respect to local particles without acceleration. In other words, expansion initiated for remote particles before it did for local particles.

Figure 26 depicts the velocity-distance relationship for 113 test particles undergoing consecutive expansion. High-recession-velocity test particles that began expanding before as a result of consecutive expansion are further away than expected – these are the remote particles. The maximum recession velocity of one such remote particle (P1) is $95,874.25 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ – this is the most distant particle in Figure 26.

Out of 113 test particles, last 13 test particles with low recession velocities (ranging between 199.478 m s^{-1} to 1 m s^{-1}) were the last particles to expand, they expanded exactly at the same time and were observed only for 1 second – these are the local particles and they exhibit a linear velocity-distance relationship as they expanded exactly at the same time – the value of slope and thus the expansion rate for these last 13 test particles is therefore the same (P101 to P113).

As shown in Figure 26, the velocity-distance relationship for 113 test particles is sufficiently self-explanatory – a plot obtained only through consecutive expansion of particles, rather than acceleration or deceleration. Remote particles that began expanding before are not only further away than expected, but they are also yielding a slower rate of expansion (deceleration) even with high recession velocities as compared to local particles that are yielding a faster rate of expansion (acceleration) even with low recession velocities, that is, the most distant, remote particle (P1) in Figure 26 even with a whopping recession velocity of $95,874.25 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ is yielding a lower expansion rate of just $0.5 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$, whereas a local particle (P113) in Figure 26 with a minuscule recession velocity of just 1 m s^{-1} is yielding a higher expansion rate of $1 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$.

How can it scientifically be justified that high recession velocity of $95,874.25 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ implies deceleration or a slower rate of expansion, whereas low recession velocity of 1 m s^{-1} implies a faster rate of expansion or acceleration? This paradoxical attribute is not something that can so easily be neglected and swept under the rug. With scientific responsibility one should be equipped with an explanation to such a paradoxical trend.

Figure 27. Plot of expansion rate versus time when expansion began (measured from past to present) for 113 test particles (remote and local particles from Figure 26) mimics an accelerating expansion (expansion rate appears to be increasing with time) when remote particles with high recession velocities began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low recession velocities. Expansion rate for remote particles that are further away than expected (see Figure 26) is lower even with high recession velocities as compared to the expansion rate for nearby, local particles even with low recession velocities.

Plot of expansion rate versus time for 113 test particles as shown above in Figure 27 gives an overall and much clearer picture how the expansion rate appears to have increased over time from past to present (remote to local) without having subjected any of those test particles to deceleration or acceleration. The plot is similar to what we have already witnessed for 11 test particles in Figure 11 and for 5 type Ia supernovae in Figure 10.

Figure 28. Plot of scale factor versus light-travel-time (measured from past to present) for 113 test particles (remote and local particles from Figure 26) mimics an expansion that accelerates (scale factor increasing with time) when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts. Figure is consistent with Universe that is accelerating as scale factor is increasing with time.

Scale factor evolution for 113 test particles shown above in Figure 28 is consistent with an expansion that is accelerating over time from past to present (remote to local). Surprisingly, not even a single test particle was subjected to deceleration or acceleration.

Figure 29. Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 588 type Ia supernovae (local and remote supernovae from Figure 5). The deviation from linearity (deviation from the blue curve) at high redshifts suggests that type Ia supernovae are further away than expected, this confirms the presence of an unknown energy component responsible for accelerating the Universe's expansion, thereby placing remote supernovae further away than expected (red curve).

As shown above in Figure 29, distance modulus versus redshift relationship is the new Hubble diagram in the cosmic literature. The plot is linear at low redshifts before deviating from linearity. The deviation from linearity at high redshifts clearly suggests that remote supernovae are further away than expected due to cosmic acceleration (red curve).

In Figure 30, distance modulus versus redshift relationship has been plotted for 113 test particles undergoing consecutive expansion, the plot is similar to what has been plotted for 588 type Ia supernovae here in Figure 29 – the plot is linear at low redshifts before deviating from linearity. The deviation from linearity at high redshifts (red curve) clearly suggests that

remote particles that began expanding before as per consecutive expansion are further away than expected; again, not even a single test particle was subjected to acceleration or deceleration.

Figure 30. Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 113 test particles (local and remote particles from Figure 26) is consistent with an accelerating Universe (in agreement with Figure 29) when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts (red curve).

Perhaps we should introduce more randomness in recession velocities of a few randomly-selected remote particles. The resultant velocity-distance relationship for 113 test particles in such a scenario turns out to be as shown below in Figure 31.

Figure 31. Velocity-distance relationship for 113 test particles (local and remote particles) expanding consecutively (one particle after another). Recession velocities here are more random for a few randomly-selected remote particles. Distances to remote particles are still larger than expected with respect to local particles without acceleration. In other words, expansion initiated for remote particles before it did for local particles.

Figure 31 is still consistent with consecutive expansion of particles – high-recession-velocity remote particles began expanding before the expansion got initiated for low-recession-velocity local particles. Overall recession velocities are still increasing with distances, however, there is more randomness now in recession velocities and hence the distances. Such randomness has made the plot more similar to the redshift-distance relationship for 588 type Ia supernovae plotted in Figure 5. Local test particles that expanded exactly at the

same time and were observed only for 1 second still continue exhibiting a linear velocity-distance relationship consistent with nearby, local supernovae.

Although random recession velocities were introduced for a few randomly-selected remote particles, the plot of expansion rate versus time relationship for these 113 test particles still remains conserved as shown below in Figure 32.

Figure 32. Plot of expansion rate versus time when expansion began (measured from past to present) for 113 test particles (remote and local particles from Figure 31) still mimics an accelerating expansion (expansion rate appears to be increasing with time) when remote particles with high recession velocities began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low recession velocities. Expansion rate for remote particles that are further away than expected (see Figure 31) is lower even with high recession velocities as compared to the expansion rate for nearby, local particles even with low recession velocities.

Figure 33. Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 113 test particles (local and remote particles from Figure 31) is still consistent with an accelerating Universe (in agreement with Figure 29) when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts (red curve).

After introducing more random recession velocities for a few randomly-selected remote particles, distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 113 test particles as shown above in Figure 33 has also become more similar to distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 588 type Ia supernovae plotted in Figure 29. Figure 33 is still consistent with consecutive

expansion of particles, rather than acceleration or deceleration of those test particles – the plot is linear at low redshifts (blue curve) and deviates from linearity at high redshifts (red curve).

8.10. Scale factor versus distance relationship

Having already plotted scale factor versus time relationship for 5 type Ia supernovae (Figure 16), 11 test particles (Figure 17 and Figure 18), and 113 test particles (Figure 28), we shall now consider plotting scale factor versus distance relationship for 588 type Ia supernovae from Figure 5 and then the same relationship for 113 test particles from Figure 31. We will also plot the scale factor versus distance relationship for 31 (binned) type Ia supernovae from Betoule et al. (2014) followed by the plotting of the same relationship for 11 test particles from Figure 9. This will help us confirm the results based on another aspect altogether.

Since distances provide an estimate of the past and the present, therefore, the scale factor evolution with distance should also help us take a look into how the scale factor has evolved from past to present (remote to local).

Figure 34. Plot of scale factor versus distance (distance giving an estimate of scale factor evolution from past to present – remote to local) for 588 type Ia supernovae (remote and local supernovae from Figure 5) shows an accelerating expansion (scale factor is increasing over time).

Figure 35. Plot of scale factor versus distance (distance giving an estimate of scale factor evolution from past to present – remote to local) for 113 test particles (remote and local particles from Figure 31) also shows an accelerating expansion (scale factor is increasing over time) when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts.

As depicted in Figure 34, Figure 35, Figure 36, and Figure 37, scale factor evolution from past to present shows a prominent increase in scale factor in the more recent epoch. For type Ia

supernovae this suggests a recent accelerated expansion. Similar relationship obtained for test particles should also suggest the same – recent accelerated expansion. However, the scale factor versus distance relationship for test particles (Figure 35 and Figure 37) has been obtained through consecutive expansion of those test particles, and not through deceleration or acceleration.

Figure 36 plotted below, depicts the scale factor evolution with distance for 31 (binned) type Ia supernovae from Betoule et al. (2014) with redshifts ranging from $z = 0.01$ to $z = 1.3$. Scale factor evolution from past to present (remote to local) shows an expansion that first decelerates, and then accelerates.

Figure 36. Plot of scale factor versus distance (distance giving an estimate of scale factor evolution from past to present – remote to local) for 31 (binned) type Ia supernovae from Betoule et al. (2014) with redshifts ranging from $z = 0.01$ to $z = 1.3$ shows an expansion that first decelerates, and then accelerates. Inner box shows the redshift-distance relationship for the same 31 (binned) type Ia supernovae.

Figure 37 plotted below, depicts the scale factor evolution with distance for 11 test particles from Figure 9. Scale factor evolution from past to present (remote to local) also shows an expansion that first decelerates, and then accelerates (in agreement with Figure 36). However, as per Figure 9, not even a single test particle was subjected to deceleration or acceleration. All these similarities make it clear enough that such a relationship can also be obtained through consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion.

Figure 37. Plot of scale factor versus distance (distance giving an estimate of scale factor evolution from past to present – remote to local) for 11 test particles (remote and local particles from Figure 9) also shows an expansion that first decelerates, and then accelerates (in agreement with Figure 36) when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts.

8.11. Deceleration parameter

Measuring the deceleration parameter (q_0) helps probing the expansion history of the Universe. We can obtain the deceleration parameter by using the following approximation,

$$q_0 \approx -\frac{2DH - 2cz - cz^2}{cz^2} \quad (12)$$

or,

$$q_0 \approx \frac{2cz + cz^2 - 2DH}{cz^2} \quad (12.1)$$

where H is the expansion rate ($\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$ or $\text{m s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$), D is the distance (Mpc or m), c is the velocity of light (km s^{-1} or m s^{-1}), and z is the redshift. Above approximations for the deceleration parameter (q_0) are valid for $z < 0.5$ and have been obtained using the following approximation from Schmidt (2012).

$$D_L \approx \frac{c}{H_0} \left[z + z^2 \frac{(1 - q_0)}{2} \right] \quad (13)$$

The surprising transition of the Universe's expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration has already shown that the deceleration parameter, as per the "current acceleration of the expansion", is negative, that is, $q_0 < 0$ (Riess et al. 1998).

We have already obtained the expansion rate versus time relationship for 5 type Ia supernovae in Section 8.2 (Figure 10) – we get an overall picture how the expansion rate has increased over time (transition from deceleration to acceleration – remote to local – past to present).

In this section we will see how the deceleration parameter values vary for the remote type Ia supernova (SN 1995K) while using evolving values of the expansion rate (H) obtained from 4 type Ia supernovae (remote to local – past to present), we will then see if the most distant, remote test particle from Figure 26 (particle P1) also exhibits a similar attribute for the deceleration parameter, that is, $q_0 < 0$ while using more recent or evolving values of the expansion rate (H).

Table 2

Deceleration parameter (q_0) values for the remote supernova (SN 1995K) obtained by using evolving values of expansion rate (H) (past to present – remote to local).

SN	H ($\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$)	q_0 values for SN 1995K
1995K	48.19194335	+ 1.000000000
1999DU	53.07308350	+ 0.577096460
1992BS	59.99558432	- 0.022671218
1994S	69.05436111	- 0.807526529

Table 2 represents the expansion rate for 4 type Ia supernovae (remote to local) and the deceleration parameter values for the remote type Ia supernova SN 1995K ($z = 0.479$, $D = 9.7211 \text{ Gly}$). The deceleration parameter is getting "more and more negative" while using evolving values of H obtained from 4 type Ia supernovae (evolving values of H signify how the expansion rate has increased over time from remote to local – past to present, while the departure of deceleration parameter from positive ($q_0 > 0$) to increasingly negative values ($q_0 < 0$) suggests the transition of the Universe's expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration) (SN 1995K yields $q_0 = -0.6$ while using H as $67 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$; this is the same q_0 value obtained by the High- z Team for SN 1995K (Schmidt 2012)).

In a Universe that is dominated by matter, one would rightfully expect the expansion rate to slow down with time due to the gravitational attraction of matter, in such a case, the deceleration parameter would simply be given as,

$$q_0 = \frac{\Omega_M}{2} \quad (14)$$

where Ω_M denotes the matter density. However, the increasingly negative values ($q_0 < 0$) for deceleration parameter obtained for the remote supernova (SN 1995K) while using more recent or evolving values of the expansion rate (H) is disturbing as it necessitates the introduction of "negative mass" exhibiting anti-gravitational effect that acts against the gravitational attraction of matter and accelerates the expansion of the Universe. According to Filippenko (2001), "In 1997 November

the results seemed puzzling" – "The only way to match the change in the expansion rate was to allow the Universe to have a "negative" mass" Riess (2012).

Now, since negative mass is practically impossible, therefore, the only solution to quench this impossible paradigm of negative mass was to reintroduce the abandoned cosmological constant " Λ ". "From our working definition of q_0 , negative values for the current deceleration (i.e., accelerations) are generated only by a positive cosmological constant and not from unphysical, negative mass density" (Riess et al. 1998). Consequently, the significance of the cosmological constant was calculated, "99.7% to 99.8% confidence no matter what the mass density" (Riess 2012). Therefore, Equation (14) now gets written as,

$$q_0 = \frac{\Omega_M}{2} - \Omega_\Lambda \quad (15)$$

where Ω_Λ denotes the energy density of empty space or vacuum (vacuum energy density). However, as discussed earlier, there is an alarming discrepancy associated with its value – a mismatch between the small observed value and the colossal theoretically-calculated value according to the quantum field theory by 120 orders of magnitude (10^{120}); a value so large would have led to a vacuum catastrophe.

Having obtained the increasingly negative values for the deceleration parameter for the remote supernova (SN 1995K) by using evolving values of expansion rate (H) obtained from 4 type Ia supernovae (remote to local – past to present), we will now bring the test particles into the picture and study how the deceleration parameter (q_0) values vary for the remote particle (P1) while using evolving values of expansion rate (H) obtained from 4 test particles (remote to local – past to present) when test particles expanded consecutively – one particle after another as per consecutive expansion.

We have already obtained the expansion rate versus time relationship for 11 test particles in Section 8.2 (Figure 11) and then for 113 test particles in Section 8.9 (Figure 27) – we get an overall picture how the expansion rate appears to have increased over time (transition from past deceleration to recent acceleration) without having subjected any of those test particles to deceleration or acceleration.

Since we have not subjected any test particle to deceleration or acceleration, therefore, it would be very interesting to see if such a similar feat would also be traced out by the most distant, remote test particle (P1) (Figure 26), that is, $q_0 < 0$ while using more recent or evolving values of the expansion rate (H). A similar behaviour would help us confirm the study conducted in this paper to an unprecedented level that advocates, not acceleration, but consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion.

Table 3

Deceleration parameter (q_0) values for the remote particle (P1) obtained by using evolving values of expansion rate (H) (past to present – remote to local).

Particle	H ($\text{m s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$)	q_0 values for P1
P1	0.5	+ 1.000000000
P41	0.625	- 1563.549397
P76	0.8	- 3753.918553
P113	1.0	- 6257.197589

Table 3 represents the expansion rate for 4 test particles (remote to local) and the deceleration parameter values for the remote particle P1 ($z = 3.195808333 \times 10^{-4}$, $D = 191,748.5 \text{ m}$). It must again be noted that remote particle P1 is the first particle that expanded, whereas local particle P113 is the last or more recent particle that underwent expansion as per consecutive expansion.

It is very clear from Table 3 that the deceleration parameter is getting "more and more negative" while using evolving values of H obtained from 4 test particles (evolving values of H signify how the expansion rate has increased over time, while the departure of deceleration parameter from positive ($q_0 > 0$) to increasingly negative values ($q_0 < 0$) suggests the transition of particles' expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration). This is exactly what we have obtained from 4 type Ia supernovae in Table 2.

The increasingly negative values for deceleration parameter ($q_0 < 0$) obtained for the remote test particle (P1) while using more recent or evolving values of the expansion rate (H) also necessitates the introduction of negative mass responsible for accelerating the expansion of test particles over time. Now, since there is no such thing as negative mass as already discussed, therefore, the only way to explain those increasingly negative values of deceleration parameter would be to introduce an energy component responsible for accelerating the expansion of those test particles with time.

It must be noted here that cosmic acceleration due to dark energy yields $q_0 < 0$ (more specifically, $-1 < q_0 < 0$), a super-exponential expansion predicted by phantom energy (an extreme case of dark energy that leads to a Big Rip – the tearing apart of the Universe from galaxy clusters to nucleons) yields $q_0 < -1$. Large and increasingly negative values for the deceleration parameter (q_0) for test particles (the expansion rate for test particles in $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$ itself being so large) depicts an expansion that has not only surpassed the accelerated expansion due to dark energy ($-1 < q_0 < 0$), but also the super-exponential expansion predicted by phantom energy ($q_0 < -1$). This necessitates the introduction of the most overwhelming amount of an energy component to account for this “super accelerated” expansion of test particles over time.

However, as we are well aware that not even a single test particle was subjected to deceleration or acceleration, therefore, the presence of an energy component responsible for the increasingly negative values of deceleration parameter, thereby indicating current acceleration of the expansion is again completely out of question. It is only because of consecutive expansion of particles wherein expansion of one particle is followed by the next in a consecutive manner that we are getting increasingly negative values for deceleration parameter for the remote test particle (P1) while using more recent or evolving values of the expansion rate (H).

8.12. Reproducibility of results

Not just replication, but reproducibility of results also plays an important role in scientific analysis. If same results as the original study are obtained “again” (consistency), then reproducibility along with replication of those results adds further credence to the analysis and helps warrant its validity.

Having considered 11 test particles and then 113 test particles to prove the validity of the study conducted in this paper that happens to be most consistent with “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, rather than “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration”, we will now bring in another set of test particles to further confirm upon this undiscovered aspect that mimics cosmic acceleration so perfectly well.

We will consider a set of 400 test particles that expand consecutively – one particle after another – in agreement with consecutive expansion. This time we will assign the redshifts of 400 type Ia supernovae from Figure 5 to these 400 test particles (redshifts ranging from 0.015 to 0.498 will help keep Equation (12) or Equation (12.1) and Equation (13) valid, this will also make the analysis more relatable in terms of actual redshifts observed). As observed for type Ia supernovae, the redshifts decrease from remote particles to local particles (similar to what has been incorporated so far). Consecutive expansion of these 400 test particles is observed for 4.99 seconds with every test particle expanding consecutively after an interval of 0.01 seconds.

Particle SN1 ($z = 0.498$) begins expanding first, 0.01 seconds later, particle SN2 ($z = 0.497$) begins expanding, the expansion of particle SN2 is followed by the expansion of particle SN3 ($z = 0.497$) after another 0.01 seconds. Consecutive expansion of particles continues in the same way for remaining particles – SN4 ($z = 0.496$), SN5 ($z = 0.495$), SN6 ($z = 0.495$), SN7 ($z = 0.493$), and so on. Particle SN400 ($z = 0.015$) is the last particle to expand, and it is observed only for 1 second. By the time this last particle (SN400) expands and is observed for 1 second, particle SN1 has already been expanding for 4.99 seconds, particle SN2 for 4.98 seconds, particle SN3 for 4.97 seconds, and so on, this becomes their respective observation time or the expansion time.

Figure 38 depicts the velocity-distance relationship for 400 test particles undergoing consecutive expansion. High-redshift test particles that began expanding before as a result of consecutive expansion are further away than expected – these are the remote particles. The maximum redshift of one such remote particle (SN1) is 0.498 – this is the most distant particle in Figure 38. Out of 400 test particles, test particle SN400 with low redshift ($z = 0.015$) was the last particle to expand and was observed only for 1 second – this is the local particle.

Figure 38. Velocity-distance relationship for 400 test particles (local and remote particles) expanding consecutively (one particle after another). Distances to remote particles are larger than expected with respect to local particles without acceleration. In other words, expansion initiated for remote particles before it did for local particles.

Velocity-distance relationship for 400 test particles is again sufficiently self-explanatory – a plot obtained only through consecutive expansion of particles, rather than acceleration or deceleration. Remote particles that began expanding before are not only further away than expected, but they are also yielding a slower rate of expansion (deceleration) even with high recession velocities as compared to local particles that are yielding a faster rate of expansion (acceleration) even with low recession velocities as shown below in Figure 39.

Figure 39. Plot of expansion rate versus time when expansion began (measured from past to present) for 400 test particles (remote and local particles from Figure 38) mimics an accelerating expansion (expansion rate appears to be increasing with time) when remote particles with high recession velocities began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low recession velocities. Expansion rate for remote particles that are further away than expected (see Figure 38) is lower even with high recession velocities as compared to the expansion rate for nearby, local particles even with low recession velocities.

Plot of expansion rate versus time for 400 test particles as shown in Figure 39 gives an overall and much clearer picture how the expansion rate appears to have increased over time from past to present (remote to local) without having subjected any of those test particles to deceleration or acceleration. The plot is similar to what we have already witnessed for 11 test particles in Figure 11, for 5 type Ia supernovae in Figure 10, and for 113 test particles in Figure 27 and Figure 32.

We need to ask ourselves an important question here to which we already know the answer – has the expansion rate really increased for test particles over time from past to present (remote to local) as a result of accelerated expansion, or is it that the expansion rate “appears” to have increased for test particles over time as a result of consecutive expansion?

Figure 40. Plot of scale factor versus light-travel-time (measured from past to present) for 400 test particles (remote and local particles from Figure 38) mimics an expansion that accelerates (scale factor increasing with time) when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts. Figure is consistent with Universe that is accelerating as scale factor is increasing with time.

Scale factor evolution for 400 test particles as shown above in Figure 40 is again consistent with an expansion that is accelerating over time from past to present (remote to local) (in agreement with Figure 16). Surprisingly, not even a single test particle was subjected to deceleration or acceleration.

Figure 41. Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 400 test particles (local and remote particles from Figure 38) is consistent with an accelerating Universe (again in agreement with Figure 29) when remote particles with high redshifts began expanding before the expansion got initiated for local particles with low redshifts (red curve).

As shown in Figure 41, distance modulus versus redshift relationship has been plotted for 400 test particles undergoing consecutive expansion, the plot is again similar to distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 588 type Ia supernovae plotted in Figure 29 – the plot is linear at low redshifts before deviating from linearity (red curve). The deviation from linearity at high redshifts clearly suggests that remote particles that began expanding before as per consecutive expansion are further away than expected; again, not even a single test particle was subjected to acceleration or deceleration.

In Section 8.11 we witnessed the increasingly negative values for the deceleration parameter for the remote supernova (SN 1995K) while using evolving values of expansion rate (H) obtained from 4 type Ia supernovae, we also witnessed the increasingly negative values for the deceleration parameter for the remote test particle (P1) while using evolving values of expansion rate (H) obtained from 4 test particles.

We will now focus on these 400 test particles and study how the deceleration parameter (q_0) values vary for the remote particle (SN5) while using evolving values of expansion rate (H) obtained from 8 test particles (remote to local – past to present) when test particles expanded consecutively – one particle after another as per consecutive expansion.

We have already obtained the expansion rate versus time relationship for these 400 test particles in this section (Figure 39) – we get an overall picture how the expansion rate appears to have increased over time (transition from past deceleration to recent acceleration) without having subjected any of those test particles to deceleration or acceleration.

Since we have not subjected any of these 400 test particles to deceleration or acceleration, therefore, it would be very interesting to see if such a similar feat would be traced out by the fifth most distant, remote test particle (SN5) (Figure 38), that is, $q_0 < 0$ while using more recent or evolving values of the expansion rate (H). A similar behaviour if obtained again will further help us confirm the study conducted in this paper to an unprecedented level that advocates “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, rather than “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration”.

Table 4

Deceleration parameter (q_0) values for the remote particle (SN5) obtained by using evolving values of expansion rate (H) (past to present – remote to local).

Particle	H ($\text{m s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$)	q_0 values for SN5
SN5	0.202020202	+ 1.00000000
SN100	0.25	+ 0.04040404
SN180	0.3125	- 1.20959596
SN250	0.4	- 2.95959596
SN300	0.5	- 4.95959596
SN340	0.625	- 7.45959596
SN375	0.8	- 10.95959596
SN400	1.0	- 14.95959596

Table 4 represents the expansion rate for 8 test particles (remote to local) and the deceleration parameter values for the remote particle SN5 ($z = 0.495$, $D = 735,075,000$ m). It must again be noted that remote particle SN5 is the fifth particle that expanded, whereas local particle SN400 is the last or more recent particle that underwent expansion.

It is again clear from Table 4 that the deceleration parameter is getting “more and more negative” while using evolving values of H obtained from 8 test particles (evolving values of H signify how the expansion rate has increased over time, while the departure of deceleration parameter from positive ($q_0 > 0$) to increasingly negative values ($q_0 < 0$) suggests the transition of particles’ expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration). This is exactly what we have obtained from 4 type Ia supernovae in Table 2.

According to Equation (14), if q_0 is negative, then Ω_M also gets rendered negative while solving for it. Therefore, the increasingly negative values for deceleration parameter ($q_0 < 0$) obtained for the remote test particle (SN5) while using more recent or evolving values of the expansion rate (H) again

necessitates the introduction of negative mass responsible for accelerating the expansion of test particles over time. Since negative mass is practically impossible as discussed earlier, therefore, the only way to account for those increasingly negative values of the deceleration parameter (q_0) would be to consider the presence of an overwhelming amount of cosmological constant or the energy associated with empty space (Equation (15)) that has accelerated the expansion of particles over time.

However, as we are well aware that not even a single test particle was subjected to deceleration or acceleration, therefore, the presence of an overwhelming amount of cosmological constant or an unknown energy component responsible for the increasingly negative values of deceleration parameter, thereby indicating current acceleration of the expansion of those test particles is again completely out of question. It is only because of consecutive expansion of particles wherein expansion of one particle is followed by the next in a consecutive manner that we are getting increasingly negative values for the deceleration parameter for the remote test particle (SN5) while using more recent or evolving values of the expansion rate (H).

The similar departure of the deceleration parameter (q_0) from positive ($q_0 > 0$) to increasingly negative values ($q_0 < 0$) for test particles as well as for type Ia supernovae help confirm that remote structures began expanding before in the preceding epochs of cosmic expansion before the expansion got initiated for local structures in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion – the study conducted in this paper using test particles is therefore most consistent with consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion, rather than cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration.

8.13. Hubble residuals

Figure 42. Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for 31 (binned) type Ia supernovae from Betoule et al. (2014) (from $z = 0.01$ to $z = 1.3$) showing the transition of the Universe's expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration (red curve) (see Figure 36 (inner box)).

A very nearby, local supernova plotted above in Figure 42 at a redshift (z) of 0.01 is yielding an expansion rate of $\approx 77 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$. The expansion rate obtained from this local supernova has been used to plot a linear expansion in the above figure (blue curve); the deviation from linearity at high redshifts (red curve) makes it obvious that distances to remote supernovae are larger than expected as a result of cosmic acceleration.

Figure 43 A. Hubble residual plot for 31 (binned) type Ia supernovae from Figure 42 (from $z = 0.01$ to $z = 1.3$) showing a slower expansion in the past and a faster expansion in the current (or more recent) epoch (linear expansion $\approx 77 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$).

Hubble residual plots ($\Delta\mu = \mu_{\text{Cosmic Acceleration}} - \mu_{\text{Linear Expansion}}$) obtained for SNe Ia and SNe Ia + GRBs (Figure 43 A, Figure

43 B, Figure 43 C, Figure 43 H, Figure 43 I) and the Hubble residual plots ($\Delta\mu = \mu_{\text{Consecutive Expansion}} - \mu_{\text{Linear Expansion}}$) obtained for test particles (Figure 43 D, Figure 43 E, Figure 43 F, Figure 43 G, Figure 43 J, Figure 43 K) are consistent with an expansion that has sped up over time.

Figure 43 B. Hubble residual plot for 31 (binned) type Ia supernovae from Figure 42 (from $z = 0.01$ to $z = 1.3$) showing a slower expansion in the past and a faster expansion in the current (or more recent) epoch (linear expansion $\approx 69 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$).

Figure 43 C. Hubble residual plot for 585 of 588 type Ia supernovae from Figure 1 (from $z = 0.015$ to $z = 1.39$) showing a slower expansion in the past and a faster expansion in the current (or more recent) epoch.

Figure 43 D. Hubble residual plot for 11 test particles from Figure 25 showing a slower expansion in the past and a faster expansion in the current (or more recent) epoch.

Figure 43 E. Hubble residual plot for 113 test particles from Figure 30 showing a slower expansion in the past and a faster expansion in the current (or more recent) epoch.

Figure 43 F. Hubble residual plot for 113 test particles from Figure 33 showing a slower expansion in the past and a faster expansion in the current (or more recent) epoch.

Figure 43 G. Hubble residual plot for 16 of 400 test particles from Figure 41 (from $z = 0.015$ to $z = 0.498$) showing a slower expansion in the past and a faster expansion in the current (or more recent) epoch.

Figure 43 H. Hubble residual plot for 588 type Ia supernovae (from $z = 0.015$ to $z = 1.7$) and for 216 GRBs (from $z = 0.414$ to $z = 9.3$) from Figure 3 showing a slower expansion in the past and a faster expansion in the current (or more recent) epoch.

Figure 43 I. Hubble residual plot for 588 type Ia supernovae from Figure 1 (from $z = 0.015$ to $z = 1.7$) showing a slower expansion in the past and a faster expansion in the current (or more recent) epoch.

Figure 43 J. Hubble residual plot for 10 of 400 test particles from Figure 41 (from $z = 0.015$ to $z = 0.25$) showing a slower expansion in the past and a faster expansion in the current (or more recent) epoch.

Figure 43 K. Hubble residual plot for 7 of 400 test particles from Figure 41 (from $z = 0.015$ to $z = 0.108$) showing a slower expansion in the past and a faster expansion in the current (or more recent) epoch.

Hubble residual plots add further credence and help confirm the study conducted in this paper that happens to be most consistent with “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, rather than “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration”.

8.14. Magnitude-redshift relationship

Another confirmation for consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion would come from plotting the magnitude-redshift relationship for 400 test particles from Figure 38 by using the following equation from Perlmutter et al. (1999),

$$m_B = 5 \log(H_0 D) + M_B \quad (16)$$

where m_B is the effective magnitude, H_0 is the current or the local expansion rate in $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$, D is the luminosity distance to a supernova in Mpc, and M_B is the absolute magnitude in the B-band at the maximum of a supernova’s light curve.

Figure 44. Magnitude-redshift relationship for 60 type Ia supernovae plotted by using the data from Perlmutter et al. (1999, Figure 2(a)) showing the transition of the Universe’s expansion from deceleration to acceleration (red curve) (as measured from past to present – high redshift to low redshift – remote to local).

The Hubble diagram or the magnitude-redshift relationship plotted above in Figure 44 by using the data from Perlmutter et al. (1999, Figure 2(a)) shows distances to remote supernovae to be larger than expected (red curve), that is, deviation from linearity (blue curve) at high redshifts or at large distances and hence a change in the expansion rate (recent acceleration (speeding up) at low redshifts and past deceleration (slowing down) at high redshifts). Had the Hubble diagram been linear throughout ($H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$ (blue curve in Figure 44), then a supernova at a redshift (z) of 0.83 would have exhibited an effective magnitude of 23.53099674, however, in an accelerating Universe (red curve in Figure 44), a supernova at a redshift (z) of 0.83 has an effective magnitude of 24.32 as it is further away than expected. Figure 44 therefore shows that the Hubble diagram is not linear at high redshifts or at large distances; it deviates from linearity as a result of cosmic acceleration. According to Davis and Lineweaver (2004), “the linear result lies 12σ from the Λ CDM concordance result”.

Since we already know the distance to each and every test particle in Mpc (400 test particles from Figure 38), as well as the local value of expansion rate (H_0) obtained from the very local test particle (SN400) in $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$, therefore, Equation (16) can be used to trace out an expansion history for these 400 test particles. Here M_B is taken as -3.45 ; the same value used by Davis and Lineweaver (2004) to plot the magnitude-redshift relationship for type Ia supernovae from the data by Perlmutter et al. (1999, Figure 2(a)) since this value closely approximates their plotted curves.

Figure 45 plotted for 400 test particles is not any different from Figure 44; the blue curve traces out a linear expansion consistent with the local expansion rate ($H_0 = 1 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$ ($3.0857 \times 10^{19} \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$)) obtained from the very local test particle (SN400), whereas the deviation from linearity (red curve) shows that distances to remote particles are larger than expected and hence an “apparent” change in the expansion rate, that is, recent acceleration (speeding up) at low redshifts and past deceleration (slowing down) at high redshifts (Figure 39 shows this “apparent” change in the expansion rate). Had the Hubble diagram been linear throughout ($H_0 = 1 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$ ($3.0857 \times 10^{19} \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$)) (blue curve in Figure 45), then the most distant test particle (SN1) at a redshift (z) of 0.498 would have exhibited an effective magnitude of 22.42175299, however, due to this “apparent” acceleration of test particles (red curve in Figure 45), the most distant, remote particle

(SN1) at a redshift (z) of 0.498 has an effective magnitude of 25.91225572 as it is further away than expected.

It must be noted that not even a single test particle was subjected to acceleration or deceleration, however, the linear result (blue curve) in Figure 45 still lies more than 12σ from the non-linear result (red curve) – and for a very obvious reason – the linear relationship (blue curve) is an attribute of expansion in the same epoch, whereas the deviation from linearity (red curve) is an attribute of expansion in different epochs, that is, consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion. In other words, there would have been no deviation from linearity had expansion initiated for all 400 test particles in the same epoch of cosmic expansion; every test particle would have obeyed the blue curve, as a result, the most distant, remote particle (SN1) along the extremity of the red curve ($z = 0.498$) as shown below in Figure 45 would have exhibited an effective magnitude of 22.42175299 instead of 25.91225572.

Figure 45. Magnitude-redshift relationship for 400 test particles from Figure 38 also shows the transition of particles’ expansion from deceleration to acceleration (red curve) (as measured from past to present – high redshift to low redshift – remote to local). The linear result (blue curve) lies more than 12σ from the non-linear result (red curve).

Now, we can go a step further and write Equation (16) as,

$$m_B = 5 \log \left[H_0 \left(\frac{v}{H} \right) \right] + M_B \quad (17)$$

where H_0 is the current or the local expansion rate in $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$, $H = v/D$ is the expansion rate of a supernova in $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$ at a given luminosity distance (D) in Mpc with observed redshift (z), and $v = cz$ is its recession velocity in km s^{-1} as per its observed redshift (z). Therefore, Equation (17) can further be written as,

$$m_B = 5 \log \left[H_0 \left(\frac{cz}{H} \right) \right] + M_B \quad (18)$$

According to Equation (16), the luminosity distance (D) in Mpc for a remote supernova at a redshift (z) of 0.83 along the extremity of the red curve in Figure 44 with an m_B of 24.32 turns out to be 5115.663387 Mpc. The expansion rate (H) (using $H = v/D$, with $v = cz$) for this further-away-than-expected remote supernova turns out to be $48.67403915 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$. Substituting these values in Equation (18) gives back the original value of m_B as 24.32 for this remote supernova at $z = 0.83$ along the extremity of the red curve in Figure 44; this is the same value for m_B obtained while using Equation (16).

As an additional test for Equation (18), let us take into account the distance moduli (μ) for this remote supernova at $z = 0.83$ (SN 1997AP) according to the Supernova Cosmology Project (Union 2 (Amanullah et al. 2010) and Union 2.1 (Suzuki et al. 2012)) ($\mu = 43.5528793931$ and $\mu = 43.5424034366$ respectively) ($\mu_{\text{avg.}} = 43.54764141485$), this ($\mu_{\text{avg.}}$) translates to a luminosity distance (D) of 5122.863685 Mpc. The expansion rate (H) (using $H = v/D$, with $v = cz$) for this further-away-than-expected remote supernova (SN 1997AP) turns out to be $48.60562671 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$. Substituting these values in Equation (18) yields m_B as 24.3230542 for this remote supernova at $z = 0.83$ along the extremity of the red curve in Figure 44; this is the same value for m_B obtained while using Equation (16).

Equation (18) is also valid for test particles plotted in Figure 45 (for the blue curve (linear result) as well as for the red curve (non-linear result)).

According to Equation (16), the distance (D) in Mpc for a remote particle at a redshift (z) of 0.498 along the extremity of the red curve in Figure 45 with an m_B of 25.91225572 turns out to be $2.416002852 \times 10^{-14} \text{ Mpc}$ ($745,506,000 \text{ m}$) is the original value in Figure 38). The expansion rate (H) (using $H = v/D$, with $v = cz$) for this further-away-than-expected remote particle turns out to be $6.183767534 \times 10^{18} \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$ ($0.200400801 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$). Substituting these values in Equation (18) gives back the original value of m_B as 25.91225572 for this remote particle at $z = 0.498$ along the extremity of the red curve; this is the same value for m_B obtained while using Equation (16).

This shows that the $v = cz$ relation is also a good approximation for the non-linear result if used with the corresponding non-linear value of H (H also obtained using the cz relation) – and this is again for a very obvious reason – for the linear result or linear expansion (expansion in the same epoch) $H = H_0$, whereas for the non-linear result or non-linear expansion (expansion in different epochs) $H \neq H_0$.

The similarity obtained while plotting the magnitude-redshift relationship further helps confirm the study conducted in this paper. As was already discussed in Section 6, if an epoch of “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” can be advocated (Riess et al. 2004), then, epochs of “consecutive expansion that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion” can also be advocated, in fact, all similarities encountered so far in this paper for test particles and for type Ia supernovae (replication and reproduction of results) help confirm that expansion began for remote structures in the preceding epochs of cosmic expansion before it did for local structures in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion – the study conducted in this paper using test particles is therefore most consistent with “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, rather than “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration”.

9. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Directly-observable quantities (actual observables) play an important role in observational cosmology. In an expanding Universe, luminosities and redshifts of type Ia supernovae are the directly-observable quantities that help us probe the expansion history of the Universe (same applies for quasars (QSOs) and gamma-ray bursts (GRBs)).

A supernova explosion illuminates a part of the Universe, which is otherwise dark, and before the supernova fades away into the darkness, researchers make sure to measure these directly-observable quantities – luminosity and redshift. Luminosity helps measure the distance (luminosity distance), whereas the redshift helps measure how fast that supernova is receding from us – these together help unravel the expansion rate of the Universe, or how fast the Universe is expanding. It were these directly-observable quantities (luminosity and redshift) that helped the research teams (the High- z Team (HZT) and the Supernova Cosmology Project (SCP)) discover the startling transition of the Universe’s expansion from past deceleration or “slowing down” at high redshifts to recent acceleration or “speeding up” at low redshifts – high-redshift remote supernovae appeared 10% to 25% dimmer as they were further away than expected as compared to low-redshift local supernovae.

Since the luminosity distance helps probe the expansion history of the Universe up to that redshift, therefore, based on these directly-observable quantities in an expanding Universe (luminosity and redshift) that can be considered as the directly-observable “end points” (or the final readings) of a particular expansion (both near and far), the study conducted in this paper, using a purely kinematic interpretation of type Ia supernova sample, provides the first-ever conclusive evidence strongly in favour of “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, rather than “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” (Riess et al. 2004).

Based on pure Hubble flow interpretation (recession velocities arising solely due to the expansion of the Universe), the study conducted in this paper unravels an undiscovered aspect of inhomogeneous expansion that perfectly mimics cosmic acceleration; the study essentially shows how consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion (one expansion epoch following the next in a consecutive manner) mimics cosmic acceleration,

more precisely, it is shown that preceding epochs of cosmic expansion “appear to be decelerating or slowing down” as compared to the epoch of cosmic expansion that succeeds them. The key aspects of the study conducted in this paper have been summarized below:

(1) Direct and the best observational evidence for an accelerating Universe comes from the comparison of redshift-distance relationship for high and low-redshift type Ia supernovae. As compared to nearby, local supernovae, remote supernovae appear 10% to 25% dimmer as they are further away than expected. There are some astrophysical effects that can imitate this direct evidence for an accelerating Universe from type Ia supernovae, for instance, a pervasive screen of extragalactic grey dust could dim the supernovae (Aguirre 1999a, 1999b), thereby tricking us into believing that remote supernovae are further away than expected, luminosity evolution of type Ia supernovae can also impact the measurements if high-redshift type Ia supernovae are intrinsically fainter as compared to the low-redshift ones (Drell et al. 2000). However, according to Riess et al. (2004), “To date, no evidence for an astrophysical origin of the apparent faintness of SNe Ia has been found (Riess 2000, Coil et al. 2000, Leibundgut 2001, Sullivan et al. 2003)”. More recent studies conducted by Betoule et al. (2014), Scolnic et al. (2018), Kenworthy et al. (2019), and Brout et al. (2022) have also confirmed cosmic acceleration based on type Ia supernova observations. The study conducted by Scolnic et al. (2018) provided $> 6\sigma$ evidence for an accelerating Universe using type Ia supernovae alone.

(2) Just like type Ia supernovae, quasars (QSOs) (Risaliti and Lusso 2015) and gamma-ray bursts (GRBs) (Demianski et al. 2017 and Dirirsa et al. 2019) have also been used as standard candles to study how the expansion of the Universe has changed over time. Studies conducted using quasars and GRBs, just like type Ia supernova observations, are also consistent with cosmic acceleration, that is, recent acceleration or “speeding up” at low redshifts and past deceleration or “slowing down” at high redshifts.

(3) Since direct and the best observational evidence for an accelerating Universe came from type Ia supernova observations (Riess et al. 1998 and Perlmutter et al. 1999); not to mention that the evidence for an accelerating Universe from type Ia supernovae-only sample is $> 6\sigma$ (Scolnic et al. 2018), therefore, the analysis conducted in this paper deals with the comparison of low-redshift type Ia supernovae ($z = 0.01$, $z = 0.015$) with a high-redshift type Ia supernova ($z = 1.7$), a quasar ($z = 6$), and a GRB ($z = 9.3$).

(4) By finding type Ia supernovae at different distances and measuring their redshifts, we can plot the expansion rate of the Universe against time. In Figure 5, the redshift of a remote supernova ($z = 1.7$ – light shifted by 170% (Schmidt 2007, SAO)) is 112 times higher than the redshift of a local supernova ($z = 0.015166$), in Figure 6, the redshift of the most distant supernova ($z = 0.479$) is 14 times higher than the redshift of a local supernova ($z = 0.0333$), similarly, in Figure 3, the redshift of the most distant GRB ($z = 9.3$) is 930 times higher than the redshift of a local supernova incorporated by Betoule et al. 2014, Scolnic et al. 2018, and Kenworthy et al. 2019 ($z = 0.01$); high redshifts are therefore no joke! Then, why does every high-redshift remote expansion (redshift even as high as 9.3 – light shifted by 930%) appear to be less or insufficient as compared to low-redshift local expansion (redshift as low as 0.01 – light shifted by just 1%)? In other words, studies that are in perfect agreement with an accelerating Universe demonstrate that the expansion rate obtained for local supernovae is higher with low redshifts as compared to the expansion rate obtained for remote supernovae, quasars, and GRBs with high redshifts. Moreover, since observed redshifts in an expanding Universe also provide an estimate of recession velocities as shown in Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 46, therefore, it is very disturbing (conflicting) to find that low recession velocities (low redshifts) indicate a faster rate of expansion (acceleration or “speeding up”), whereas high recession velocities (high redshifts) indicate a slower rate of expansion (deceleration or “slowing down”). Such an aspect cannot be ignored and swept under the rug, because, the more shifted a spectral line is towards the red end of the spectrum (redshift), the faster that object is said to be receding from us in an expanding Universe;

according to Davis and Lineweaver (2004), “higher redshift galaxies are more distant from us and receding faster than lower redshift galaxies”. The notion of “deceleration or slowing down” at high redshifts is, therefore, an unsettling paradox.

(5) The evidence for an accelerating Universe came from measuring how the expansion rate of the Universe has changed over time. Since the deviation of the redshift-distance relationship from linearity at large distances (high redshifts) implies distances to remote supernovae to be larger than expected and hence an obvious change in the expansion rate (the steeper the slope or the line is, the faster the expansion is), therefore, we say that the Universe is expanding faster now and had a slower expansion in the past. This apparent transition of the Universe’s expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration is explained by invoking dark energy – a mysterious and hypothetical energy of unknown origin having no explanation in fundamental physics. As pointed out by Durrer (2011), “our single indication for the existence of dark energy comes from distance measurements and their relation to redshift. Supernovae, cosmic microwave background anisotropies and observations of baryon acoustic oscillations simply tell us that the observed distance to a given redshift z is larger than the one expected from a Friedmann–Lemaître universe with matter only and the locally measured Hubble parameter”. Also, according to Mohayaee et al. (2021), “it was inferred (based on type Ia supernova observations) that the Hubble expansion rate is accelerating as if driven by a positive Cosmological Constant Λ in Einstein’s theory of gravity. This is still the only *direct* evidence for the ‘dark energy’ that is the dominant component of today’s standard Λ CDM cosmological model. Other data such as baryon acoustic oscillations (BAO) in the large-scale distribution of galaxies, temperature fluctuations in the cosmic microwave background (CMB), measurement of stellar ages, the rate of growth of structure, *etc.* are all ‘concordant’ with this model but do not provide independent evidence for accelerated expansion”.

(6) Theoretical calculation for the value of dark energy believed to be the intrinsic energy associated with empty space or the vacuum energy according to the quantum field theory results in a huge 120-orders-of-magnitude (10^{120}) discrepancy. Such a colossal value of the cosmological constant would have resulted in a vacuum catastrophe; it would have ripped the Universe apart; structures we observe in the Universe would have not formed, and life as we know it would have not existed. The fact that there is no fundamental explanation available in physics for this mysterious and hypothetical energy component, suggests that it has only been introduced as a fudge factor or an ad hoc to account for the apparent transition of the Universe’s expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration.

(7) One should also consider that “expansion of gas molecules in a vacuum chamber by the virtue of vacuum energy or dark energy” has never been heard before. In fact, it is worth noting that an experiment conducted by Sabulsky et al. (2019) by using atom interferometry to detect dark energy acting on a single atom inside an ultra-high vacuum chamber showed no trace of any mysterious energy. Dark energy believed to be stronger in high-vacuum environments should have easily been detected acting on a minuscule mass – a single atom.

(8) Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for near and far objects (Figure 1, Figure 2, and Figure 3) is the new Hubble diagram. Supernova observations ($z > 1$) confirmed the result that the Universe was decelerating in the past before it began accelerating (Riess 2012). Therefore, by just looking where the objects lie on the Hubble diagram (including Figure 5), one gets to know if the Universe is accelerating or decelerating over time. High-redshift remote objects ($z = 1.7$, $z = 6$, $z = 9.3$) that are further away than expected are expanding at a slower rate (decelerating) as compared to a low-redshift local object ($z = 0.015$), and this is where a paradoxical trend gets uncovered.

(9) It is an observational fact, and also according to Davis and Lineweaver (2004), “higher redshift galaxies are more distant from us and receding faster than lower redshift galaxies”. Moreover, only high recession velocity can be linked with an observational redshift (z) of 1.7 – the more shifted a line in the spectrum is towards the red (redshift), the faster that object is said to be receding from us in an expanding Universe. Furthermore, this has also been acknowledged by Nugent (Research News 2001) while referring to this highly-redshifted supernova with a redshift (z) of 1.7, Nugent remarks, “highly

redshifted objects are moving away from us so fast". However, something very strange that does not go hand in hand simultaneously with the given statement is then advocated while referring to the same supernova ($z = 1.7$), "the supernova allows us to glimpse an era when matter in the universe was still relatively dense and expansion was still slowing under the influence of gravity. More recently the dark energy has begun to predominate and expansion has started to speed up" (Nugent, *Research News* 2001). These statements clearly imply that the "highly-redshifted type Ia supernova with a redshift (z) of 1.7 is moving away from us so fast (of course, due to expansion) that it is also providing us an indication of past deceleration or slowing down under the gravitational influence of matter" – this sounds paradoxical; how can "moving away from us so fast" simultaneously be an indication of "slowing down" under the gravitational influence of matter? Intuitively, "moving away from us so fast" and "slowing down" do not go hand in hand simultaneously. Also, at the time of the discovery of this most distant supernova at a high redshift of 1.7, one of the questions raised by Schmidt (2007, *SAO*) was, "how fast was the object moving away?" This would help measure how fast the Universe was expanding in the past. Consequently, "this most distant exploding star provided the remarkable answer. As predicted, the Universe was slowing down" in the past (Schmidt 2007, *SAO*). However, the acknowledgement by Nugent (*Research News* 2001), while referring to this supernova itself ("highly redshifted objects are moving away from us so fast"), renders the notion of past deceleration or "slowing down" at high redshifts very conflicting, particularly when the redshift is high and the question raised is, "how fast was the object moving away?" It is very disturbing to accept that high-recession-velocity remote expansion ($z = 1.7$) also indicates (simultaneously) a slower rate of expansion (deceleration or "slowing down") as compared to low-recession-velocity local expansion ($z = 0.01, z = 0.015$) – a paradox. Moreover, based on the velocity versus luminosity distance relationship for type Ia supernovae (Figure 6 and Figure 8) as well as the plot by the High- z Supernova Search Team (Figure 7), it is again disturbing to find that further-away-than-expected remote supernovae even with high recession velocities (60% of speed of light) are yielding a slower rate of expansion (deceleration) as compared to the nearby, local supernovae that are yielding a faster rate of expansion (acceleration) even with low recession velocities (just 1% of speed of light). Confidently enough, remote expansion at 60% of speed of light is way faster than local expansion at just 1% of speed of light. Then why should we encounter such a paradoxical (conflicting) trend wherein remote expansion at 60% of speed of light indicates a slower rate of expansion (deceleration), whereas local expansion at just 1% of speed of light indicates a faster rate of expansion (acceleration)? Same question also arises while taking into account the following magnitude-redshift relationship for type Ia supernovae that acknowledges high recession velocities at high redshifts (illustrated by Howell (*American Scientist* 2013) – one of the co-authors of Conley et al. (2011)).

Figure 46. Magnitude-redshift relationship for type Ia supernovae from various surveys (shown in different colours). Credit: Howell D. A., *American Scientist*, Vol. 101, 4, page 274, year 2013. Reprinted by permission of *American Scientist*, magazine of Sigma Xi, The Scientific Research Honor Society. Copyright © 2013 The Scientific Research Honor Society. <https://doi.org/10.1511/2013.103.274> (This figure is a part of the study conducted by Conley et al. (2011) and shows that "SN data alone require cosmic acceleration at > 99.999% confidence" <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/0067-0049/192/1/1>)

(10) Such a paradoxical or a conflicting trend as just discussed in (9) is not limited only to type Ia supernova observations. To study how the expansion of the Universe has changed over time, Risaliti and Lusso (2015) used quasars as standard candles (up to $z \approx 6$) as quasars are available in large numbers especially at much higher redshifts as compared to type Ia supernovae. The Hubble diagram (distance modulus vs. redshift relationship) obtained by them for those quasars (extending up to $z > 6$) is in perfect agreement with the Hubble diagram for type Ia supernovae in the redshift (z) range of 0.01 to 1.4 as shown in Figure 2. Therefore, the study conducted by them using quasars is also consistent with "cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration" (Riess et al. 2004).

(11) Studies incorporating gamma-ray bursts (GRBs) have gone even beyond by focusing at much higher redshifts (up to $z \approx 8$ and $z \approx 9$ (Dirirsa et al. 2019 and Demianski et al. 2017 respectively)). GRBs, just like type Ia supernovae, have also been used as standard candles to probe the expansion history of the Universe. The results obtained using GRBs, just like quasars and type Ia supernovae, are also consistent with cosmic acceleration, that is, past deceleration or "slowing down" at high redshifts and recent acceleration or "speeding up" at low redshifts as shown in Figure 3.

(12) Now, according to Riess et al. (2001), "If the cosmological acceleration inferred from SNe Ia is real, it commenced rather recently, at $0.5 < z < 1$. Beyond these redshifts, the universe was more compact and the attraction of matter dominated the repulsion of dark energy. At $z > 1$, the expansion of the universe should have been decelerating". Quasars, as depicted by the Hubble diagram (Figure 2) which extends up to $z > 6$, are way beyond, GRBs, as depicted by the Hubble diagram (Figure 3) which extends up to $z > 9$, are even way beyond, at these redshifts, the Universe was more compact, and the expansion of the Universe should have been decelerating according to Riess et al. (2001). However, when we observe remote objects, (a supernova at $z = 1.7$, a quasar at $z \approx 6$, or a GRB at $z \approx 9$), we find that they are further away than expected (as per the observed luminosity), and they have high redshifts (as per the observed shifts in their spectral lines towards the red), and as already stated, the more shifted a line in the spectrum is towards the red (redshift), the faster that object is said to be receding from us in an expanding Universe; this is exactly what the High- z Team has also depicted in their plot (Figure 7); as a matter of fact, how type Ia supernovae are used as cosmological indicators to map how fast the Universe is expanding has succinctly been explained by Riess (*News Hour* 1998), "we would like to map out the universe. We would like to see how fast it's expanding, but the universe is very dark. And occasionally a supernova explodes and it illuminates a piece of the universe. And while it's lit up, we can use that supernova to measure how fast that piece of the universe is rushing away from us". So basically while a supernova is lit up, it provides us two important observable quantities – luminosity and redshift. Luminosity helps measure the distance, whereas the redshift helps measure how fast the supernova is receding from us – these together help unravel the expansion rate of the Universe, or how fast the Universe is expanding; according to Riess (2012), "The relation between redshift and distance is then used to determine the expansion rate of the Universe. Supernovae with greater redshifts and distances reveal the past expansion rate. When compared to their nearby brethren they can measure how the expansion rate has changed over time". Now, it is because this given description is valid that Riess et al. (1998) incorporated seven nearby supernovae with low redshifts corresponding to recession velocities of 7000 km s^{-1} within 108 Mpc and obtained the local expansion rate (H_0) as $65 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ (this local expansion rate is 6% greater than the expansion rate measured for the more distant objects as noted by Zehavi et al. (1998)). Therefore, if nearby, local supernovae with low redshifts can be incorporated to measure the local expansion rate by deeming their low redshifts ($z \ll 1$) as recession velocities of 7000 km s^{-1} , then intuitively, do distant, remote supernovae with high redshifts ($z > 1$) not imply that they are receding from us at even higher recession velocities in an expanding Universe? Does recession velocity interpretation of observed redshifts in an expanding Universe "miraculously" disappear for high-redshift objects, or, is it only to reconcile with type Ia supernova observations (no other

better explanation/alternative available) that the notion of past deceleration or “slowing down” under gravity is put forward at high redshifts? It is very disturbing (surprising even) that discoveries at high redshifts ($z > 1$) get advocated as evidence for past deceleration or “slowing down” under the gravitational attraction of matter (Riess et al. 2001, Riess et al. 2004, Riess 2012) particularly when low redshifts ($z \ll 1$) are clearly advocated as recession velocities of 7000 km s^{-1} (Riess et al. 1998) and $30,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (*European Southern Observatory (ESO) 1998*). Even more disturbing (shocking even) is the official acceptance of such an impossible-to-go-together notion that advocates deceleration or “slowing down” at high redshifts without raising even a single question when it is already known that “higher redshift galaxies are more distant from us and receding faster than lower redshift galaxies” (Davis and Lineweaver 2004), when it is already known that the more shifted a line in the spectrum is towards the red (redshift), the faster that object is said to be receding from us in an expanding Universe. One should answer, how can every high-redshift (high-recession-velocity) remote expansion ($z = 1.7, z = 6$, and $z = 9.3$) even scientifically be justified or termed as deceleration or “slowing down” under gravity as compared to low-redshift (low-recession-velocity) local expansion ($z = 0.01$)?

(13) Finding this question to be a problematic threat to the notion of past deceleration or “slowing down” at high redshifts, a proponent, or a supporter of cosmic acceleration would readily suggest that recession velocities (particularly at high redshifts) are meaningless. Such a suggestion renders the recession velocity interpretation of observed redshifts in an expanding Universe meaningless for high-redshift objects, helps reconcile with type Ia supernova observations the notion of past deceleration or “slowing down” under gravity at high redshifts, and relieves one from the burden of providing a logical justification to the notion of deceleration or “slowing down” at higher and higher recession velocities (higher and higher redshifts ($z > 1$)). According to Vishniac (2022) (*American Astronomical Society Journals’ Editor-in-Chief*) (private communication (electronic) (April 2022)), “As long as the universe is expanding, redshift will always rise for more distant objects. If one insists on quoting a velocity that will also rise. However, that velocity is just a convention anyhow and corresponds to something meaningful only in our immediate neighbourhood”. A more precise reason for such a paradigm shift of recession velocity interpretation of observed redshifts from “meaningful at low redshifts ($z \ll 1$) to meaningless at high redshifts ($z > 1$)” may be found embedded in the curved spacetime of General Relativity – “In the curved spacetime of general relativity, there is no unique way to compare vectors at widely separated spacetime points, and hence the notion of the relative velocity of a distant galaxy is almost meaningless” (Bunn and Hogg 2009); according to them, the spacetime curvature is small over regions encompassing nearby objects, specifically those with $z \ll 1$; within this region there should be no hesitation in interpreting the observed redshifts as recession velocities. They also state that aside from the nearby, low-redshift sources, the spacetime curvature can also be neglected in low-density cosmological models. For instance, in a low but nonzero density cosmological model, the length scale associated with spacetime curvature is much longer than the horizon distance. Hence, the spacetime curvature effects (that is, gravitational effects) are weak throughout the observable volume and the recession velocity interpretation remains valid even for galaxies with arbitrarily high redshifts (Bunn and Hogg 2009). Another view by Davis and Lineweaver (2004) deals specifically with the focus set by some of the physics community on the observable, that is, the redshift; according to them, “Recession velocities of individual galaxies are of limited use in *observational* cosmology because they are not directly observable. For this reason some of the physics community considers recession velocities meaningless and would like to see the issue swept under the rug”. However, according to Bunn and Hogg (2009), the enlightened view presented by many cosmologists and astrophysicists regarding this observable (the redshift) is far from universal; many cosmologists and astrophysicists advocate that distant galaxies are “really at rest”, and that the observed redshift is a consequence of some sort of “stretching of space” as per the general relativistic description. However, in general relativity itself, this “stretching of space” explanation of the redshift is quite problematic. Light is

governed by Maxwell’s equations (or their general relativistic generalization), which contain no “stretching of space term” (Bunn and Hogg 2009). Moreover, if observables are so important in *observational* cosmology such that it is the directly observable redshift that gets taken into consideration by some of the physics community and not the recession velocity as it is not directly observable, then why worry about something that is also not directly observable at the present cosmic time. For instance, according to Bunn and Hogg (2009), “if a distant galaxy’s redshift is measured today, we wouldn’t expect the result to depend on what the galaxy is doing today, nor on what the observer was doing long before the age of the dinosaurs”. They argue that the recession velocity interpretation is valid even for more distant galaxies, that is, those with redshifts of order one or more where we cannot approximate the spacetime as flat with good accuracy. They advocate that if we wish to discuss the redshift of a distant galaxy as a recession velocity, we need to be willing to talk about the velocity of the galaxy *then* relative to us *now*. That is, recession velocities as per the observed redshifts (this is exactly what Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8, Figure 46, and the description by Riess and Turner (*Scientific American* 2004) do). They also provide a suitable example to support this claim, that is, “when astronomers measure the orbital speeds of planets orbiting other stars, the measured velocities are always of this sort”. And, according to them, “There is an excellent reason for this convention: we never have information about what a distant object is doing (or if the object even exists) at the present cosmic time. Any statement in which “now” is used to refer to the present cosmic time at the location of a distant object is not about anything observable”. Recession velocity interpretation of the observed redshift in an expanding Universe is therefore not “just a convention” (Vishniac 2022), it is a “useful convention” for which there is an excellent reason. Additionally, Bunn and Hogg (2009) show that the redshifts of distant objects in an expanding Universe may be viewed as kinematic shifts due to relative velocities; they argue that if they are forced to interpret the redshift, this interpretation is more natural than any other. This further strengthens the question that I have been asking, that is, if the redshifts of distant objects in an expanding Universe may be viewed as kinematic shifts due to relative velocities, since this interpretation is more natural than any other, then how can higher and higher redshifts (higher and higher recession velocities) logically be justified as “slowing down” under gravity? Moreover, if low redshifts can qualify as recession velocities while advocating “recent acceleration or *speeding up*”, then high redshifts must also qualify as recession velocities while advocating “past deceleration or *slowing down*”. Suggesting that recession velocities are meaningful only at low redshifts and meaningless at high redshifts is literally like switching all of a sudden from recession velocity (at low redshift ($z \ll 1$)) to redshift (at high redshift ($z > 1$)) on the same axis of the plot. No such absurd mid-way-switching has ever been observed in the literature; researchers plot either the redshift-distance relationship, or the velocity-distance relationship for type Ia supernovae, and therefore, with respect to the latter, recession velocities cannot be deemed meaningless even at *larger redshifts* in an expanding Universe. According to Davis and Lineweaver (2004), “If recession velocity were meaningless we could not refer to an ‘expanding universe’ and would have to restrict ourselves to some operational description such as ‘*fainter objects have larger redshifts*’”; according to them, “The host of low redshift distance measures and the multitude of available evidence for the Big Bang model all suggest that higher redshift galaxies are more distant from us and receding faster than lower redshift galaxies”. According to Jha et al. (2007), “Constructing a Hubble diagram requires a Hubble flow sample, for which the measured recession velocities are dominated by the cosmological redshift (as opposed to peculiar motions)”. According to Shanks et al. (2019), “we need to go to distances beyond the largest local inhomogeneities so that the recession velocity completely dominates any peculiar velocity”. So, are recession velocities at high redshifts meaningless where they are completely dominant? According to the proponents of cosmic acceleration – Riess and Turner (*Scientific American* 2004), “Astronomers can deduce the recession velocity of a supernova by measuring the redshift of the light from the galaxy in which it lies”. According to them, the expansion history of the Universe

“is encoded in the relation between the distances and recession velocities of galaxies. If the expansion is speeding up, the distant galaxy’s velocity would fall below the predicted value. Or, to put it another way, a galaxy with a given recession velocity will be farther away than expected – and hence fainter – if the universe is accelerating”. The genie is suddenly out of the bottle and has turned the table! Descriptions like these, by none other than the proponents of cosmic acceleration themselves, make it clear that recession velocities are not just a convention; recession velocities do correspond to something meaningful even beyond our immediate neighbourhood for the discovery of cosmic acceleration to make sense as per the description given by them. If velocity corresponds to something meaningful only in our immediate neighbourhood as suggested by Vishniac (2022), then, as per this suggestion, one should readily take into consideration the evidence presented by Jha et al. (2007) for the 6.5% offset between the Hubble constant (H_0) measured from the nearby Hubble flow sample of type Ia supernovae ($2500 \text{ km s}^{-1} < cz < 7400 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) and the Hubble constant (H_0) measured from the distant Hubble flow sample of type Ia supernovae ($7400 \text{ km s}^{-1} < cz < 45,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) – “Specifically, the more distant supernovae are slightly fainter than one would expect, implying a high local value of H_0 ” (Conley et al. 2007) (the more distant supernovae are slightly fainter than one would expect as they are slightly further away than expected). Now, both these Hubble flow samples are from our immediate neighbourhood where velocity has been said to correspond to something meaningful (Vishniac 2022), therefore, in such a case, rather than sweeping the question under the rug, one is expected to answer, how can the distant (slightly-further-away-than-expected), high-recession-velocity Hubble expansion ($7400 \text{ km s}^{-1} < cz < 45,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) be justified as a slower rate of expansion (6.5% slower) as compared to the nearby, low-recession-velocity Hubble expansion ($2500 \text{ km s}^{-1} < cz < 7400 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), particularly when objects with $cz \geq 2500 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ have been considered by Jha et al. (2007) to be in the Hubble flow? This particular question cannot be swept under the rug since both these Hubble flow samples are from our immediate neighbourhood where velocity has been said to correspond to something meaningful (Vishniac 2022). Moreover, one can use a convention as a test to help locate a *needle in a haystack*, or help separate *the wheat from the chaff*; there is no hard-and-fast rule that says one cannot, or should not use a convention as a test, in fact, using a convention as a test can spark the fruitful hint to help solve a profound problem. Furthermore, even if recession velocities are suggested to be a convention, then, even a convention (involving something as elementary as velocity) should make sense; it should not defy logic. However, with respect to cosmic acceleration, once redshifts get interpreted in terms of recession velocities, the notion of deceleration or “slowing down” at higher and higher recession velocities ($z > 1$) really makes no sense; it clearly defies logic, and, therefore, this problem, instead of being addressed, gets swept under the rug, just because there is no answer. Is this notion of deceleration or “slowing down” at higher and higher recession velocities ($z > 1$) not an exposure of a logical shortcoming (or a loophole) associated with the startling discovery of cosmic acceleration? According to Riess (2020 (Seminar)), “Don’t sweep “problems” under the rug. “Problems” are often clues!” Therefore, is the notion of deceleration or “slowing down” at higher and higher recession velocities ($z > 1$) not the “problem” that provides the hint to a “clue”? An interpretation that can logically justify deceleration or “slowing down” at higher and higher recession velocities ($z > 1$) would definitely be its plus point over the discovery of cosmic acceleration that fails to do so.

(14) Now, if one still wants to suggest recession velocities (particularly at high redshifts) to be meaningless, then the description given by Riess and Turner (*Scientific American* 2004) regarding the distant galaxy’s velocity falling below the predicted value if the expansion is speeding up should also be declared meaningless, Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 46 should also be declared meaningless, recession velocities of 7000 km s^{-1} incorporated by Riess et al. (1998) from the observed redshifts of seven nearby low-redshift supernovae (within 108 Mpc) to determine the local expansion rate as $65 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ should also be declared meaningless, the comparison of this local expansion rate which happens to be 6% greater than the expansion rate measured for the more distant

objects as noted by Zehavi et al. (1998) should also be declared meaningless, and meaningless should also be the recession velocities of $2500 \text{ km s}^{-1} < cz < 7400 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from the redshifts of nearby Hubble flow objects and the recession velocities of $7400 \text{ km s}^{-1} < cz < 45,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from the redshifts of distant Hubble flow objects incorporated by Jha et al. (2007) to derive the value of H_0 which is 6.5% higher using the nearby Hubble flow sample as compared to the distant Hubble flow sample. Clearly, “*expanding Universe*”, “*accelerating Universe*”, “Universe’s expansion is *not slowing down* with time, as expected, *but is speeding up*”, “remote supernovae, quasars, and GRBs are *not receding as quickly* as expected from observations of the local ones” (as per the discovery of accelerating Universe), that is, the distant galaxy’s velocity is falling below the predicted value as the expansion is speeding up (as per the description given by Riess and Turner (*Scientific American* 2004)), and then, the expansion rate measured in “ $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ ” that itself has units of *velocity* over distance, all these necessarily require a velocity description to make sense in an expanding Universe.

(15) As a matter of fact, the original discovery of accelerating Universe itself was based (to a reasonable extent) on measuring the recession velocities of type Ia supernovae from their observed redshifts (see Figure 6 and Figure 7) and finding that a distant galaxy’s velocity fell below the predicted value (Riess and Turner (*Scientific American* 2004)) as discussed in (13) of this section, that is, remote supernovae were found to be receding slowly (not as fast, therefore, decelerating or “slowing down”) as compared to local supernovae; here are some notable excerpts that vouch for recession velocity interpretation of observed redshifts in an expanding Universe – “Team members (HJT) measured the *speed at which these distant supernovae are moving away*. The rate was then compared with the motion of supernovae much closer to Earth” – “How far away a supernova is, and how *fast it’s moving away from us*, tells us how fast the universe is expanding, Riess says” (*CNN* 1998). Another excerpt from *Science News* (1998) states this more specifically, “The team (HJT) also measured the supernovas’ *recession velocity*”. Here is another excerpt describing the discovery of the most distant supernova ever seen in 1992 ($z = 0.458$), “The scientists (SCP) are planning to use the light from this supernova – and from others like it – to make a precise measurement of its distance from Earth and the *velocity at which it is receding from us in the expanding universe*” (*Currents*, Lawrence Berkeley Laboratory 1992). Riess et al. (1998) clearly mention in their study the incorporation of seven nearby supernovae with recession velocities of 7000 km s^{-1} within 108 Mpc and obtain local expansion rate (H_0) as $65 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ – an expansion rate that is 6% greater than that measured for the more distant objects as noted by Zehavi et al. (1998)). Here is another excerpt from the book *Bold Science* (Anton 2000), “They (SCP) plotted their findings on a graph, matching the distance of the stellar explosions against their *velocity* as they were swept away by cosmic expansion”. Here is yet another excerpt from the 2007 *Gruber Cosmology Prize Press Release*, “they (HJT and SCP) not only needed to be able to *measure the speed with which distant objects are travelling away from us*, but also how far away they are”. Let us also recall and take a look at the excerpt that describes this astounding discovery of cosmic acceleration from “*Written in the stars*” by the Nobel Committee for Physics – the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, “By establishing the distance to the supernovae and the *speed at which they are moving away from us*, scientists hoped to reveal our cosmic fate”. This is exactly where the notion of deceleration or “slowing down under gravity” at high redshifts ($z > 1$) is made to fit in, or is made to reconcile with type Ia supernova observations as per the startling discovery of cosmic acceleration, that is, high-redshift remote supernovae were found to be receding slowly (not as fast) as compared to low-redshift local supernovae. Therefore, a problem should not arise if redshifts are interpreted in terms of recession velocities; after all, “Astronomers measure the velocity of a galaxy from its spectrum. Radial velocities show up as shifts in the wavelengths of the lines from the galaxy compared with the spectra of the same atoms at rest in the observatory: blueshifts for objects approaching us and redshifts for objects receding” (Kirshner 2004). This clearly implies that the more shifted a spectral line is towards the red end of the spectrum (redshift), the faster that object is

receding from us in an expanding Universe. However, within the framework of accelerating Universe itself, a problem soon arises once redshifts get interpreted in terms of recession velocities and the notion of deceleration or “slowing down under gravity” at higher and higher redshifts (higher and higher recession velocities) becomes very conflicting (a paradox). In sheer excitement of a startling discovery, did the researchers forget to take this into consideration that the more shifted a line in the spectrum is towards the red (redshift), the faster that object is said to be receding from us in an expanding Universe, or, is it only to reconcile with type Ia supernova observations (no other better explanation/alternative available) that the researchers have come up with such a notion that advocates the impossible – “slowing down under gravity” at high redshifts? For instance, the High- z Team acknowledge in their webpage (*The High-Z SN Search*) that an even more distant object (an even more high-redshift object) such as SN 1999FV (the most distant supernova discovered by the High- z Team between October and November 1999) “is receding at 80% of the speed of light” (of course, due to expansion). Therefore, with respect to the very surprising discovery of accelerating Universe (the apparent transition of the Universe’s expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration), how can every high-redshift (high-recession-velocity) remote expansion ($z = 1.7, z = 6, \text{ and } z = 9.3$) even be termed as deceleration or “slowing down under gravity” as compared to low-redshift (low-recession-velocity) local expansion ($z = 0.01, z = 0.015$)?

(16) Since redshifts as low as 0.01 (Betoule et al. 2014, Scolnic et al. 2018, Kenworthy et al. 2019) and 0.001 (Brout et al. 2022) can also be used to determine Universe’s expansion rate to confirm recent acceleration or “speeding up” at low redshifts and past deceleration or “slowing down” at high redshifts, therefore, in such a case, the above question becomes even more serious and rightfully demands an answer, rather than being swept under the rug.

(17) Studies that are in perfect agreement with an accelerating Universe (using SNe Ia, QSOs, and GRBs) have made it very clear to us that as compared to a minuscule redshift of 0.01 (SN Ia) that indicates acceleration, a high redshift of 1.7 (SN Ia) indicates deceleration, an extreme redshift of 6 (QSO) also indicates deceleration, and surprisingly, a whopping redshift of 9.3 (GRB) also indicates deceleration – this sounds quite weird since every high-redshift (high-recession-velocity) remote expansion ($z > 1$) simultaneously becomes an indication of deceleration or “slowing down” under the gravitational influence of matter as compared to low-redshift (low-recession-velocity) local expansion (a mere redshift of 0.01). A crucial aspect appears to have gone unnoticed, thereby making the researchers conclude that the Universe is accelerating now at low redshifts ($z \ll 1$) under the influence of hypothetical dark energy having no explanation in fundamental physics and was decelerating (“slowing down”) in the past at high redshifts ($z > 1$) under the gravitational influence of matter! According to Carroll (2004), it remains conceivable that the researchers have dramatically misinterpreted the data.

(18) The discovery of cosmic acceleration is laced with problems of its own, the first problem itself being that there is still no understanding as to why the Universe is accelerating or what is driving cosmic acceleration, and then, in order to explain this apparent acceleration, or to explain what is driving this accelerating expansion of the Universe, researchers pass the buck to an energy component which itself is mysterious, hypothetical, of unknown origin, and has no explanation in fundamental physics; this is doubly unfair; it is adding more complication to a problem that is already complicated. According to Carroll (2004), “In trying to understand the universe in which we apparently live, we are faced with a problem, a puzzle, and a scandal:

- The cosmological constant problem: why is the energy of the vacuum so much smaller than we estimate it should be?
 - The dark energy puzzle: what is the nature of the smoothly-distributed, persistent energy density which appears to dominate the universe?
 - The coincidence scandal: why is the dark energy density approximately equal to the matter density today?
- Any one of these issues would represent a serious challenge to physicists and astronomers” (Carroll 2004).

(19) According to Durrer (2011), “Dark energy is very disturbing. On the one hand, the fact that such an unexpected

result has been found by observations shows that present cosmology is truly data driven and not dominated by ideas that can be made to fit sparse observations. On the other hand, a small cosmological constant is so unexpected and difficult to bring into agreement with our ideas about fundamental physics that people have started to look into other possibilities”.

(20) One such idea that helps to take a look into another possibility that happens to mimic cosmic acceleration has therefore been presented here. The surprising discovery of accelerating Universe is the result of an undiscovered aspect that has been unravelled in this paper. Based on the study conducted and the results obtained in this paper, this undiscovered aspect perfectly mimics cosmic acceleration. The most compelling evidence that provides an independent confirmation in favour of this undiscovered aspect comes from the recession velocity interpretation of actual observable in an expanding Universe, that is, the redshift (as shown in Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 46); an observational fact, and also according to Davis and Lineweaver (2004), “higher redshift galaxies are more distant from us and receding faster than lower redshift galaxies”; as per definition, the more shifted a line in the spectrum is towards the red (redshift), the faster that object is said to be receding from us in an expanding Universe. In fact, as discussed earlier in (15) of this section, the original discovery of cosmic acceleration itself was based (to a reasonable extent) on measuring the recession velocities of supernovae from their observed redshifts (notable figures and excerpts supporting this have been referenced in (15) of this section). According to Riess and Turner (*Scientific American* 2004), “Astronomers can deduce the recession velocity of a supernova by measuring the redshift of the light from the galaxy in which it lies”. According to ESO (1998), “In astronomy, the redshift (z) denotes the fraction by which the lines in the spectrum of an object are shifted towards longer wavelengths. The observed redshift of a distant galaxy or quasar gives a direct estimate of the universal expansion (i.e. the “recession velocity”). For instance, a redshift of $z = 0.1$ corresponds to a velocity of $30,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ – if this is the case, then objects with high redshifts ($z > 1$) that are advocated to be “slowing down under gravity” have much higher recession velocities as compared to a nearby object (a supernova with a redshift of $z = 0.01$). In fact, as discussed earlier, a direct and official acknowledgement that “highly-redshifted objects are receding faster” has been provided by Nugent (*Research News* 2001) while referring to a highly-redshifted supernova with a redshift (z) of 1.7; Nugent remarks, “highly redshifted objects are moving away from us so fast” (of course, due to expansion). Therefore, it is very disturbing (conflicting) to find that “moving away from us so fast” or every high-redshift (high-recession-velocity) remote expansion ($z = 1.7, z = 6, z = 9.3$) also indicates (simultaneously) a slower rate of expansion (deceleration or “slowing down” under gravity) as compared to low-redshift (low-recession-velocity) local expansion ($z = 0.01, z = 0.015$) that indicates a faster rate of expansion (acceleration or “speeding up”).

(21) If an epoch of “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” can be advocated (Riess et al. 2004), then, epochs of “consecutive expansion that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion” can also be advocated (this paper). It remains undiscovered that an object that begins expanding before in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion (as a result of consecutive expansion) will not only be further away than expected, but it will also be yielding a lower value of slope (or a slower rate of expansion) even with high recession velocity as compared to an object with low recession velocity that begins expanding comparatively later in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion.

(22) Intuitively, an object that begins expanding before (as a result of consecutive expansion) in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion has an utmost probability of being further away than expected; the observational fact, that such an object, which happens to be further away than expected, yields a lower value of slope (a slower rate of expansion (deceleration or “slowing down”)) even with high recession velocity as compared to an object that yields a higher value of slope (a faster rate of expansion (acceleration or “speeding up”)) even with low recession velocity is the most compelling (independent) evidence that serves as a powerful “confirmatory test” (a litmus test)

in favour of “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, rather than “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” (Riess et al. 2004).

(23) There is absolutely no other reason for an object with high recession velocity to yield a lower value of slope (or a slower rate of expansion, thereby suggesting deceleration or slowing down) and then be further away than expected as compared to an object with low recession velocity, unless it began expanding before in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion.

(24) Plotting together the high-recession-velocity remote structures that began expanding before in the preceding epochs of cosmic expansion, and the low-recession-velocity local structures that began expanding comparatively later in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion, causes the Hubble diagram to deviate from linearity.

(25) Comparing the slope and thus the expansion rate of high-recession-velocity remote structures that began expanding before in the preceding epochs of cosmic expansion, with the slope and thus the expansion rate of low-recession-velocity local structures that began expanding comparatively later in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion, causes the high-recession-velocity remote structures to appear as if they are receding slowly (not as fast) as compared to the low-recession-velocity local structures. For this reason, the recession velocity (and hence the redshift) of a remote structure appears to be lower than the recession velocity (and hence the redshift) predicted by the Hubble’s law for a local structure, that is, the Universe appears to be expanding slowly (decelerating) in the past and faster (accelerating) now.

(26) Just like recession velocity, the redshift of a remote structure for which expansion initiated before in the preceding expansion epoch will also appear to be less (or insufficient) when compared to the redshift of a local structure for which expansion initiated comparatively later in the current (or more recent) expansion epoch. One would therefore be forced into believing that the Universe is expanding faster now than it did in the past. This satisfactorily explains why remote supernovae, quasars, and gamma-ray bursts even with very high redshifts (redshifts as high as 1.7, 6, and 9.3 respectively) appear as if they are not expanding as quickly as expected from the observations of the local ones (redshifts as low as 0.01).

(27) An object with high recession velocity (no matter how high) that began expanding before in the preceding expansion epoch will be further away than expected and will appear to be decelerating or “slowing down”, whereas an object with low recession velocity (no matter how low) that began expanding comparatively later in the current (or more recent) expansion epoch will appear to be accelerating or “speeding up”.

(28) Intuitively, objects that began expanding exactly at the same time (in the same expansion epoch) will only yield exactly the same value of slope (will fall exactly on the same line), and will therefore have exactly the same expansion rate (see Figure 9 and Figure 11 – particle J and particle K are the only particles that have exactly the same value of slope (they fall exactly on the same line), and have exactly the same expansion rate as they began expanding exactly at the same time). Same applies for 13 local test particles (P101 to P113) in Figure 26 and Figure 31. In other words, linear expansion is an attribute of expansion in the same epoch, whereas the deviation from linearity is an attribute of expansion in different epochs, that is, “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”.

(29) Velocity-distance relationship for objects (particles and supernovae) (Figure 9, Figure 26, Figure 31, and Figure 38 for particles, Figure 6, Figure 8, and Figure 21 for supernovae) shows distances to remote objects to be larger than expected, that is, “the observed distance to a remote object is larger than the one expected from the locally-measured expansion rate” (consistent with the description given by Durrer (2011)). Remote objects with high recession velocities are not only further away than expected, but they are also yielding a lower value of slope (a shallower slope), or a slower rate of expansion (deceleration or slowing down) as compared to local objects that are yielding a higher value of slope (a steeper slope), or a faster rate of expansion (acceleration or speeding up) even with low recession velocities, that is, high-recession-velocity remote objects appear as if they are receding slowly (not as fast) as

compared to low-recession-velocity local objects (apparent transition of the expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration (remote to local)).

(30) According to Riess and Turner (*Scientific American* 2004), the expansion history of the Universe “is encoded in the relation between the distances and recession velocities of galaxies. If the expansion is speeding up, the distant galaxy’s velocity would fall below the predicted value. Or, to put it another way, a galaxy with a given recession velocity will be farther away than expected – and hence fainter – if the universe is accelerating”. The study conducted in this paper also exhibits such a trend for test particles, then why not also say (based on the velocity-distance relationships obtained for test particles), “If the expansion is speeding up, the distant particle’s velocity would fall below the predicted value. Or, to put it another way, a particle with a given recession velocity will be farther away than expected – and hence fainter – if the expansion is accelerating”.

(31) Expansion rate versus time (time when expansion began) relationship for objects (supernovae and particles) (Figure 10 for supernovae, Figure 11, Figure 27, Figure 32, and Figure 39 for particles) shows further-away-than-expected remote objects yielding a slower rate of expansion (deceleration or “slowing down”) even with high recession velocities as compared to local objects that are yielding a faster rate of expansion (acceleration or “speeding up”) even with low recession velocities (apparent transition of the expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration (remote to local). It must be noted here that the value of the Hubble parameter ($H(t)$) (the expansion rate (H) at time t) varies with time depending on how the scale factor ($a(t)$) varies with time; all this differs from model to model, and, the current value of a model’s Hubble parameter ($H(t)$) constitutes that model’s Hubble constant (H_0) (the current value of that model’s expansion rate) (Jones and Lambourne 2004). In most of the accelerating models, the scale factor ($a(t)$) increases comparatively faster than the rate of change of scale factor ($\dot{a}(t)$), so the Hubble parameter ($H(t)$) or the expansion rate (H) decreases with time in such models as per its following definition,

$$H(t) = \frac{\dot{a}(t)}{a(t)} \quad (19)$$

where, $H(t)$ is the Hubble parameter or the expansion rate at time t , $\dot{a}(t)$ is the rate of change of scale factor at time t or the first time derivative of the scale factor at time t , and $a(t)$ is the scale factor at time t . If the rate of change of scale factor ($a(t)$) is denoted by $\dot{a}(t)$ (first time derivative of the scale factor), then the rate of change of $\dot{a}(t)$ is denoted by $\ddot{a}(t)$ (second time derivative of the scale factor). What defines an accelerating Universe is that the second time derivative ($\ddot{a}(t)$) of the scale factor ($a(t)$) is positive (Jones and Lambourne 2004); this is equivalent to the deceleration parameter (q_0) being negative ($-1 < q_0 < 0$) (see (46) of this section). Now, expansion rate increasing with time would be the attribute of an expansion surpassing the expansion predicted by dark energy that is responsible for the observed acceleration of the Universe. Test particles incorporated in this paper clearly show that the expansion rate (H) is increasing with time (such that the inverse of the slope or the expansion rate (H) obtained from those test particles gives back the time when expansion began for them), such an attribute (expansion rate (H) increasing with time) defines a Universe containing phantom energy ($q_0 < -1$) (an extreme case of dark energy that leads to a Big Rip – the tearing apart of the Universe from galaxy clusters to nucleons). Moreover, large and increasingly negative values for the deceleration parameter (q_0) obtained in Table 3 and Table 4 for test particles (the expansion rate for test particles in $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$ itself being so large), depicts an expansion that has not only surpassed the accelerated expansion due to dark energy ($-1 < q_0 < 0$), but also the super-exponential expansion predicted by phantom energy ($q_0 < -1$).

(32) Observed trends just discussed in (29), (30), and (31) are based on recession velocity interpretation of observed redshifts in an expanding Universe (consistent with the original discovery of cosmic acceleration that itself was based (to a reasonable extent) on measuring the recession velocities of type Ia supernovae from their observed redshifts as discussed in (15) of this section; also refer to the plots by the High- z Team

(Figure 6 and Figure 7)) and are possible only when objects with high recession velocities began expanding in the preceding expansion epochs before the expansion got initiated for objects with low recession velocities in the current (or more recent) expansion epoch, that is, recession velocity interpretation of observed redshifts in an expanding Universe (as shown in Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8, Figure 46, and supported by notable excerpts quoted in (15) of this section) serves as a powerful “confirmatory test” (a litmus test) that alone provides the most compelling and independent evidence in favour of “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, rather than “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” (Riess et al. 2004). Moreover, for test particles incorporated in this paper, it can confidently be appealed that their recession velocities are solely due to expansion or the Hubble flow since the inverse of their slope or the expansion rate (H) gives back the time when expansion began for them; had there been the contribution or addition of any other contaminating velocity component (peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow) to recession velocity arising solely due to expansion or the Hubble flow, then the value of time when expansion began for test particles (obtained from the inverse of their slope or the expansion rate (H)) would have completely been different from the actual value.

(33) According to Vishniac (2021) (American Astronomical Society Journals’ Editor-in-Chief) (private communication (electronic) (December 2021)), as a response to the question, How can every high-recession-velocity (high-redshift) remote expansion ($z > 1$) be justified as deceleration or “slowing down” under gravity as compared to low-recession-velocity (low-redshift) local expansion ($z = 0.01$)? “This particular question can be addressed by reading a standard cosmology text, which will explain that if one compares a distance measure (e.g. the luminosity distance – used for SNe Ia) with redshift, one will recover the local expansion rate as a linear function of redshift and the acceleration as a quadratic term. This implies that the acceleration can only be measured easily by looking at objects with redshifts of order unity”. This provides an answer to the question, “How can we measure cosmic acceleration easily?” It neither answers the question asked nor does it justify the notion of “slowing down” at higher and higher recession velocities ($z > 1$) (reiterating only helped getting the question (and hence the argument) swept under the rug by suggesting that recession velocities (meaningful at low redshifts ($z \ll 1$)) are meaningless at high redshifts ($z > 1$) as discussed in (13) of this section). The question has been parried by providing a completely different or an unrelated answer because there is no possible way to logically justify deceleration or “slowing down” at higher and higher redshifts ($z > 1$) in an expanding Universe, particularly when velocities are quoted – according to Vishniac (2022) (American Astronomical Society Journals’ Editor-in-Chief) (private communication (electronic) (April 2022)) (as discussed in (13) of this section), “As long as the universe is expanding, redshift will always rise for more distant objects. If one insists on quoting a velocity that will also rise”. Now, if one also compares the redshift-distance relationship, or even the velocity-distance relationship (already plotted for test particles in this paper (prior to this private communication)), then one will indeed recover (should have recovered) the local expansion rate as a linear function of redshift (recession velocity) and the deviation from linearity (the “apparent” acceleration of test particles) as a quadratic term, that is, the deviation from linearity (the “apparent” acceleration of test particles) fits using second-order polynomial regression; a second-order polynomial indeed forms a quadratic expression. This should then also imply that the “apparent” acceleration of test particles can only be measured easily by looking at test particles with high redshifts (high recession velocities) or those test particles that deviate from linearity at large distances. It is very upsetting that no consideration of any sort has been given by Vishniac (2021) to this same attribute exhibited by test particles, while confidently suggesting the same for type Ia supernovae.

(34) Expansion factor versus time (time when expansion began) relationship for objects (particles and supernovae, Figure 12 and Figure 13 respectively) shows expansion factor increasing exponentially with time (past to present – remote to local).

(35) Expansion factor versus light-travel-time relationship for objects (particles and supernovae, Figure 14 and Figure 15 respectively) shows expansion factor increasing exponentially with time (past to present – remote to local).

(36) Scale factor versus light-travel-time relationship for objects (supernovae and particles) (Figure 16 for supernovae, Figure 17, Figure 28, and Figure 40 for particles) shows scale factor evolution consistent with a Universe that accelerates with time (past to present – remote to local).

(37) Scale factor versus light-travel-time relationship for objects (particles and supernovae, Figure 18 and Figure 19 respectively) shows scale factor evolution consistent with a Universe that first decelerates, and then accelerates (past to present – remote to local).

(38) Scale factor versus distance relationship for objects (supernovae and particles, Figure 34 and Figure 35 respectively) shows scale factor evolution consistent with a Universe that accelerates with time (past to present – remote to local).

(39) Scale factor versus distance relationship for objects (supernovae and particles, Figure 36 and Figure 37 respectively) shows scale factor evolution consistent with a Universe that first decelerates, and then accelerates (past to present – remote to local).

(40) Distance-redshift relationship for objects (supernovae and particles, Figure 22 and Figure 23 respectively) makes it obvious that high-redshift objects lie above the line; the deviation from linearity makes it clear enough that the distances to remote objects are larger than expected and hence an obvious change in the expansion rate (high-redshift remote expansion appears to be less or insufficient as compared to low-redshift local expansion).

(41) Distance modulus versus redshift relationship for objects (supernovae, quasars, supernovae + GRBs, and particles) (Figure 1, Figure 24, Figure 29, and Figure 42 for supernovae, Figure 2 for quasars, Figure 3 for supernovae + GRBs, Figure 25, Figure 30, Figure 33, and Figure 41 for particles) shows linearity at low redshifts and a deviation from linearity at high redshifts.

(42) Hubble residuals for objects (supernovae, supernovae + GRBs, and particles) (Figure 43 A, Figure 43 B, Figure 43 C, and Figure 43 I for supernovae, Figure 43 H for supernovae + GRBs, Figure 43 D, Figure 43 E, Figure 43 F, Figure 43 G, Figure 43 J, and Figure 43 K for particles) show a slower expansion in the past and faster expansion in the current (or more recent) epoch.

(43) Magnitude-redshift relationship for objects (supernovae and particles, Figure 44 and Figure 45 respectively) also shows linearity at low redshifts and a deviation (12σ deviation and more than 12σ deviation respectively) from linearity at high redshifts. Moreover, it is also shown (as per consecutive expansion epochs that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion) that the $v = cz$ relation can also be used for the non-linear result if the corresponding non-linear value of H (H also obtained using the cz relation) is substituted in Equation (18). And, this is for a very obvious reason, that is, for the linear result or linear expansion (expansion in the same epoch) $H = H_0$, whereas for the non-linear result or non-linear expansion (expansion in different epochs) $H \neq H_0$.

(44) Observed trends just discussed in (34), (35), (36), (37), (38), (39), (40), (41), (42), and (43) are based on redshift interpretation and are possible only when remote objects with high redshifts began expanding in the preceding expansion epochs before the expansion got initiated for local objects with low redshifts in the current (or more recent) expansion epoch, that is, redshift interpretation also provides the most compelling evidence in favour of “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, rather than “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” (Riess et al. 2004).

(45) Moreover, the departure of deceleration parameter (q_0) from positive ($q_0 > 0$) to increasingly negative values ($q_0 < 0$) for the remote type Ia supernova SN 1995K (Table 2) while using more recent or evolving values of expansion rate (H) obtained from 4 type Ia supernovae (remote to local – past to present) suggests past deceleration and recent acceleration. Exact attribute, that is, the departure of deceleration parameter from positive ($q_0 > 0$) to increasingly negative values ($q_0 < 0$) for the remote particles – particle P1 (Table 3) and particle

SN5 (Table 4) while using more recent or evolving values of expansion rate (H) obtained from 4 test particles (Table 3) and 8 test particles (Table 4) respectively should also suggest the same – past deceleration and recent acceleration (remote to local – past to present). It must again be noted that cosmic acceleration due to dark energy yields a negative value for the deceleration parameter ($q_0 < 0$) (more specifically, $-1 < q_0 < 0$), a super-exponential expansion of the Universe predicted by phantom energy (an extreme case of dark energy that leads to a Big Rip – the tearing apart of the Universe from galaxy clusters to nucleons) yields even more negative value for the deceleration parameter ($q_0 < -1$). Large and increasingly negative values for the deceleration parameter (q_0) obtained in Table 3 and Table 4 for test particles (the expansion rate for test particles in $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$ itself being so large) depicts an expansion that has not only surpassed the accelerated expansion due to dark energy ($-1 < q_0 < 0$), but also the super-exponential expansion predicted by phantom energy ($q_0 < -1$).

(46) According to Vishniac (2022) (American Astronomical Society Journals’ Editor-in-Chief (private communication (electronic) (April 2022)), “Terms like deceleration and acceleration refer to the second time derivative of $a(t)$ ”. Now, to be even more precise, if the expansion is slowing down (decelerating), then the second time derivative of the scale factor ($a(t)$) will be negative, if the expansion is speeding up (accelerating), then the second time derivative of the scale factor ($a(t)$) will be positive. Vishniac (2022) has confidently suggested that “Terms like deceleration and acceleration refer to the second time derivative of $a(t)$ ”, but then, it is very upsetting that no consideration of any sort has been given by Vishniac (2022) to the fact that negative values for the deceleration parameter, that is, $q_0 < 0$ (already obtained as per the study conducted in this paper (prior to this private communication)) indeed refers to the second time derivative of $a(t)$, that is, a negative value for the deceleration parameter is equivalent to the second time derivative of $a(t)$ being positive (acceleration) as per the following definition of the deceleration parameter ($q(t)$),

$$q(t) = -\frac{\ddot{a}(t)a(t)}{\dot{a}^2(t)} \quad (20)$$

where $q(t)$ is the deceleration parameter at time t , $a(t)$ is the scale factor at time t , $\dot{a}(t)$ is the first time derivative of the scale factor at time t , and $\ddot{a}(t)$ is the second time derivative of the scale factor at time t . On rearranging (in terms of $\ddot{a}(t)$) we get,

$$\ddot{a}(t) = -\frac{q(t)\dot{a}^2(t)}{a(t)} \quad (21)$$

It is clear from the above rearrangement that if the deceleration parameter ($q(t)$) is negative, then the second time derivative of the scale factor ($a(t)$), that is, $\ddot{a}(t)$ will be positive, in other words, cosmic acceleration.

(47) Therefore, “a purely kinematic interpretation of the test particles’ sample also provides evidence at the greater than 99% confidence level for a transition from deceleration to acceleration” (consistent with the description by Riess et al. (2004)). It might be worth pointing out again that test particles were not at all subjected to acceleration or deceleration, however, we still obtained plots and the deceleration parameter values for test particles that are consistent with an expansion that is not at all slowing down with time, but is speeding up (apparent transition of the expansion from deceleration to acceleration (past to present – remote to local)); remote particles even with high recession velocities (high redshifts) appear as if they are not receding (expanding) as quickly as expected from observations of the local ones; this is exactly what is observed for supernovae, quasars, and gamma-ray bursts. Therefore, such multiple similarities obtained for test particles strongly confirm the study conducted in this paper that happens to be most consistent with “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, rather than “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” (Riess et al. 2004). In agreement with consecutive expansion, remote structures began expanding in the preceding expansion epochs before the expansion got initiated for local structures in the current (or more recent) expansion epoch. Remote supernovae, quasars, and gamma-ray bursts are therefore not only further

away than expected, but they also happen to yield a slower rate of expansion, thereby suggesting their deceleration or “slowing down” even with high recession velocities (high redshifts).

(48) Since consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe “preceded” the current epoch of cosmic expansion, as proved in this paper, therefore, it is prudent to consider that the current epoch of cosmic expansion is definitely not a special epoch; consecutive expansion epochs “succeeding” the current epoch of cosmic expansion are also expected. The expansion rate obtained from such consecutive expansion epochs that will “succeed” or that have already “succeeded” the current epoch of cosmic expansion will also appear to be higher than the expansion rate of the current expansion epoch, again, not because of acceleration, but because the expansion initiated comparatively later. To be more precise, expansion epochs “succeeding” the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion will make the Universe appear to us as if it is not only expanding faster than before but is also younger than before (discussed here in (49) and (50)).

(49) The type of expansion unravelled in this paper would also help solve the “Hubble tension” that has necessitated an immediate need for some new physics beyond Λ CDM (Riess et al. 2019) to explain the discrepancy in the expansion rates of early and late Universe. Based on the undiscovered aspect of expansion unravelled in this paper, only those objects that began expanding exactly at the same time (in the same epoch of cosmic expansion) will be yielding exactly the same expansion rate (as discussed in (28) of this section), in other words, the expansion rate obtained from an object whose expansion initiated before in the preceding expansion epoch will be lower than the expansion rate obtained from an object whose expansion initiated comparatively later in the current (or more recent) expansion epoch. This has already been shown to be valid using test particles (Figure 11, Figure 27, Figure 32, and Figure 39); as a result of consecutive expansion epochs that preceded the current epoch of expansion, the expansion rate for test particles “appears” to have increased over time from past to present (remote to local). Therefore, it is quite concerning if such a value (the one measured in $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$) gets taken into account as a measure of how fast the Universe is expanding; what if this value (the inverse of it, in particular) associates itself with time when expansion began? For instance, an object that began expanding 14.3 billion years ago (in the “preceding” epoch of cosmic expansion) will be yielding a lower expansion rate of $\approx 68 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$, an object that began expanding comparatively later 13.8 billion years ago (in the “current” (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion) will be yielding a higher expansion rate of $\approx 71 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$, and, an object that began expanding 12.2 billion years ago (in the expansion epoch “succeeding” the current epoch of cosmic expansion) will be yielding even a higher expansion rate of $\approx 80 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$. Therefore, the values corresponding to such “apparent expansion rates” should be taken not as the age of the Universe, also, not even as a measure of how fast the Universe is expanding, but more precisely as the time when expansion began for those particular objects (this has already been shown to be valid as per the study conducted in this paper using test particles and will again be proven to be valid here in (50) of this section) – this would help solve not only the Hubble tension, but also an additional perplexing problem that makes the Universe appear to us as if it is not only expanding faster than before but is also younger than before. Particularly, the study conducted in this paper would also help solve the tension pointed out through the study conducted by Riess et al. (2016) that showed that the Universe is not only expanding 9% faster than before but is also younger than before. However, as just discussed here, as well as in (48) of this section, expansion epochs “succeeding” the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion will also have the same effect of making the Universe appear to us as if it is not only expanding faster than before but is also younger than before.

(50) To prove what has just been discussed above in (48) and (49), let us go back and take a look at Section 7. The distance covered by particle B^* in 1 second with a recession velocity of 0.4 m s^{-1} was 0.4 m. According to Equation (1), particle B^* ended up yielding a slope or an expansion rate of $1 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$; according to Equation (2), the inverse of this slope or expansion rate gives back the time when expansion began for particle B^* (1 second ago). Since particle B^* expanded only for 1 second,

therefore, the expansion of particle B^* can be considered as an expansion that occurred very, very recently – just 1 second ago, that is, expansion of particle B^* “succeeds” every expansion epoch of the Universe so far – it “succeeds” an expansion that occurred 14.3 billion years ago ($\approx 68 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$), it “succeeds” an expansion that occurred 13.8 billion years ago ($\approx 71 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$), and, it also “succeeds” an expansion that occurred 12.2 billion years ago ($\approx 80 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$). Consequently, the corresponding value of slope or the expansion rate for particle B^* in terms of $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ turns out to be a whopping $3.0857 \times 10^{19} \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ (for comparison, a slope or an expansion rate of $2.268529021 \times 10^{18} \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$ corresponds to $70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$). Why would particle B^* with a minuscule recession velocity of just 0.4 m s^{-1} end up yielding such a colossal value of expansion rate? Moreover, the deceleration parameter (q_0) value for the remote supernova SN 1995K (Table 2) using this colossal value of expansion rate turns out to be a ground breaking $-2.673460323 \times 10^{18}$. With a negative value of the deceleration parameter so large (the expansion rate itself being so large), such an expansion has not only surpassed the accelerated expansion due to dark energy (observed cosmic acceleration with $-1 < q_0 < 0$), but also the super-exponential expansion predicted by phantom energy (an extreme case of dark energy with $q_0 < -1$ that leads to a Big Rip – the tearing apart of the Universe from galaxy clusters to nucleons); a negative value obtained for the deceleration parameter so large will cause an expansion of the Universe much greater than the super-exponential expansion predicted by phantom energy ($q_0 < -1$) that leads to a Big Rip. A negative value obtained for the deceleration parameter so large makes it imperative to introduce the most overwhelming amount of an energy component to account for this “super acceleration” of the Universe’s expansion even though this particular particle was not at all subjected to acceleration. The expansion of particle B^* ($z \approx 1.3333 \times 10^{-9}$) “succeeding” every expansion epoch of the Universe so far has rendered even a redshift (z) of 0.01 (from the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion) to be insufficient. This makes it evidently clear that expansion epochs “succeeding” the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion will also have the same effect of making the Universe appear to us as if it is not only expanding faster than before but is also younger than before, that is, based on the slope or the expansion rate obtained from particle B^* that underwent expansion just 1 second ago – “succeeding” every expansion epoch of the Universe so far, one would believe (from the inverse of the slope or the expansion rate obtained from particle B^*) that the Universe is just 1 second old (younger than ever) and is expanding faster than ever at a ground-breaking rate of $3.0857 \times 10^{19} \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. As a matter of fact, every test particle that expanded 1 second ago (“succeeding” every expansion epoch of the Universe so far) ends up yielding this colossal, ground-breaking expansion rate of $3.0857 \times 10^{19} \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ – so be it particle B^* from Section 7 (that we just took into account here), or particles J and K (Figure 9), or particles P101 to P113 (Figure 26 and Figure 31), or even particle SN400 (Figure 38). This further provides evidence and again helps confirm the study conducted in this paper that happens to be most consistent with “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion” – an object that began expanding before in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion (as a result of consecutive expansion) will not only be further away than expected, but it will also be yielding a lower value of slope (or a slower rate of expansion, thereby suggesting its deceleration or “slowing down”) even with high recession velocity as compared to an object with low recession velocity that began expanding comparatively later in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion. Moreover, as discussed before, only those objects that began expanding exactly at the same time (in the same epoch of cosmic expansion) will be yielding exactly the same value of slope (will fall exactly on the same line), and will therefore have exactly the same value of expansion rate.

(51) The type of expansion unravelled in this paper would also help solve the “impossible early galaxy problem” – the conundrum that galaxies at high redshifts, especially those observed by the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST), appear as evolved, as bright, and as massive as those at lower redshifts (Gupta 2023). Since expansion has been advocated in this paper

to have begun for remote structures in the preceding epochs of cosmic expansion before it did for local structures in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion, therefore, with the type of expansion unravelled in this paper (consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion) it becomes possible to increase the age of the Universe (particularly at high redshifts, or for the remote part of the Universe); the expansion time or the time when expansion began for remote structures is increased, allowing more time for their formation. Stretching the timeline, especially at high redshifts, allows the formation of large galaxies (Gupta 2023); this would help resolve “the ‘impossible early galaxy’ problem by stretching rather than compressing the timeline for the formation of stars and galaxies as required by the Λ CDM model” (Gupta 2024). According to Gupta (2023), it might be prudent to consider alternative models that *stretch* the timeline, especially at high redshifts, to allow the formation of large galaxies. Moreover, according to Gupta (2024), “If the Universe’s age is established by other methods to be significantly higher than the currently accepted 13.8 Gyr, astrophysicists will be relieved from the burden of constraining stellar ages below 13.8 Gyr”.

(52) The study conducted in this paper does not advocate in any way that we are located in a region of the Universe where the expansion is faster than the remote expansion because of peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow. Instead, the study conducted in this paper explains why the local expansion “appears to be faster” than the remote expansion by unravelling an undiscovered aspect of inhomogeneous expansion based on pure Hubble flow interpretation (recession velocities solely due to the expansion of the Universe). To be more precise, the study conducted in this paper is able to justify this scientifically (or logically) why low-recession-velocity (low-redshift) local expansion “appears to be accelerating or speeding up”, and why high-recession-velocity (high-redshift) remote expansion (comparatively) “appears to be decelerating or slowing down”. A logical justification like this is the plus point of the study conducted in this paper since cosmic acceleration cannot justify logically the notion of “slowing down” at higher and higher recession velocities ($z > 1$). The study conducted in this paper advocates “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion” which is perfectly analogous to (and stems entirely from) the description by Riess et al. (2004), “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration”. According to Starkman et al. (1999), “direct measurements of the cosmic expansion using supernova at redshifts from $z = 0 - 1.2$, suggest that the expansion of our portion of the universe is *accelerating*. The study conducted in this paper perfectly fits with this given description by showing how “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion” can make it “appear” to us “that the expansion of our portion of the universe is *accelerating*”. As long as there are epochs of consecutive expansion (one expansion epoch following the next in a consecutive manner) an observer in any expansion epoch will observe expansion attributes that appear similar to cosmic acceleration, that is, “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” – to an observer in any expansion epoch, preceding expansion epochs will appear to be decelerating or “slowing down”, whereas the observer’s current epoch of cosmic expansion, that happens to “succeed” those preceding epochs of cosmic expansion, will appear to be accelerating or “speeding up”. In reality, however, such an observation would be attributed not to deceleration or acceleration, but to consecutive expansion epochs wherein one expansion epoch is followed by the next in a consecutive manner. The expansion rate of preceding expansion epoch appears to be lower (decelerating or “slowing down”) as compared to the expansion rate of the expansion epoch that succeeds it – a natural feature of consecutive expansion. It is this undiscovered aspect of expansion that “gives the false impression of an increase in the low-redshift expansion rate relative to the high-redshift expansion rate” (excerpt quoted from Riess et al. 1998).

(53) Perhaps the study conducted in this paper is “confusing”, suggests a “complicated history” of Universe’s expansion, and “advocates something other than General Relativity” (Vishniac 2021) (American Astronomical Society Journals’ Editor-in-Chief) (private communication (electronic) (July 2021, May

2021, and July 2021 respectively)). This should be a daunting problem only for those astronomers who like the simplest solutions of General Relativity and do not like considering other, more complicated solutions. According to Professor Subir Sarkar (astroparticle physicist and cosmologist, University of Oxford), “We are in a mess with dark energy. Astronomers like the simplest solutions of General Relativity but there are other, more complicated solutions that we have to consider” (Chalmers 2012). The current Lambda Cold Dark Matter (Λ CDM) standard model of cosmology assumes that Einstein’s General Relativity is valid on all astrophysical scales (Haslbauer et al. 2020). However, there is “mounting evidence that the standard Λ CDM model is in tension at more than 4σ with local direct measurements of the Hubble constant” (Lusso et al. 2019) suggesting new physics beyond Λ CDM (Riess et al. 2019, Lusso et al. 2019). Therefore, does it not become obvious that new physics beyond Λ CDM would also require more complicated solutions that go beyond or even advocate something other than the simplest solutions of General Relativity? Working on alternatives to explain the unknown is a crucial aspect of the scientific process; that is how science progresses; ignoring alternatives is bringing science to a standstill, hampering breakthroughs and discoveries. Therefore, working on an alternative even if it advocates something other than General Relativity is scientifically valid, especially when the results can be reproduced (the study can mimic cosmic acceleration) without requiring a hypothetical energy component of unknown origin having no explanation in fundamental physics (dark energy). This satisfactorily explains why there is no problem and why alarm bells do not ring when General Relativity is replaced with modified Newtonian dynamics (Haslbauer et al. 2020), or when the left-hand side of Einstein’s equation is modified, that is, when gravity is modified (Durrer and Maartens 2008, 2010), or when it is assumed that the graviton (a massless, hypothetical particle) has mass (an assumption that also modifies gravity) (de Rham et al. 2011, de Rham 2014). All such mentioned alternatives (replacement and modifications (tweaks)) have worked pretty well in explaining the unknown. Then why should the study conducted in this paper that perfectly mimics cosmic acceleration be frowned upon if it uses equations that come under the realm of General Relativity to support the claims and help determine the expansion history by taking into account the directly-observable “end points” (or the final readings) of a particular expansion (both near and far)? For instance, taking into consideration the velocity-distance or the redshift-distance relationships for test particles – Figure 9, Figure 26, Figure 31, and Figure 38 (as they are), then using Equation (1), we obtain the expansion rate (H), while the inverse of this expansion rate ($1/H$ or H^{-1}) gives back the time (t_H) when the expansion began for them, using Equation (7), we obtain the scale factor ($a(t)$) evolution with time, using Equation (12), or Equation (12.1), we obtain negative values for the deceleration parameter (q_0), that is, ($q_0 < 0$). Anyway, speaking of a “conceivable model” (based on the type of expansion unravelled in this paper) Vishniac (2021) (American Astronomical Society Journals’ Editor-in-Chief) (private communication (electronic) (February 2021)) states, “The closest General Relativistic version would be to assume that the universe is inhomogeneous with us at, or near, a preferred point”. However, for Vishniac (2021) (American Astronomical Society Journals’ Editor-in-Chief) (private communication (electronic) (May 2021)), “to assume that the universe is inhomogeneous with us at, or near, a preferred point” turns out to be a solution that is “well known and also not attractive” (discussed in (55) and (56) of this section; there we will also discuss why the type of inhomogeneous solution unravelled in this paper is actually, “completely unknown (not yet discovered) and also attractive”). Now, “astronomers who like the simplest solutions of General Relativity and do not like considering other, more complicated solutions” are welcome to model the type of expansion unravelled in this paper using the “simplest solutions of General Relativity”, in fact, everyone is welcome to model the type of expansion unravelled in this paper the way they want, however, they all should keep this in mind that the underlying principle of the type of expansion unravelled in this paper would still remain the same, that is, one expansion epoch following the next in a consecutive manner, or “consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion that preceded

the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, which is perfectly analogous to (and stems entirely from) the description by Riess et al. (2004), “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration”. In other words, the study conducted in this paper lays the “prototype foundation” of an inhomogeneous expansion unravelled based on pure Hubble flow interpretation.

(54) According to Davis (2022) (private communication (electronic) (July 2022)) the study conducted in this paper depicts an expansion that “puts us at the centre of an isotropic but inhomogeneous model”. At the centre of an inhomogeneous model in the sense that expansion began for remote structures in the preceding epochs of cosmic expansion before it did for local structures in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion, and, isotropic in the sense that an observer in any epoch of cosmic expansion observes expansion attributes that appear similar to cosmic acceleration, that is, “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” – to an observer in any epoch of cosmic expansion, preceding epochs of cosmic expansion appear to be decelerating or “slowing down”, whereas the observer’s current epoch of cosmic expansion, that happens to “succeed” those preceding epochs of cosmic expansion, appears to be accelerating or “speeding up”.

(55) According to Vishniac (2021) (American Astronomical Society Journals’ Editor-in-Chief) (private communication (electronic) (February 2021)), “You can fit the SNe distances in various ways. I do not doubt that a fairly simple function will reproduce the data at the price of giving up on statistical homogeneity. This is not terribly interesting. It has always been clear that giving up on statistical homogeneity will allow one to explain high redshift data of any kind”. Also, according to Vishniac (2021) (American Astronomical Society Journals’ Editor-in-Chief) (private communication (electronic) (May 2021)), “the kind of global inhomogeneity that you are postulating is well known to be a way of explaining any dynamical peculiarity in high redshift data”. The cat has been let out of the bag; these statements inadvertently acknowledge that the study conducted in this paper is able to mimic cosmic acceleration. Anyway, to make it very clear, what “is well known to be a way of explaining any dynamical peculiarity in high redshift data” is the inhomogeneous cosmology that advocates our location in a region of the Universe where the expansion is faster than the remote expansion due to local inhomogeneities in the distribution of matter, that is, local inhomogeneities in the distribution of matter add a contaminating velocity component (peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow arising due to gravitational interaction) to recession velocity arising solely due to the expansion of the Universe or the Hubble flow. The addition of this contaminating velocity component (to recession velocity arising solely due to the expansion of the Universe or the Hubble flow) boosts the local expansion rate, thereby giving us “the false impression of an increase in the low-redshift expansion rate relative to the high-redshift expansion rate” (Riess et al. 1998); for this reason, “we go to distances beyond the largest local inhomogeneities so that the recession velocity completely dominates any peculiar velocity” (Shanks et al. 2019). Now, as discussed earlier in (52) of this section, the study conducted in this paper does not advocate in any way that we are located in a region of the Universe where the expansion is faster than the remote expansion. In other words, the study conducted in this paper deals with “an undiscovered aspect of inhomogeneous expansion based on pure Hubble flow interpretation” and does not add or incorporate any contaminating velocity component (peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow) to boost the expansion rate; the study is able to mimic cosmic acceleration and obtains higher expansion rate based on recession velocity arising solely due to the expansion of the Universe or the Hubble flow. Therefore, there is a clear-cut difference between “well-known inhomogeneous cosmologies” (Zehavi et al. 1998, Caldwell and Stebbins 2008, Garcia-Bellido and Haugbølle 2008, Kashlinsky et al. 2008, Räsänen 2008, Watkins et al. 2009, Lavaux et al. 2010, Colin et al. 2011, Tsagas 2011, Räsänen 2011, Colin et al. 2019, Seifert et al. 2024) based on peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow interpretation, and the “completely unknown and therefore a new type of inhomogeneous expansion” unravelled in this paper based on pure Hubble flow interpretation. In even more simple terms, as per the given clear-enough

description of the study conducted in this paper, “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, there is absolutely no place for contaminating velocity component (peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow) to creep in and boost the expansion rate; the quoted description alone is able to mimic cosmic acceleration based on pure Hubble flow interpretation. Therefore, “what is well known to be a way of explaining any dynamical peculiarity in high redshift data” should be the inhomogeneous expansion based on peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow interpretation, and not the inhomogeneous expansion unravelled in this paper based on pure Hubble flow interpretation. It is very upsetting that Vishniac (2021) has missed noticing such a clear-cut difference.

(56) According to Vishniac (2021) (American Astronomical Society Journals’ Editor-in-Chief) (private communication (electronic) (May 2021)), “the kind of global inhomogeneity that you are postulating is also not an attractive solution since one then has to believe that we occupy a privileged position in an inhomogeneous universe”. Then why not also consider, “Dark energy may not be an attractive proposition”, admits Professor Brian Schmidt; it requires us to invent 73% of the Universe (Chalmers 2012). Anyway, to make it very clear, what makes one “believe that we occupy a privileged position in an inhomogeneous universe”, is again, the inhomogeneous cosmology that advocates our location in a “privileged or a special” region of the Universe where the expansion is faster than the remote expansion due to local inhomogeneities in the distribution of matter, that is, contaminating velocity component arising due to gravitational interaction (peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow) creeps in and boosts the local expansion rate. The studies conducted by Zehavi et al. (1998), Caldwell and Stebbins (2008), Garcia-Bellido and Haugbølle (2008), Kashlinsky et al. (2008), Räsänen (2008), Watkins et al. (2009), Lavaux et al. (2010), Colin et al. (2011), Tsagas (2011), Räsänen (2011), Colin et al. (2019), Seifert et al. (2024) come under this category (studies conducted by Zehavi et al. (1998), Kashlinsky et al. (2008), and Lavaux et al. (2010), in particular, have been published by the American Astronomical Society itself). Now, if homogeneity is to be retained, then inhomogeneous solutions should have not been published in reputed journals as an alternative to dark energy, unless the academic review process is strongly biased towards established names in the field (Huber et al. 2022), or “the Matthew effect in science” – according to Merton (1968), “The Matthew effect may serve to heighten the visibility of contributions to science by scientists of acknowledged standing and to reduce the visibility of contributions by authors who are less well known”. For instance, the study conducted by Zehavi et al. (1998) (published by the American Astronomical Society itself) found that type Ia supernovae out to 7000 km s⁻¹ exhibit an expansion rate that is 6% greater than that measured for the more distant objects (Riess et al. 1998); their study based on the peculiar velocities of 44 type Ia supernovae clearly makes us occupy a privileged position in an inhomogeneous Universe (“near the centre of a roughly spherical void”) where the expansion rate is 6% greater than that measured for the more distant region. Now, if “inhomogeneity is not an attractive solution since one then has to believe that we occupy a privileged position in an inhomogeneous universe”, as suggested by Vishniac (2021) (American Astronomical Society Journals’ Editor-in-Chief) (private communication (electronic) (May 2021)), then why has this particular paper by Zehavi et al. (1998) been considered by the American Astronomical Society as an alternative to dark energy? Will the American Astronomical Society retract this particular paper by Zehavi et al. (1998)? The study conducted by Jha et al. (2007) (also published by the American Astronomical Society itself) also shows a void signature, similar in both location and amplitude to the Zehavi et al. (1998) result. Their study finds a 6.5% offset between the Hubble constant (H_0) measured from the nearby Hubble flow sample of type Ia supernovae (2500 km s⁻¹ < cz < 7400 km s⁻¹) and the Hubble constant (H_0) measured from the distant Hubble flow sample of type Ia supernovae (7400 km s⁻¹ < cz < 45,000 km s⁻¹). According to them, “Regardless of whether the Hubble bubble is due to a real local void in the universe or an artifact of SN Ia distances, the feature is present in the Hubble flow SN sample”. Therefore, on a similar note, why has this particular paper by Jha et al. (2007)

been considered by the American Astronomical Society if it also shows a void signature or the feature of a Hubble bubble similar to the Zehavi et al. (1998) result? Will the American Astronomical Society retract this particular paper by Jha et al. (2007)? According to Garcia-Bellido and Haugbølle (2008), “The possibility that we live in a special place in the universe, close to the centre of a large void, *seems an appealing alternative* to the prevailing interpretation of the acceleration of the universe in terms of a Λ CDM model with a dominant dark energy component”. Therefore, it would be wrong to say that these inhomogeneity-based studies, including those that make us occupy a privileged position in the Universe, close to the centre of a large void (Zehavi et al. 1998, Caldwell and Stebbins 2008, Garcia-Bellido and Haugbølle 2008), do not provide an attractive solution to the dark energy problem. According to Clarkson and Maartens (2010), inhomogeneous solutions should be considered even if they are philosophically uncomfortable, particularly in light of the fact that they can explain away the dark energy problem through inhomogeneity. It is particularly for this reason that the paper by Zehavi et al. (1998) has been considered and published by the American Astronomical Society itself as an alternative to dark energy even when their study makes us occupy a privileged position in an inhomogeneous Universe (“near the centre of a roughly spherical void”), but then, it is very upsetting that the study conducted in this paper gets deemed by Vishniac (2021) (American Astronomical Society Journals’ Editor-in-Chief) as “not an attractive solution since one then has to believe that we occupy a privileged position in an inhomogeneous universe”. Now, on one hand where the studies conducted by Zehavi et al. (1998), Caldwell and Stebbins (2008), Garcia-Bellido and Haugbølle (2008), Kashlinsky et al. (2008), Räsänen (2008), Watkins et al. (2009), Lavaux et al. (2010), Colin et al. (2011), Tsagas (2011), Räsänen (2011), Colin et al. (2019), Seifert et al. (2024) rely on contaminating velocity component (peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow) for boosting the expansion rate, the study conducted in this paper on the other hand relies only on recession velocity arising solely due to the expansion of the Universe or pure Hubble flow to obtain higher expansion rate – this is what draws a dividing line between “well-known inhomogeneous cosmologies” (Zehavi et al. 1998, Caldwell and Stebbins 2008, Garcia-Bellido and Haugbølle 2008, Kashlinsky et al. 2008, Räsänen 2008, Watkins et al. 2009, Lavaux et al. 2010, Colin et al. 2011, Tsagas 2011, Räsänen 2011, Colin et al. 2019, Seifert et al. 2024) based on peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow interpretation, and the “completely unknown and therefore a new type of inhomogeneous expansion” unravelled in this paper based on pure Hubble flow interpretation. Therefore, “the kind of global inhomogeneity that is not an attractive solution since one then has to believe that we occupy a privileged position in an inhomogeneous universe”, should be the inhomogeneous expansion based on peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow interpretation, and not the inhomogeneous expansion unravelled in this paper based on pure Hubble flow interpretation. If inhomogeneous expansion based on peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow interpretation that makes us occupy a privileged position in the Universe can be an appealing alternative to dark energy (as suggested by Garcia-Bellido and Haugbølle 2008) (with studies conducted by Zehavi et al. 1998, Caldwell and Stebbins 2008, Garcia-Bellido and Haugbølle 2008, Kashlinsky et al. 2008, Räsänen 2008, Watkins et al. 2009, Lavaux et al. 2010, Colin et al. 2011, Tsagas 2011, Räsänen 2011, Colin et al. 2019, Seifert et al. 2024 coming under this category), then the inhomogeneous expansion unravelled in this paper based on pure Hubble flow interpretation that also makes us occupy a privileged position in the Universe can also be an appealing alternative to dark energy, in fact, the inhomogeneous solution unravelled in this paper is far more appealing than the inhomogeneous solutions published in the literature in the sense that it is able to mimic cosmic acceleration based on pure Hubble flow interpretation alone and does not require the addition or incorporation of any contaminating velocity component (peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow) to boost the expansion rate. It is again very upsetting that Vishniac (2021) has missed noticing all these clear-cut differences as well.

(57) Moreover, if it is the description of the study conducted in this paper, “consecutive expansion epochs ‘that preceded the current epoch’ of cosmic expansion” that makes one believe

that we occupy a privileged position, then one should also consider the similar description by Riess et al. (2004), “cosmic deceleration ‘that preceded the current epoch’ of cosmic acceleration”. Since the study conducted in this paper is perfectly analogous to (and stems entirely from) this description given by Riess et al. (2004), therefore, from their (Riess et al. 2004) description, the “current epoch” also gets rendered special or privileged; it seems that we are living in a privileged or a very special epoch of cosmic expansion – we are not only lucky to witness the recent onset of cosmic acceleration in the *current epoch* (other observers were unlucky and probably depressed witnessing a decelerating Universe), but we are also more than lucky to witness this recent onset in an epoch when the dark energy density is approximately equal to the matter density (“the coincidence scandal: why is the dark energy density approximately equal to the matter density today?” (Carroll 2004)). “How finely-tuned is it that we exist in the era when vacuum and matter are comparable?” (Carroll 2004). Moreover, in order to justify the small observed value of the cosmological constant or the vacuum energy (as compared to the 10^{120} times larger theoretically-calculated value obtained according to the quantum field theory), we have to entertain the idea that there are infinite number of Universes with different values of the vacuum energy in each (Chalmers 2012) – so far so good, but then, to make things worse, we are “extremely privileged” to be a part of a Universe (one of infinite!) in which the cosmological constant or the vacuum energy takes on the observed small and gentle value for life to exist.

(58) According to Carroll (2004), “there is an approximately 1% chance that an observer living in a randomly selected logarithmic expansion interval in the history of our universe would be lucky enough to have Ω_M and Ω_Λ be the same order of magnitude” – fine-tuning involved; substantial, but not completely ridiculous according to Carroll (2004). If such a slim chance can be considered a possibility even when it involves an unnatural fine-tuning which has been deemed substantial, but not completely ridiculous by Carroll (2004), then why not also consider the possibility that the current epoch of cosmic expansion was preceded by consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion (one expansion epoch following the next in a consecutive manner). Such an interpretation imparts the liberty to an observer located in any epoch of cosmic expansion to observe expansion attributes that appear similar to cosmic acceleration, therefore, there is nothing special about the current epoch – the apparent transition of the Universe’s expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration is observed in every epoch of cosmic expansion – to an observer located in any epoch of cosmic expansion, preceding epochs of cosmic expansion appear to be decelerating or “slowing down”, whereas the observer’s current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion, that happens to “succeed” those preceding epochs of cosmic expansion, appears to be accelerating or “speeding up”.

(59) The aim of the study conducted in this paper is to help unravel an undiscovered aspect of inhomogeneous expansion based on pure Hubble flow interpretation that perfectly mimics cosmic acceleration and *not* to advocate that we occupy a privileged or a special position in the Universe. Of course, the way expansion has been depicted in this paper using test particles (consecutive expansion epochs that preceded the “current epoch” of cosmic expansion) makes it obvious that we occupy a privileged or a special position in the Universe (vantage-dependent) as discussed in (54) and (56) of this section. However, it is only for making the demonstration of the type of expansion depicted in this paper relatable to the mapping of the Universe’s expansion history using type Ia supernovae, that a reference or a vantage point has been chosen, after all, the way researchers map the expansion history of the Universe using type Ia supernovae is from our reference or vantage point; no one makes a teleporting trip to a distant region of the Universe to verify what the expansion rate there is (it is “assumed” that a distant region of the Universe is undergoing the same rate of expansion as here). According to Professor Subir Sarkar (astroparticle physicist and cosmologist, University of Oxford), “It is an assumption to say that a distant region of the Universe is undergoing the same rate of expansion as here. The expansion rate would vary in space – not just in time – in an inhomogeneous Universe” (Chalmers 2012). Moreover, even if a vantage or a reference point has been

chosen, an important question that needs to be answered is – why does the type of inhomogeneous expansion unravelled in this paper (consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion) based on pure Hubble flow interpretation (recession velocities arising solely due to expansion) mimic cosmic acceleration so perfectly well, particularly when there is no contribution in any way of any additional (contaminating or boosting) velocity component (peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow)?

(60) Interestingly, as it happens to turn out, the study conducted in this paper is also vantage-independent at the same time – the study essentially shows how one expansion epoch following the next in a consecutive manner (consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion) can mimic cosmic acceleration, that is, if there are epochs of consecutive expansion (one expansion epoch following the next in a consecutive manner), then intuitively, no matter which epoch of cosmic expansion an observer is located in, there will be epochs of consecutive expansion preceding the observer’s epoch of cosmic expansion, and there will be epochs of consecutive expansion succeeding the observer’s epoch of cosmic expansion; the Universe will therefore appear to be accelerating to an observer from any reference point, that is, preceding epochs of cosmic expansion will appear to be decelerating or slowing down as compared to the epoch of cosmic expansion that succeeds them. As just discussed in (59), according to Professor Subir Sarkar (astroparticle physicist and cosmologist, University of Oxford), “It is an assumption to say that a distant region of the Universe is undergoing the same rate of expansion as here. The expansion rate would vary in space – not just in time – in an inhomogeneous Universe” (Chalmers 2012). Therefore, based on the inhomogeneous expansion unravelled in this paper, one does not have to rely on this “assumption” that a distant region of the Universe is undergoing the same rate of expansion as here, because, the type of inhomogeneous expansion unravelled in this paper makes it evidently clear that a distant region of the Universe will *not* be undergoing the same rate of expansion as here – this “evidence” is better than an “assumption” and provides a new hope to help solve the Hubble tension (discussed earlier).

(61) The value of the Hubble constant (H_0) derived by Jha et al. (2007) is 6.5% higher using a Hubble flow sample of type Ia supernovae with recession velocities of $2500 \text{ km s}^{-1} < cz < 7400 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ as compared to a Hubble flow sample of type Ia supernovae with recession velocities of $7400 \text{ km s}^{-1} < cz < 45,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. One natural explanation for this offset according to Conley et al. (2007) is a “Hubble bubble” or a local monopole in the peculiar velocity field, perhaps caused by a local void in the mass density. According to Jha et al. (2007), “Regardless of whether the Hubble bubble is due to a real local void in the universe or an artifact of SN Ia distances, the feature is present in the Hubble flow SN sample”. If Jha et al. (2007) can use the Hubble flow recession velocities of type Ia supernovae in their analysis and present evidence for a “Hubble bubble”, then, as per the study conducted in this paper that also uses the Hubble flow recession velocities in the analysis, why not also say, “regardless of whether the type of expansion unravelled in this paper “puts us at the centre of an isotropic but inhomogeneous model” (Davis 2022), or makes us “occupy a privileged position in an inhomogeneous universe” (Vishniac 2021), the feature of “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion” is present in the Hubble flow sample of type Ia supernovae, quasars, and gamma-ray bursts”. As already discussed in Section 6 itself, recession velocity interpretation of observed redshifts in an expanding Universe (as shown in Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8, Figure 46, and supported by notable excerpts quoted in (15) of this section) serves as a powerful “confirmatory test” (a litmus test) that alone provides the most compelling (independent) evidence in favour of “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, rather than “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” (Riess et al. 2004), that is, with respect to Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8, Figure 46, and the notable excerpts quoted in (15) of this section, a further-away-than-expected object with high recession velocity will end up yielding a lower value of slope (or a slower rate of expansion, thereby suggesting its deceleration or “slowing down”) as compared

to an object with low recession velocity, only if it began expanding before in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion. As discussed in (13) of this section, recession velocity interpretation of observed redshifts in an expanding Universe is *not* “just a convention” (Vishniac 2022), it is a “useful convention” that can be used as a test to help confirm independently the undiscovered aspect of expansion unravelled in this paper in the most compelling manner.

(62) Some of the primary advantages/salient features of the study conducted in this paper are summarized here, these include: **(i)** the study does not question the observations carried out by the Nobel Prize-winning teams (the observations that showed remote supernovae are further away than expected (Riess et al. 1998 and Perlmutter et al. 1999)); in fact, the study conducted in this paper takes into consideration the observations carried out by the Nobel Prize-winning teams and helps provide a robust and a novel explanation/interpretation why remote supernovae, quasars, and GRBs would end up being further away than expected without acceleration, **(ii)** the study does not make any modifications to gravity, **(iii)** the study is free from complications associated with an accelerating Universe and hypothetical dark energy of unknown origin having no explanation in fundamental physics, **(iv)** the study, “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion” is perfectly analogous to (and stems entirely from) the description by Riess et al. (2004), “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration”, therefore, the study is most likely to provide the “subtle reason” (Filippenko 2001) that the researchers have been looking for ever since the unexpected discovery of cosmic acceleration, that is, “consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion that preceded” works analogous to in producing the apparent effect of “cosmic deceleration that preceded”, whereas “the current epoch of cosmic expansion” works analogous to in producing the apparent effect of “the current epoch of cosmic acceleration”, **(v)** the study unravels “an undiscovered aspect of inhomogeneous expansion” based on pure Hubble flow interpretation alone (recession velocities arising solely due to the expansion of the Universe), that is, the study does not add or incorporate any contaminating velocity component (peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow) to boost the expansion rate; the study is able to mimic cosmic acceleration and obtains higher expansion rate based on recession velocity arising solely due to the expansion of the Universe (pure Hubble flow), **(vi)** since the study deals with inhomogeneous expansion based on pure Hubble flow interpretation, therefore, it becomes possible to rely on any redshift or recession velocity as low as possible without having to worry about any contaminating velocity component (peculiar velocity/bulk flow/outflow) while modelling the expansion, **(vii)** based on pure Hubble flow interpretation, the study is able to justify why local expansion “appears to be faster” than remote expansion, or why high-recession-velocity remote expansion “appears to be decelerating or slowing down” as compared to low-recession-velocity local expansion. Since cosmic acceleration cannot justify logically the notion of “slowing down” at higher and higher recession velocities ($z > 1$), therefore, the ability to logically justify this notion forms the plus point of the study conducted in this paper and imparts it the added advantage over cosmic acceleration, **(viii)** unlike cosmic acceleration that renders the current epoch very special (we are not only lucky to witness the recent onset of cosmic acceleration in the *current epoch* (other observers were unlucky and probably depressed witnessing a decelerating Universe), but we are also more than lucky to witness this recent onset in an epoch when the dark energy density is approximately equal to the matter density), the study conducted in this paper imparts the liberty to an observer located in any epoch of cosmic expansion to observe expansion attributes that appear similar to cosmic acceleration, therefore, there is nothing special about the current epoch; past deceleration and recent acceleration manifest in every epoch – preceding epochs of cosmic expansion appear to be decelerating or slowing down as compared to the epoch of cosmic expansion that succeeds them, that is, the “apparent” transition of the Universe’s expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration is observed in every epoch of cosmic expansion, **(ix)** the type of expansion unravelled in this paper provides a more natural solution to explain the further-away-than-expected placement of

remote objects. It is practically more feasible to consider that expansion began for objects in different epochs of cosmic expansion, rather than at the same time or in the same epoch of cosmic expansion. It is practically impossible that all objects would have expanded at the same time or in the same epoch of cosmic expansion. What seems more possible explanation to account for the further-away-than-expected placement of remote objects is that expansion began for remote objects in the preceding epochs of cosmic expansion before it did for local objects in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion, **(x)** since expansion has been advocated in this paper to have begun for remote structures in the preceding epochs of cosmic expansion before it did for local structures in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion, therefore, with the type of expansion unravelled in this paper (consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion) it becomes possible to increase the age of the Universe (particularly at high redshifts, or for the remote part of the Universe); the expansion time or the time when expansion began for remote structures is increased allowing more time for their formation. *Stretching* the timeline, especially at high redshifts, allows the formation of large galaxies (Gupta 2023); this would help solve the “impossible early galaxy problem”. According to Gupta (2023), it might be prudent to consider alternative models that *stretch* the timeline, especially at high redshifts, to allow the formation of large galaxies. Also, “If the Universe’s age is established by other methods to be significantly higher than the currently accepted 13.8 Gyr, astrophysicists will be relieved from the burden of constraining stellar ages below 13.8 Gyr” (Gupta 2024), **(xi)** the type of inhomogeneous expansion unravelled in this paper makes it evidently clear that a distant region of the Universe will *not* be undergoing the same rate of expansion as here – this “evidence” is better than an “assumption” that a distant region of the Universe is undergoing the same rate of expansion as here; according to Professor Subir Sarkar (astroparticle physicist and cosmologist, University of Oxford), “It is an assumption to say that a distant region of the Universe is undergoing the same rate of expansion as here. The expansion rate would vary in space – not just in time – in an inhomogeneous Universe” (Chalmers 2012); this “evidence” that is better than an “assumption” provides a new hope to help solve the Hubble tension (discussed earlier), **(xii)** an additional aspect unravelled in this paper based on “expansion epochs of the Universe “succeeding” the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion” would help solve the Hubble tension that has necessitated an immediate need for some new physics beyond Λ CDM (Riess et al. 2019, Lusso et al. 2019) (discussed earlier), **(xiii)** this additional aspect discussed above in (xii) would also help solve an additional perplexing problem that makes the Universe appear to us as if it is “not only expanding faster than before but is also younger than before” (Riess et al. 2016) (discussed earlier).

(63) Since the apparent transition of the Universe’s expansion from past deceleration to recent acceleration still cannot be explained; we are still searching for an explanation since 1998 – “Unfortunately, no obvious breakthrough in our understanding has yet occurred – cosmic acceleration remains the same mystery that it was in 1998” (Schmidt 2012) – “probably one of the greatest challenges in modern physics” (Ezquiaga and Zumalacárregui 2017) – mysterious and hypothetical dark energy of unknown origin having no explanation in fundamental physics (“the dark energy puzzle”), the colossal 120-orders-of-magnitude discrepancy – a mismatch between the small observed value and the huge theoretically-calculated value of the energy associated with empty space or the vacuum energy according to the quantum field theory by an alarming 120 orders of magnitude (10^{120}) (“the cosmological constant problem”), the fact that we are not only lucky to witness the recent onset of cosmic acceleration in the current epoch (other observers were unlucky and probably depressed witnessing a decelerating Universe), but we are also more than lucky to witness this recent onset in an epoch when the dark energy density is approximately equal to the matter density (“the coincidence scandal”), and finally, the “mounting evidence that the standard Λ CDM model is in tension at more than 4σ with local direct measurements of the Hubble constant” (Lusso et al. 2019) suggesting new physics beyond Λ CDM (Riess et al. 2019, Lusso et al. 2019);

a tension that is confirmed to be “at $> 4\sigma$ with the whole SNe Ia + quasars + GRB data set” (Lusso et al. 2019), we therefore need to consider the study conducted in this paper (“consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”) that perfectly mimics cosmic acceleration (“cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration”) based on multiple similarities (replication and reproduction of results) obtained in a single paper while plotting velocity-distance relationship, expansion rate vs. time relationship, expansion factor vs. time relationship, scale factor vs. time relationship, scale factor vs. distance relationship, distance-redshift relationship, distance modulus vs. redshift relationship, Hubble residuals, and magnitude-redshift relationship, moreover, and most importantly, the deceleration parameter (q_0) was also found to be departing from positive ($q_0 > 0$) to increasingly negative values ($q_0 < 0$) while using more recent or evolving values of the expansion rate (H) as measured from past to present (remote to local).

(64) Since the study conducted in this paper mimics cosmic acceleration by taking into consideration the distance measurements and their relation to redshift based on observations pertaining to type Ia supernovae, quasars, and GRBs only (with type Ia supernova observations providing the direct and the best observational evidence for cosmic acceleration and hence for the existence of dark energy), therefore, researchers, especially the proponents of cosmic acceleration may oppose and undermine the study conducted in this paper by saying that they have other data (or additional probes) as evidence for cosmic acceleration and dark energy, such as, baryon acoustic oscillations (BAO) in the large-scale distribution of galaxies, temperature fluctuations in the cosmic microwave background (CMB), measurement of stellar ages, the rate of growth of structure, etc., however, as pointed out by Mohayaee et al. (2021), these additional probes “are all ‘concordant’ with the standard Λ CDM cosmological model but do not provide independent evidence for accelerated expansion”. More precisely, “cosmic microwave background anisotropies and observations of baryon acoustic oscillations simply tell us that the observed distance to a given redshift z is larger than the one expected from a Friedmann–Lemaître universe with matter only and the locally measured Hubble parameter” (Durrer 2011); nothing different than what one gets using type Ia supernovae, quasars, and GRBs. Anyway, if the proponents of cosmic acceleration are so confident with the fact that the evidence for an accelerating Universe from type Ia supernovae-only sample is greater than 6σ (Scolnic et al. 2018), then, additional probes, that neither provide independent nor direct evidence for cosmic acceleration and require a particular cosmological model (Λ CDM) to infer cosmic acceleration, become unnecessary; just type Ia supernovae, that provide the direct and the best observational evidence for cosmic acceleration, should suffice as the central dataset in any analysis (including this paper); it is basically for this reason that researchers, who question the discovery of cosmic acceleration and come up with alternatives to explain the unknown, keep type Ia supernovae as the central dataset in their analysis; their ideas, not only get published in top-notch scientific journals, but also gain special coverage from the mainstream media (Colin et al. 2011, Nielsen et al. 2016, Colin et al. 2019, Kang et al. 2020, Mohayaee et al. 2021, Seifert et al. 2024).

(65) We should keep this in mind and not forget that the discovery of accelerating Universe came as a complete surprise to the research teams (HZT and SCP) – it was an unexpected discovery. According to Filippenko (2001), “This was not the answer we had expected, and many members of the HZT were worried that a subtle error had been made; indeed, Bob Kirshner reflected that “deep in our hearts, we know this can’t be right”. “The conclusion reached by the HZT and SCP is so dramatic, so “crazy” in some respects, that it behooves us to find an alternative explanation” (Filippenko 2001).

(66) Had the study conducted in this paper (that happens to be most consistent with “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”) been on the wrong track by not being in agreement with, or not being perfectly analogous to “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” (Riess et al. 2004), then the results obtained in this paper would have completely been different; replication and reproduction of

results would have not worked at all. Velocity-distance or the redshift-distance relationships obtained for test particles through “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion” are so identical to the velocity-distance or the redshift-distance relationships obtained for type Ia supernovae through actual observations pertaining to “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” (Riess et al. 2004), that if all those plots are placed side by side, then by just looking at the relative positions of objects on those plots, “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” would be inferred by a proponent of cosmic acceleration for all the plots.

(67) Of course, sending the plots as they are to a proponent of cosmic acceleration to infer if there is acceleration or not would not reveal to the proponent any details regarding how those plots have been obtained. The plots would only reveal the plotted data points (which actually are the end results of a particular expansion (both near and far)); the plots would only show that there is a deviation from linearity at large distances, or that the distances to remote objects are significantly larger than expected with respect to the local objects – nothing different from what is observed on the plot for type Ia supernovae. Therefore, not knowing how the plots have been obtained, a proponent of cosmic acceleration is expected to “play it safe” and would refrain from inferring acceleration even when the plots have ended up being not any different, for instance, with respect to Figure 9 that was sent as it is along with the request to help decode the expansion history depicted by 11 data points on that plot and to infer if there is acceleration or deceleration, the inference drawn by Riess (2024) (private communication (electronic) (January 2024)) was that the distances (what have been plotted) versus luminosity distances (what is observed from supernovae) differ by a factor of $(1 + z)$. Now, to help settle this difference and to make the definition of distances clear, it might be worth recalling that Figure 9 is the resultant plot for test particles that were subjected to “expansion”, and, the distances plotted for them are indeed those distances that are based purely on their Hubble flow expansion dynamics, such that, the inverse of the slope or the expansion rate (H) obtained from those test particles gives back the time when expansion began for them (had we been dealing with any other distances, then the value of time when expansion began for test particles (obtained from the inverse of their slope or the expansion rate (H)), would have completely been different from the actual value). Anyway, even if the plot (Figure 9) was sent (as it is) to infer the expansion history (if there is acceleration or deceleration), an important question that arises based on the inference drawn by Riess (2024), is – is it really the factor of $(1 + z)$ that provides a strong indication or a direct observational evidence from type Ia supernova observations for an accelerating Universe? The answer is, No! The factor of $(1 + z)$ manifests as a result of expansion (the expansion of the Universe) and it is not a direct evidence for cosmic acceleration. According to Durrer (2011), what do we really measure from type Ia supernova observations that provide a strong indication of an accelerating Universe is just the distance-redshift relation; all data support a measurement of distance which is significantly larger than the one expected from the locally-measured expansion rate. Therefore, if all data support a measurement of distance which is significantly larger than the one expected from the locally-measured expansion rate, then, rather than “playing it safe”, the following should have been the inferences drawn based on the relative positions of objects on those plots, (a) remote objects are further away than expected, implying a high local value of H_0 (consistent with the description given by Conley et al. (2007)), (b) remote objects are not only further away than expected, but they are also yielding a lower value of slope (a shallower slope), or a slower rate of expansion (deceleration or “slowing down”) even with high recession velocities as compared to the local objects that are yielding a higher value of slope (a steeper slope), or a faster rate of expansion (acceleration or “speeding up”) even with low recession velocities, (c) direct measurements of the expansion using the objects suggest that the expansion of our portion of the Universe is *accelerating* (consistent with the description given by Starkman et al. (1999)), (d) the observed distance to a remote object is larger than the one expected from the locally-measured expansion rate (consistent with the description given by Durrer (2011)), (e) distant object’s velocity

is falling below the predicted value. Or, to put it another way, an object with a given recession velocity is farther away than expected as the Universe is accelerating (consistent with the description given by Riess and Turner (*Scientific American* 2004)), (f) high-redshift or high-recession-velocity remote objects are receding slowly (not as fast, therefore, decelerating or “slowing down”) as compared to low-redshift or low-recession-velocity local objects.

(68) It would be fruitful to recall on a concluding note that directly-observable quantities play an important role in observational cosmology. Since the luminosity distance helps probe the expansion history of the Universe up to that redshift, therefore, in an expanding Universe, the directly-observable luminosity distance and the directly-observable redshift associated with type Ia supernova observations can be considered as the directly-observable “end points” (or the final readings) of a particular expansion (both near and far) that help us determine the expansion history of the Universe; it is only when a type Ia supernova attains peak luminosity that researchers make a note of its luminosity and the redshift associated with it – luminosity helps measure the distance, whereas the redshift helps measure how fast the supernova is receding from us. Therefore, if the directly-observable “end points” (or the final readings) of a particular expansion show to us that a distant, remote object is further away than expected and is yielding a lower value of slope, or a slower rate of expansion, thereby suggesting its deceleration or “slowing down” even with high recession velocity as compared to a nearby, local object with low recession velocity (that is, if distant object’s velocity is falling below the predicted value as per the description by Riess and Turner (*Scientific American* 2004)), then the inference drawn should be “consecutive expansion epochs of the Universe that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”, rather than “cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” (Riess et al. 2004).

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CONTRIBUTION

The author (Karan R. Takkhi) participated in the analysis and in writing this paper.

ORCID iD

Karan R. Takkhi <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3859-6511>

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